

GOOD PRACTICES OF SUSTAINABLE AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
EU	European Union
GreenComp	European Sustainability Competence Framework
SD	Sustainable Development
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
UDL	Universal Design for Learning
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Glossary

Term	Definition
Action Competence	The ability to act intentionally and effectively in sustainability-related issues with confidence and responsibility (Mogensen & Schnack, 2010).
Collective Action	Collaborative efforts by groups to address shared sustainability issues or achieve common goals (UNESCO, 2020).
Community engagement	Community engagement is a collaborative process through which educational institutions actively partner with local communities to identify needs, co-create solutions, and implement actions that promote mutual learning and sustainable development. It involves authentic, reciprocal relationships that empower both students and community members, often through mechanisms like service learning, participatory research, and civic action. Rodríguez-Zurita et al. (2024)
Critical Thinking	The ability to question norms, evaluate evidence, and reflect on assumptions to support informed decision-making in sustainability contexts (UNESCO, 2017).
Experiential learning	Experiential learning is defined as a dynamic, cyclical process through which learners construct knowledge by engaging directly with real-world environments, followed by structured reflection, conceptual understanding, and practical application. In the context of environmental education, it involves in-situ, inquiry-based learning—such as fieldwork in natural reserves—where experience, reflection, abstraction, and action come together to develop ecological awareness and sustainability competencies (Crespo-Castellanos et al., 2024).
Four Dimensions of Sustainability	The environmental, social, economic, and cultural dimensions that underpin comprehensive approaches to sustainability (UNESCO, 2017).
Futures Thinking / Futures Literacy	The capacity to imagine and evaluate possible future scenarios and make informed choices to shape sustainable futures (Miller, 2015).
Individual Initiative	Personal motivation and proactivity in engaging with sustainability challenges and solutions (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022).

Personalized support system	A personalized support system is a structured, responsive framework that tailors educational resources, instructional strategies, and interventions to meet the individual academic, social, emotional, and developmental needs of each learner—particularly those at risk of exclusion—by using data, learner profiles, and adaptive tools to ensure equitable participation and success (Romero García & Pedró Ostáriz, 2023).
Planetary Well-being	A concept that frames human well-being within the ecological limits of Earth’s systems, linking health, sustainability, and equity (Kortetmäki et al., 2021).
Political Agency	The capacity of individuals or groups to influence decision-making and advocate for sustainability policies and practices (UNESCO, 2020).
Project-based Learning	A student-centered teaching method in which learners gain knowledge and skills by working over an extended period to investigate and respond to real-world questions, problems, or challenges. PBL emphasizes collaboration, critical thinking, and application of knowledge in practical contexts (Larmer & Boss, 2015).
Student-led initiative	Actions, practices, or projects initiated and promoted by students either at a school or higher education level, with support from teachers and other staff members.
Student empowerment	Student empowerment refers to the process of enabling students to take control of their own learning by giving them the autonomy, voice, and responsibility to make decisions about their education. Empowered students are actively involved in setting goals, making choices, and reflecting on their learning, fostering a sense of ownership and intrinsic motivation (Zimmerman, 1995). Student empowerment in sustainability education refers to the process of enabling learners to actively participate in decision-making, co-create sustainable solutions, and take ownership of both their learning and environmental outcomes. It emphasizes giving students agency, responsibility, and voice in projects that tackle real-world sustainability challenges—from school policies to community initiatives (Tassone et al., 2017).
Systems Thinking	Understanding the interconnections and interdependencies within ecological, social, and economic systems (Bianchi et al., 2022).

Valuing Sustainability	Recognizing the importance of sustainability for present and future generations and integrating these values into personal and collective actions (Bianchi et al., 2022).
Vulnerable students	Students considered to be at academic risk (e.g., school failure, dropout, discrimination) or social risk (e.g., poverty, exclusion, mental illness) due to specific characteristics such as gender, age, nationality, ethnicity, health condition, socioeconomic status, or any other social condition (Pisco Costa et al. 2023).

Executive summary

Good practices of Sustainability Education and Inclusiveness

InclusiveFuture: Fostering Inclusion through Sustainable Education

Undertaken as part of the InclusiveFuture project, funded by the European Union, the report showcases examples of good practice of sustainability education and inclusiveness in eight partner countries: Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye. The InclusiveFuture project addresses the urgent need to develop learners with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to think, plan, and act responsibly for the planet. It supports the integration of sustainability competences into the educational process, creating a more inclusive environment and empowering primary and secondary schools towards sustainable practices. This collection of good practices aims to provide a central body of evidence for shaping an inclusive pedagogical model for sustainability education, showcasing the strategies, stakeholders, and learning contexts that successfully integrate environmental responsibility with equity, active participation, and learner diversity. The foundation of sharing good practices rests on the idea that innovation does not always involve creating something entirely original; instead, it often entails introducing an idea in a way that feels new or meaningful to its adopters. From this perspective, imitation serves as a legitimate and valuable springboard for educational innovation.

The 55 good practices offer a compelling portrait of sustainability education in practice in the partner countries. They highlight a spectrum of pedagogical approaches and institutional strategies, driven by diverse agents, adapted across educational levels, and spread through geographically and culturally varied landscapes. This diversity itself is a strength—illustrating that no single model dominates, but rather that sustainability in education is best approached through contextualized, flexible, and participatory frameworks. This structured diversity spreads ownership, reduces over-reliance on single strategies, embeds learning from both successes and failures, and ensures all efforts align with shared goals.

Pedagogical Approaches: A series of pedagogical approaches are evident in the good practices offering varied pathways for participation and assessment. Living laboratories, such as *Oeiras Experimenta* in Portugal, are immersive and externally collaborative, focused on real-world contexts. Service learning such as in *Green Mission* in Hungary emphasizes civic engagement and social responsibility through community-focused projects. Problem-based learning, for example in *Brigada #MARVIVO* in Portugal, and project-based learning, for example in *The Game Library* in Bulgaria, are both highly collaborative but with a more structured approach focused on solving specific problems or completing projects. Phenomenon-based learning, for

example in *Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish Schools* takes a broad, interdisciplinary approach to studying global issues, while experiential learning, for example in *Our School Garden* in Greece, focuses on integrating practical experiences and reflection within specific educational settings.

All these approaches prioritize active, student-driven learning, and real-world issues, helping students see the direct relevance of what they learn. Collaboration is a core feature of all these methods. They foster teamwork and collective problem-solving, allowing students to engage with peers, experts, and community members. This collaborative dimension supports social learning, communication skills, and empathy. While all these approaches share common goals of enhancing engagement, fostering critical thinking, and creating meaningful learning experiences, they differ in how they structure the learning process, the role of the instructor, and the focus of the learning, whether it's disciplinary, interdisciplinary, or community centered.

Implementing alternative pedagogies faces multiple challenges, including difficulty aligning with national standards due to their mismatch with traditional metrics, high time and resource demands that can strain underfunded schools, and the need for significant teacher training to support interdisciplinary, student-led learning. Equity concerns also arise when students lack access to space, resources, or community partners, potentially excluding disadvantaged groups. Additionally, many initiatives remain small-scale or pilot projects, limiting scalability and policy integration at the national level.

Many of these approaches are highly adaptable, with modular, theme-based models offering easy transfer across school levels and cultures, and problem-based or service-learning models adapting well to local community contexts. Widely recognized frameworks like project-based learning support global transfer with proper scaffolding, while individualized learning requires substantial systemic support for effective adoption. Phenomenon-based learning is also transferable but depends heavily on teacher capacity and professional development for successful implementation.

Curriculum Innovations: Integrating sustainability into curriculum content transforms both what students learn and how they relate to the world. The good practices in this category demonstrate that curriculum can serve as a powerful lever for systemic change in education. Successful integration of sustainability and inclusion into curricula depends on supportive policy environments, accessible teaching tools, digital readiness, and strong cultural and community engagement. Government mandates, as in Romania's *Săptămâna Verde*, can drive participation and system transformation, while resources like *MAPPA* and the *School Repair Guide* in Finland reduce teacher burden. Projects such as *Technologies 2.0* in Spain show how infrastructure and digital tools enable inquiry-based learning, and culturally rooted initiatives like *Heritage Language Classes* in Finland strengthen school-community connections.

However, these initiatives face challenges around scalability, equity, teacher capacity, and curricular rigidity. Resource-intensive or tech-heavy programs may struggle in rural or

underfunded schools, while innovative content often demands more planning and training than schools can sustain. Some themes, like biomimicry or sustainability entrepreneurship, clashes with rigid subject structures, and the absence of robust assessment tools for transversal competences hampers recognition of impact.

Transferability is promising when models are modular, open-access, and framework-aligned, such as *MAPPA* or EU GreenComp-based programs, which can be localized with minimal loss of intent. Policy-driven models offer strong national adaptation potential, particularly where reforms align with European Green Deal goals. Culturally specific programs, however, require sensitive local adaptation and active community participation to succeed.

Networks and Accreditation: A series of networks and accreditation systems institutionalize sustainability through collaboration, recognition, and capacity building—helping to scale impact and maintain quality. Networks and accreditation systems succeed when backed by strong institutional support and policy alignment, as seen in initiatives like *Eco-Schools Romania* and *Escoles Verdes* in Spain, where government and agency involvement provide credibility and resources. Clear criteria and recognition pathways, such as the *Green Flag* model, motivate participation through visibility and reputational gains, while capacity-building and peer learning foster skill development, mentorship, and innovation sharing. Linking local efforts to global movements like the international *Eco-Schools* program further enhances sustainability, advocacy reach, and access to funding.

Network-based and accreditation-driven models face challenges such as resource disparities that hinder participation in underserved areas, administrative burdens that can overwhelm smaller institutions, and difficulties maintaining quality and consistency across expanding networks. Sustaining motivation is also critical, as frameworks relying on initial enthusiasm may lose momentum without ongoing opportunities for reflection, renewal, and recognition.

These good practices demonstrate strong adaptability and scalability, with international frameworks like *Eco-Schools* offering high transferability through flexible design, multilingual resources, and global support, and national systems such as Hungary's *Green Kindergarten Network* or Spain's *Escoles Verdes* providing models for locally adapted accreditation. Youth-led or non-formal networks excel in diverse settings due to their peer-driven, culturally adaptable nature. Transfer works best when frameworks are modular, low-cost, and supported by open training, though initiatives deeply tied to national systems may require significant contextualization for new contexts.

Alignment with the GreenComp Framework: While the *Embodying sustainability values* and *Acting for sustainability* dimensions of the GreenComp framework are present in many initiatives, the *Embracing complexity in sustainability* and *Envisioning sustainable futures* dimensions are underdeveloped. Reference to the framework itself is very limited, *Bringing GreenComp to Life: Sustainability Competence Week in Bozkir* in Türkiye being a notable exception.

Inclusiveness Across Practices: While inclusiveness is a very strong element in many good practices, it is addressed unevenly. Pedagogies are flexible but need trained educators. Curricula target equity but lack universal design. Networks support inclusion but risk excluding resource-poor schools.

Systemic Support: Sustainability education and inclusiveness advance both through whole-institution reforms (driven by leadership and policy) and through grassroots initiatives led by committed individuals thus opening opportunities for pairing bottom-up innovations with top-down support.

From Good practice to “Next Practice”: A solid evidence base is essential, but so too are adaptability and creativity. Next practices—innovative, teacher-led experimentation—should work alongside proven good practices to spark future innovations.

Critical Reflection: Educational innovation is shaped by underlying value judgments about what counts as “best.” Sustainability education needs to engage in transformative practices, namely integrating reflection and action to question established norms and reimagine what quality in education means.

Overall Strategic Recommendations:

- Maintain a strategic mix of initiatives.
- Support a diversity of pedagogical approaches. Ensure that these align with the advancement of our understanding of what supports inclusiveness.
- Embed sustainability and inclusiveness into curricula with robust frameworks and both teacher and institutional support.
- Leverage networks to scale, standardize quality, collaborate, and build capacity. Ensure equitable access to these networks.
- Pair top-down policy support with bottom-up innovation.
- Make GreenComp more visible and support its uptake. Strengthen especially the Embracing complexity in sustainability and Envisioning sustainable futures dimensions.
- Foster next practices for experimentation and adaptability.
- Engage in critical reflection on the values underpinning good practices and educational innovation.

1. Introduction

1.1 Structure of the report

The structure of this report is designed to guide the reader through a comprehensive exploration of good practices in sustainability education and inclusiveness, as developed through the InclusiveFuture project. Following the executive summary that outlines the project's goals, scope, and key findings, the introduction sets the context for this compendium of 55 good practices. It introduces the InclusiveFuture project and includes an overview of the GreenComp framework, a conceptual foundation of inclusiveness, and background information on the participating countries and partner organizations. A methodology section explains the research questions and the method used to collect and analyze the good practices. The findings are presented thematically, highlighting pedagogical approaches, curriculum innovations, and institutional strategies that support sustainability and inclusive education. Each section discusses the frameworks used, enabling factors, challenges, and the transferability of practices. Alignment with the GreenComp framework and inclusiveness are analyzed. Conclusions are drawn and recommendations made, followed by the compendium of the good practices contributed by partner organizations, presented with contextual information, implementation strategies, outcomes, and reflections.

1.2 InclusiveFuture project

Humanity is currently confronting a complex web of interconnected challenges that threaten the well-being of people and the planet. Among the most pressing are climate change, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss, rising social and economic inequalities, political instability, and rapid technological disruption. These challenges are not confined by national borders and often exacerbate one another, creating a cycle of vulnerability and insecurity. These interconnected issues underscore the urgent need for systemic change across sectors and societies.

Sustainability and sustainable development have emerged as powerful frameworks for addressing the complex and interrelated challenges facing humanity. Rooted in the principles of equity, environmental stewardship, and long-term resilience, sustainable development aims to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. It offers a holistic approach that balances social well-being, economic prosperity, and ecological health. As a means of fostering positive transformation, sustainability encourages systemic change—redefining how societies produce, consume, and relate to the natural world to create more just, resilient, and thriving communities worldwide.

A key pillar of the global sustainability agenda is the integration of sustainability into lifelong learning, aimed at developing sustainability competences. These encompass the knowledge,

skills, and attitudes needed for learners of all ages to think critically, plan effectively, and act with empathy, responsibility, and care for both people and the planet (Bianchi et al., 2022).

The InclusiveFuture project, funded by the European Union, seeks to promote the integration of sustainability competences within educational systems directly addressing the Erasmus+ priority of promoting education for sustainable development (Topic 4: School education, Priority 9: Building sustainability competencies). It is guided by the European Framework for Green Competences (GreenComp) and involves policy experimentation, stakeholder engagement, and the development of innovative educational tools and resources. The project is committed to fostering inclusive education practices that embrace diversity and promote equity within the learning environment. Through these efforts, the project aims to foster a more inclusive learning environment for both educators and students, while supporting schools in their transition toward more sustainable and inclusive practices. The project's objectives are intricately connected to the priorities of the European Education Area (EEA) Facilitating inclusive education and Advocating education for sustainable development (ESD) (Hooda & Tuba, 2025).

1.2.1 GreenComp - the sustainability competence framework

The GreenComp framework (Bianchi, 2022), used as a reference framework in both the curriculum mapping study and the focus groups study, is the European Union's official framework for developing sustainability competencies across all areas of education and training. Developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) as part of the European Green Deal, GreenComp aims to empower individuals of all ages to live, learn, and work in ways that support ecological, social, and economic sustainability. It provides a shared foundation for promoting a sustainability mindset across formal, non-formal, and informal learning environments.

GreenComp is a reference model designed to inform curriculum development, teacher education, policy design, and assessment strategies. The competences are non-hierarchical and interrelated, meant to be adapted to different learning levels and contexts. The framework organizes 12 key competences into four interconnected areas, based on the belief that meaningful action for sustainability is dependent on the ability to think systemically, envision change, and act ethically.

Figure 1. GreenComp conceptual reference model (Bianchi et al., 2022, pg. 3)

1. **Embodying Sustainability Values** – This area focuses on internalizing values that support sustainability. It includes:
 - Valuing Sustainability: Reflecting on personal and societal values in relation to sustainable living.
 - Supporting Fairness: Promoting social and intergenerational equity.
 - Promoting Nature: Recognizing human-nature interdependence and fostering care for ecosystems.

2. **Embracing Complexity in Sustainability** – This area cultivates the skills needed to understand and address complex, interconnected sustainability challenges. It includes:
 - Systems Thinking: Seeing the bigger picture and interrelations across systems.
 - Critical Thinking: Evaluating information, questioning assumptions, and resisting greenwashing.
 - Problem Framing: Understanding sustainability issues from multiple perspectives and defining them appropriately.

3. **Envisioning Sustainable Futures** – Learners are encouraged to imagine and shape possible futures. This area includes:
 - Futures Literacy: Anticipating and planning for alternative futures.
 - Adaptability: Navigating change and making informed decisions under uncertainty.
 - Exploratory Thinking: Using creativity and interdisciplinary approaches to generate new solutions.

4. Acting for Sustainability – This area emphasizes taking initiative and influencing change. It includes:

- Political Agency: Understanding governance systems and advocating for policy change.
- Collective Action: Collaborating with others for sustainable outcomes.
- Individual Initiative: Identifying and exercising one's own capacity to contribute meaningfully.

Beyond its comprehensiveness and European relevance, GreenComp's competence-based structure allows for the identification of diverse approaches to integrating sustainability across various subjects and educational levels, rather than being tied to specific content. Furthermore, the framework's development through a participatory methodology, involving experts and stakeholders from various backgrounds, ensures that it represents a wide range of perspectives on sustainability education, making it a robust and widely accepted reference point for comparison across different national contexts and diverse educational settings. This inclusive development process enhances GreenComp's legitimacy and applicability, while its living document character ensures that it remains relevant and responsive to the dynamic nature of sustainability education (Hooda & Tuba, 2025).

1.2.2 Inclusiveness

Contrary to the logic of integration, namely merely enrolling children with special educational needs or disadvantages to schools where such children have not previously been present. Inclusion holds that there is nothing about a pupil that needs to be fixed or compensated to fit into the existing educational settings. Rather it is the educational context itself that must adapt to the individual characteristics of all children regardless of their backgrounds and abilities. Inclusion thus requires systemic change regarding teaching methods, pedagogical approaches, and school structures to enable adaptation to the immense diversity of students. It involves the removal of barriers created by society that undermine the individual's ability to succeed. Barriers could include, for instance, a lack of a lift or ramp access to a building, insufficient access to relevant computer software, or a busy and overwhelming learning environment. There has also been a further shift in the perceptions of barriers, linked to the World Health Organization's (WHO's) International Classification of Functioning (ICF), which focuses on the relationship between the individual and their environment. The ICF states that a person's level of functioning can change over time and is affected by a combination of factors, including their health, environmental factors and other personal factors (WHO, 2001). This therefore recognizes that a person's level of functioning is fluid, rather than being fixed.

Learners may present with challenges linked to:

- Behavior: regulating and conveying emotions appropriately, e.g. frustration, disengagement, withdrawal or anger.

- Executive Functions: time management, planning, prioritizing organization and working memory.
- Mental Health: depression, anxiety, eating disorders, obsessive compulsive disorders.
- Concentration and Attention: impulsiveness, distractibility, hyper focus and information overload.
- Literacy: reading, spelling or writing content.
- Communication and Language: speaking, listening and the social use of language.
- Motor: fine motor, gross motor and balance difficulties.
- Numeracy: difficulties with mathematics competency.

Starting from common presentations of learning difficulties, it is possible to identify recurring patterns that hinder learning (Eaton 2010). The *patterns beyond labels* model offers several lenses—physical, cultural, and cognitive—for understanding these patterns in inclusive practice.

- **Physical:** The *where* of learning—such as access to buildings, classrooms, or learning resources.
- **Cultural:** The *what* of learning—whether examples are relevant, instructions are clear, and content reflects diverse perspectives.
- **Cognitive:** how effectively students assimilate, process, recall, and synthesize knowledge, and whether flexible options exist for demonstrating learning.

By applying these lenses, targeted strategies can be designed to help learners overcome common challenges.

Inclusive education is expected to be proactive rather than reactive. The emphasis is on anticipating, planning for and mitigating challenges to learning, which in turn reduces the need for individual adjustments. Inclusive education aims to enable all learners to fulfil their potential (Naraian, 2019). The approach shifts the focus away from correcting areas of weakness to that of enhancing learners’ strengths and using this to offset any challenges to learning (Masataka, 2017).

Figure 2. Diagram by Joel Gibbs based on Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological model, from *Housing Children: South Auckland*, by K. Scott

The focus is on providing learning for everyone by teaching with neurodiversity in mind. Neurodiversity includes those who are considered 'neurotypical' and those who are considered 'neurodivergent'. What is considered 'typical' or 'divergent' will depend on contemporary and cultural norms and so relate closely to what is described in Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Model (Ellis et al, 2023). This benefits other areas of diversity too – such as learners whose first language is not English, learners with varying levels of cultural capital, and learners with sociocultural or socio-economic barriers.

An inclusive approach makes sure that any learner, whether they qualify for individual support or not, can still access teaching, learning and assessment which directly supports their needs and allows them to both take part and make progress. While the earliest examples of inclusion focused on access to mainstream education in response to the exclusion of students with special educational needs, the term now also encompasses the importance of enabling learners to participate fully and progress to achieve their full potential.

Figure 3. Diagram adapted from ‘The inclusive classroom’ image (Ellis, Kirby and Osborne, 2023. P84)

Inclusive education benefits all learners, not just some, because it can give them more choice and flexibility in how they learn. While teachers’ skills in recognizing where any learners need extra support remain important, using effective inclusive teaching means that there should be less need to adapt activities or resources for individual learners. In this regard, inclusive education has increasingly become associated with the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) (Cambridge International Education, 2024).

From the UDL perspective, learners’ diversity has a range of sources (CAST, 2020). Learners are motivated and engaged in different ways depending on their individual context. While some thrive on spontaneity and novelty, others may feel uncomfortable or overwhelmed by such unpredictability, preferring consistent routines instead. Similarly, some learners enjoy working independently, while others are more engaged when collaborating with peers—and these preferences can shift daily or weekly. As no single approach to engagement suits all learners in every context, offering diverse pathways for engagement is critical.

Learners also vary in how they perceive and interpret information. Individuals with sensory or learning disabilities—such as those who are blind, deaf, or dyslexic—as well as learners from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds, interact with content in unique ways. These differences must be acknowledged and respected. Equally important is ensuring that content reflects a range of identities, cultures, perspectives, and ways of knowing. Using multiple forms

of representation helps learners connect ideas both within and across subject areas, enhancing understanding and transfer of learning. Therefore, providing varied means of representation is essential.

Moreover, learners differ in how they interact with learning environments, process tasks, and express their understanding. For instance, some may prefer writing over speaking—or vice versa—based on personal comfort or context. These differences are especially significant for learners with disabilities but apply broadly across all learners. Effective action and expression often require planning, strategy, and practice, and individuals vary greatly in these skills. Consequently, there is no one-size-fits-all method for action and expression; it is essential to offer flexible options to support diverse learners.

The UDL approach ensures the curriculum and learning environment are usable by all learners to the greatest extent possible, reducing the need for individual adaptations. This approach makes teaching and learning more flexible by providing learners with many ways of taking part, feeling included, and action and expression (Meyer et al, 2013; CAST 2020).

Beyond the uniqueness of each student, the logic of inclusion also emphasizes the role a community plays in education. Inclusive education always unfolds against the background of a wider social environment, and this contextual focus is at the heart of those educational strategies that attempt to broaden the concept of inclusion. Students and teachers are not merely parts of a school, but they also belong to a public community which surrounds the school, and which reveals the public or communistic dimension of education (Inclusion4Schools, 2025).

1.2.3 Participating countries and organizations

The following 10 partner organizations of the InclusiveFuture project contributed good practices to this compendium (see Figure 1):

Bulgaria

1. The Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM) in Bulgaria is a government-supported institution focused on promoting equal educational opportunities for children from ethnic minority backgrounds. It works to integrate students into the education system, support bilingual education, and foster intercultural dialogue. The center develops policies, funds projects, and collaborates with NGOs and schools to reduce educational disparities.
2. Law and Psychology (LP), a non-profit organization based in Bulgaria. The main activities of the organization are focused on enhancing the

development of skills and competences of youth and vulnerable groups; organizing training, conferences and seminars; supporting Law and Psychology students during their internship, as well as conducting research in the field of Bulgarian, European and international legislation.

Finland

3. Glocal Minta OY (GM), is a globally connected SME located in Jyväskylä, Finland, at the heart of education development, with its focus on sustainability and global citizenship education (www.finnminta.com/en). GM fosters dialogue and development both in Finland and globally. It specializes in education for sustainable development, planetary well-being education, action competence for well-being, phenomenon-based and interdisciplinary learning. Its expertise extends to educational research and innovation, framework development, and collaborative, comparative research processes, driving meaningful advancements in education worldwide. Its initiatives, such as sustainability theme weeks and Finn Minta Forum teacher training events, provide practical and experiential learning and dissemination opportunities.

Greece

4. Big Bang School (BBS), an innovative primary school established in 2019 on the border of Thessaloniki and Halkidiki, was founded by visionary educators to provide a holistic learning experience for students from across Greece on three core principles: improvement of consciousness, development of life skills, and teaching through differentiated learning. In an environment that nurtures curiosity, personal growth, and a deep appreciation for knowledge and nature, the students at BBS are empowered to shape the future. Through educational field trips, interactive workshops, artistic activities, and collaborative projects, students cultivate their talents, develop critical thinking skills, and enhance their social engagement. BBS fosters a strong connection with nature, creating a dynamic learning environment that encourages collaboration, discovery, and personal development—shaping responsible, innovative, and creative individuals. Embracing the principles of multilingualism from an early age, we explore the interaction of languages and cultures in the human brain, equipping students with valuable linguistic and intercultural skills. The school's vision is to create a transformative learning environment for every student, preparing them for the future and helping them become the best versions of themselves.

Hungary

5. Obuda University (OE) is a key player in Hungarian higher education and a leading practice-oriented institution, where 11,000 students pursue their studies. According to the latest, 2024 Times Higher Education report, OU is the highest ranked technical university in Hungary. It offers competitive knowledge in the fields of mechanical engineering, mechatronic engineering, computer science, applied mathematics, economics, geoinformatics, architecture, marketing and teacher training in 7 faculties, 2 education centers, 16 BA/BSc (8 in English), and 14 MA/MSc (7 in English) programs. OU runs 3 doctoral schools. OU is an actor in multiple international organizations and bilateral and international programmes (currently over 20 EU financed scientific projects).
6. RCISD, a women-led SME, brings extensive expertise in inclusive education and combating inequalities through international cooperation. As coordinator of *Inclusion4Schools* (H2020), RCISD has deep experience in removing systemic barriers and ensuring marginalized communities are reached. The *STEAMCRAFT* project uses virtual experiential learning to engage students, while the coordination of Hungary's *Researchers' Night* fosters collaboration between scientists and citizens—an approach valuable for interdisciplinary sustainability education. RCISD's work in *BIOLOC* and *CELEBio* links sustainability themes with education, showing how environmental, social, and economic issues intersect.

Portugal

7. Instituto Superior Técnico /Lisbon University Técnico Lisboa is Portugal's leading school of Engineering, Science, Technology, and Architecture, recognized for academic excellence, research impact, and strong international partnerships. With over 11,000 students from 60+ nationalities, Técnico fosters innovation, entrepreneurship, and cutting-edge research to address global challenges. The school actively participates in international academic networks (CLUSTER, TIME, CESAER) and collaborates with top universities such as MIT, CMU, UT-Austin, and EPFL through double degree and joint PhD programs. Técnico is committed to expanding its global presence through strategic partnerships, interdisciplinary research, and knowledge transfer, making it a key player in international projects.

Oeiras City Council. The Municipality of Oeiras, as an associate partner of the Inclusive Future project through the Instituto Superior Técnico (IST), plays a key role in supporting the development of innovative educational content and the dissemination of sustainable practices in school contexts.

Romania

8. Focus Eco Center is a non-profit organization based in Tg. Mures, Romania, and is mainly active in the Central Transylvania region. The main goal of the organization is to collect and distribute quality information on key environmental issues, such as climate change or biodiversity loss, and to promote valuable, scientifically proven information on solutions. Focus believes that schoolteachers and educators are the right people who can influence the future of generations to come, so our main target groups are schools, but also work with other groups such as policy makers. It develops pilot projects especially in the field of water management and offers its experience for implementation by larger systems.

Spain

9. Open Europe is a non-profit organization based in Reus, Spain, dedicated to promoting European mobility, lifelong learning, and educational innovation. It provides training, career guidance, and access to European programs for students and educators. Open Europe specializes in fostering inclusion, sustainability, and digital skills, creating educational platforms and innovative learning resources to support professional development and social integration.
10. Escola Pia de Catalunya (EPC) is an institution with a network of 23 schools. The studies go from kindergarten to higher education. We have VET studies in 13 of the 22 schools, in different fields: Administration, IT, Sport, Health care, Childhood, Marketing, forestry, hospitality etc. EPC has 20.000 students, 2.900 teachers, and one foundation (Camins). EPC has more than 400 years of experience in education in Catalunya. Since then, and up until today, the Escola Pia de Catalunya has continued to evolve, adapting to new times without ever losing the purpose of promoting education as a driving force for social transformation.

Türkiye

11. Konya Provincial National Education Directorate (Konya IL MEM) is a state institution responsible for the planning and coordination of educational and training activities in preschool, primary, secondary, and adult

education throughout Konya. The province encompasses 31 districts, hosting a total of 2,913 schools, 36,439 teachers, and 543,379 students. Konya IL MEM acts as an umbrella organization, uniting this extensive educational network.

Figure 4. Participating countries and number of partner organizations (*associated partners) represented on a map.

1.3 Purpose of the good practice compendium and analysis

As a first step towards providing support to schools across partner countries in integrating and assessing the development of sustainability competences, it was considered crucial to understand the countries' latest progress and existing needs with respect to sustainability education and Inclusiveness. Hence a comparative study has been carried out to evaluate the state of art concerning sustainability education in the national core curricula and selected practices of the 8 partner countries through analysis of each country's primary and secondary school curricula as well as supporting documents. The curricular analysis was supported by provision of evidence on teacher training and assessment practices regarding development of sustainability competences provided by partner countries. The focus of the study was on evaluating the readiness and relevance of national core curricula regarding sustainability competence development and assessment based on the GreenComp Framework (Hooda & Tuba, 2025). To contextualize further the findings from the curriculum mapping, the consortium collected empirical data from the partner countries in the form of focus group discussions. The

purpose of these focus groups was to identify the needs and challenges schools face, as well as practices they developed, and barriers they encountered, in embedding and assessing sustainability competences (Vesely & Szövérfi, 2025).

To complement the curriculum analysis and focus group consultations, this compendium of good practices brings together 55 good practices contributed by partners of the InclusiveFuture project, offering rich, ground-level insights into how sustainability education is being implemented across diverse European contexts. These practices were collected and analyzed not only to showcase innovation but also to deepen understanding of how inclusive and transformative sustainability learning can be fostered in real-world educational settings. This collection is intended to serve as a key source of evidence for developing an inclusive pedagogical model for sustainability education—highlighting the strategies, actors, and learning environments that effectively combine environmental responsibility with equity, participation, and learner diversity.

1.4 Research questions

The good practices analysis was guided by a set of core questions with the aim of generating insight into the current practice of sustainability education and inclusiveness across diverse educational contexts in partner countries:

- What types of sustainability education practices emerge across the good practices?
- At which educational levels (early childhood, primary, secondary, vocational, non-formal) are the sustainability education practices most implemented, and what patterns emerge?
- Who are the main agents driving sustainability initiatives in good practices (e.g., teachers, students, school leaders, policymakers, community actors)?
- What factors (e.g., policy support, resources, teacher training, community involvement) contribute to the success of sustainability education initiatives?
- What challenges and constraints are reported in the implementation and sustainability of these practices?
- Which practices show potential for scalability and transferability in other educational or geographical contexts, and why?
- To what extent do the good practices align with the four dimensions of the GreenComp framework (Embodying sustainability values; Embracing complexity in sustainability; Envisioning sustainable futures; Acting for sustainability)?
- Is inclusiveness addressed in the design and implementation of sustainability education practices (e.g., attention to learner diversity, social equity, accessibility)?

1.5 Good practice collection as a methodological approach

In the pursuit of advancing sustainability education and promoting inclusiveness, identifying, and learning from successful models is essential. One effective technique for achieving this is the collection of good practices—documented examples of strategies, programs, or initiatives that have demonstrated positive outcomes in real-world settings. This method enables practitioners, educators, and policymakers to draw insights from proven approaches, adapt them to their local contexts, and avoid common pitfalls.

The basis of sharing good practices lies in the understanding that innovation doesn't always require inventing something entirely new; rather, it is often about presenting an idea as new or meaningful to those who adopt it. In this sense, imitation becomes a valid and valuable starting point for educational innovation (Inclusion4Schools, 2025).

The development of this compendium of good practices was guided by a shared agreement among the InclusiveFuture project partners on both the focus and scope of the collection. Partners agreed to concentrate on sustainability education with a strong emphasis on inclusiveness, reflecting the project's commitment to promoting learning environments that address both environmental and social challenges. The scope was likewise agreed to encompass a diverse range of educational levels—from early childhood to secondary and vocational education—and to be geographically limited to the eight partner countries involved in the project, ensuring contextual relevance and transnational diversity.

The methodology combined primary and secondary data collection. Primary data included focus group consultations conducted in each country with teachers, school leaders, and education specialists. These consultations helped identify initial good practices and contributed qualitative insights into local needs, enabling factors, and perceptions of inclusive sustainability education (Vesely & Szövérfi, 2005). In parallel, a case study protocol was developed to guide the documentation process, supported by a structured case study template filled in directly by each partner. This template captured essential dimensions of each practice, including implementation modalities, learning activities, enabling factors, challenges encountered, and aspects of transferability. Importantly, partners were given the freedom to select practices they considered most relevant to the project's goals, encouraging reflection and authentic and grounded contributions.

To ensure coherence and usability of the compendium, the process included iterative consultation among partners. Drafts were discussed collectively, feedback loops were built into each stage, and cross-validation helped refine both the template and its application. This collaborative process also laid the foundation for future outputs: the partners initiated the design of an online survey tool that will evolve into an interactive library of good practices, enabling future expansion and stakeholder engagement.

The main purpose of the analysis of the compiled practices was to inform the development of an inclusive pedagogical model for sustainability education. To this end, the analysis was structured around a set of research questions addressing the spectrum of practices, educational levels, agents of change, enabling factors, challenges, transferability, alignment with the GreenComp framework, and inclusiveness.

What is “good practice” with regards the potential to inform the development of an inclusive pedagogical model for sustainability education was left to the professional judgement of the project partners. It is therefore important to acknowledge that good practices represent past successes and must be complemented by next practices—innovative, forward-looking experiments that can shape future directions (Hannon, 2006). Furthermore, what is considered “best” is inherently a value judgment, requiring ongoing critical reflection (Biesta, 2010).

2. Key findings

2.1 Overview of good practices

2.1.1 Coverage

Drawing on a diverse range of examples from institutions and programs in the partner countries, a series of 55 good practices was collected that illustrates a broad and dynamic spectrum of educational approaches to sustainability. They range from highly structured, policy-led initiatives to grassroots, student-led experiments. There is strong regional diversity, with many good practices responding to local cultural, ecological, and policy contexts. Through our analysis, three key categories of good practice emerged: pedagogical transformations that reimagine how learning takes place; curriculum innovations that embed sustainability into learning content and teaching methods; and networks and accreditation that aim to institutionalize sustainability across schools and regions. These three categories will be analyzed in separate subsections, each offering insights into distinct yet interconnected dimensions of sustainability education. Across all three areas, the analysis will highlight implications for inclusiveness, identifying practices that not only advance sustainability goals but also promote participation, equity, and representation in educational systems. The good practices collectively reflect a whole-school approach to sustainability—spanning governance, curriculum, pedagogy, infrastructure, and community engagement.

2.1.2 Educational levels

The initiatives span early childhood to vocational education, but certain patterns stand out. Primary education is the most frequently represented level, benefiting from the flexibility to integrate outdoor learning, environmental themes, and community involvement. Secondary education features prominently in projects that involve youth activism, civic engagement, and competency-based curricula (e.g., *PAL-TIN*, *The World We Want*). Early childhood education is effectively engaged through networked programs like the *Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network*, demonstrating that sustainability values can be introduced early. Vocational and technical education is less frequently represented but present in standout examples like *Green Mission in the Petzelt Jozsef School*, which show how sustainability intersects with job skills. Non-formal and lifelong learning contexts appear in initiatives like *AGLT* and *Second Chance Schools*, which offer inclusive, alternative pathways for marginalized youth.

While sustainability is adaptable across age groups, early and primary levels lead in terms of project volume and diversity, while vocational and non-formal sectors remain underleveraged.

2.1.3 Agents of change

Across the good practices, the main agents driving change vary and often work in partnership. Teachers and school leaders are the primary implementers in most cases, often initiating or adapting projects in response to local context (*Recycling School, Our Sustainable School*). Students emerge as active agents of change in over half the good practices—particularly in problem-, service-, and project-based learning models (*Compost Bucket Challenge, Green Mission, Brigada #MARVIVO*). Policy and institutional actors (e.g., ministries of education, NGOs, regional governments) provide structural support and frameworks in many accreditation and network-based initiatives (*Escoles Verdes, Săptămâna Verde*). Community members, families, and local organizations feature heavily in experiential and service-learning projects (*Young & Old Gardeners, Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood*), ensuring local relevance and co-ownership. These good practices reinforce the notion of shared responsibility in sustainability education, with effective implementation often involving multi-stakeholder partnerships.

2.2 Good practices of pedagogical approaches

In recent years, sustainability education has increasingly embraced diverse pedagogical strategies to engage students in meaningful, real-world learning. The collection of good practices in Table 1 showcases a variety of pedagogical approaches—including living laboratories, problem-based learning, phenomenon-based learning, experiential and project-based learning, service learning, and individualized learning. These approaches provide students with hands-on opportunities to address sustainability challenges, fostering agency, critical thinking, collaboration, and civic engagement. Together, these practices illustrate the diverse ways schools across Europe are reimagining teaching and learning to equip students for a sustainable and inclusive future.

Good Practice Category: Pedagogical Approaches		
Good practice ID	Good practice title	Country
LIVING LABORATORY		
GP01	Oeiras Experimenta	Portugal
GP02	Rainwater for Toilets: A Practical Approach to Water Conservation in Schools	Spain
PROBLEM BASED LEARNING		
GP03	Tisza River PET Cup for Youth (Tiszai PET Kupa)	Hungary
GP04	Brigada #MARVIVO	Portugal
GP05	Engaging with Fishing: Transforming the Social and Environmental Reality of the Surroundings Through Education for Sustainable Development	Spain
GP06	We act together for Nature and Man	Greece
GP07	Our Sustainable School	Greece
GP08	Reducing Classroom Plastic Use via Student Leadership	Turkey
GP09	Young & Old Gardeners	Greece
GP10	We are joining our forces for water	Greece
GP11	Efficient with the Environment	Spain
GP12	Birds, Let's Fly Together!	Spain

Good Practice Category: Pedagogical Approaches		
Good practice ID	Good practice title	Country
GP13	PAL - TIN - Youth Participation Councils for Sustainable and Inclusive Communities	Romania
PHENOMENON BASED LEARNING		
GP14	Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish Schools	Finland
EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING		
GP15	Forest Classrooms: Connecting Learning with Nature	Turkey
GP16	Compost Bucket Challenge - Engaging Families in Urban Biodiversity Actions	Hungary
GP17	From Waste to Growth : Composting for a Greener School	Turkey
GP18	Our School Garden , a Field of Learning and Creation	Greece
GP19	Participatory Design for the Creation of a School Herb Garden	Greece
GP20	Sowing Seeds in an Eco-sustainable Environment (Balearic Islands)	Spain
GP21	Looking for the Present in the Past	Greece
PROJECT BASED LEARNING		
GP22	Turning Waste into Value : A Creative Sustainability Approach	Turkey
GP23	The World We Want . A Globalising Experience through Project-based Learning	Spain
GP24	Escola da Ponte	Portugal
GP25	Different Together - Building an Inclusive School Community through Intercultural Dialogue and Non-formal Education	Bulgaria
GP26	The Game Library - Enhancing Parental Engagement and Educational Inclusion in Early Childhood Education at Kindergarten "Barborino"	Bulgaria
GP27	Lab in a Box - Oeiras	Portugal
SERVICE LEARNING		
GP28	Next Stop SDG 2030 : A Very Real Path	Spain
GP29	Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood	Spain

Good Practice Category: Pedagogical Approaches		
Good practice ID	Good practice title	Country
GP30	Green Mission in the Petzelt Jozsef Technical and Vocational School	Hungary
INDIVIDUALISED LEARNING		
GP31	Social Plans: Ensuring Equal Educational Opportunities for All Students	Spain

Table 1: Good practices of pedagogical approaches

2.2.1 Frameworks

Each pedagogical approach is anchored in distinctive educational frameworks that guide implementation:

- Living laboratories like *Oeiras Experimenta* and *Rainwater for Toilets* are grounded in place-based and inquiry-driven frameworks, where the school environment becomes a testing ground for ecological innovation and behavior change.
- Problem-based learning initiatives follow frameworks that emphasize learner-driven inquiry, often using community challenges (e.g., plastic waste, water use, or biodiversity loss) as entry points for critical thinking and collaborative problem-solving. Projects such as *Tisza River PET Cup for Youth* and *We Act Together for Nature and Man* exemplify this approach.
- Phenomenon-based learning, as practiced in *Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish Schools*, uses a systems thinking framework that breaks down disciplinary silos, encouraging students to explore interconnected environmental, social, and economic phenomena.
- Experiential learning is based on constructivism and nature-based education frameworks, where students learn through direct interaction with their environment. This is evident in school gardens (*Our School Garden*), composting (*Compost Bucket Challenge*), and outdoor classrooms (*Forest Classrooms*).
- Project-based learning frameworks drive initiatives like *Escola da Ponte* and *The World We Want*, where students undertake interdisciplinary, long-term projects tied to global challenges and community goals.

- Service learning, as in *Next Stop SDG 2030* and *Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood*, combines civic education and curriculum content, encouraging students to apply knowledge to real-world service for sustainable development.
- Individualized learning, represented by *Social Plans*, follows a personalized learning framework that emphasizes equity, inclusion, and differentiated instruction, particularly for disadvantaged learners.

Pedagogical approach	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Living laboratory	Living labs are open, user-centered innovation ecosystems operating in real-world settings, where students collaborate with diverse stakeholders to co-create sustainability solutions. In sustainability education, these labs immerse learners in authentic challenges—e.g. urban planning, waste management.	Deep engagement; fosters transferable lifelong learning skills, collaboration, and critical reflection.	Resource-intensive; scalability and facilitation vary; possible imbalance between emancipatory and instructive elements.	Expand teacher professional competence; integrate across disciplines; partner with communities or professional bodies.	Expand teacher professional competence; integrate across disciplines; partner with communities or professional bodies.
Problem-	Problem-based	Deep	Can detach	Reconnect PBL	Without robust

Pedagogical approach	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
based learning	learning places open-ended, ill-structured problems at the center of learning. Students collaboratively identify, investigate, and propose solutions.	engagement; fosters transferable lifelong learning skills, collaboration, and critical reflection.	learning from real contexts; requires strong tutor scaffolding; student motivation and prior knowledge vary.	to active civic contexts; integrate sustainability challenges that require real-world responsibility.	design, PBL risk becomes superficial; pressure for standardized outputs may undermine depth.
Phenomenon-based learning	engages students in interdisciplinary inquiry by studying a real-world phenomenon—such as climate change, urban flooding, or biodiversity loss—instead of discrete subjects.	Integrates multiple disciplines, boosts relevance to student interests, deepens systems awareness.	Demands significant planning by schools and teachers; risk of superficial coverage if coordination fails.	Aligns well with sustainable development goals; promotes equity by letting students pursue personally relevant phenomena.	Equity issues if access is uneven; logistical and safety challenges; may privilege those already inclined to outdoors experiences.
Experiential learning	Emphasizes cycles of concrete experience, reflection, conceptualization and application in authentic environments. In sustainability education, it may involve field-based environmental research, workshops, hands-on projects, or community engagements.	High engagement; builds self-efficacy and motivation; bridges theory and practice.	Access to suitable field sites and resources may be limited; scale can be small and context-specific.	It can be embedded in living labs, schools or communities; supports inclusion through diverse activity designs.	Equity issues if access is uneven; logistical and safety challenges may privilege those already inclined to outdoors experiences.
Project-based	moves away from passive reception	Deep conceptual	Requires significant	Can link to real community or	Without support,

Pedagogical approach	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
learning	of information and towards active construction of knowledge through real-world projects. Centers around extended, student-driven projects tackling real sustainability issues (e.g. recycling systems, sustainable city design)	knowledge; development of sustainability competencies (systems thinking, anticipation, collaboration); supports equity and agency.	teacher support, project management skills, time and resources; risk of unfocused outcomes.	institutional partners	projects flounder; institutional constraints may limit flexibility; student self-management challenges.
Service learning	Combines educational objectives with meaningful community service, embedding reflection and reciprocity into civic action projects that address sustainability challenges. Students research, plan, enact service, then reflect on contributions to both learning and community well-being.	Connects learning to community impact; develops civic empathy and ethical awareness; supports marginalized communities.	Risk of superficial “good deeds” without critical reflection; power imbalances with community partners; inconsistent stakeholder communication.	Position service as critical, inclusive engagement; embed critical reflection for transformative justice.	Institutional mandates may lead to compliance rather than meaningful engagement; possibility of reinforcing inequalities if not co-designed.

Table 2. SWOT analysis of good practice pedagogical approaches

2.2.2 Enabling Factors

Several key enablers support the successful implementation of these pedagogical approaches:

- Flexible curriculum structures and school autonomy allow educators to adopt alternative learning models, as seen in *Escola da Ponte* and the Finnish recycling program.
- Community partnerships are essential, particularly in problem-based and service-learning models, where local stakeholders contribute knowledge, context, and support—such as fishermen in *Engaging with Fishing* or residents in *Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood*.
- Teacher leadership and creativity enable programs like *Brigada #MARVIVO* and *Birds, Let's Fly Together!* to evolve organically and stay responsive to student interests and local issues.
- Outdoor and green infrastructure—gardens, compost bins, or experimental installations—are key assets in experiential and living laboratory models, making sustainability visible and tangible.
- Student agency and participation are core enabling values, especially in models like *PAL-TIN* (Youth Participation Councils), where learners are empowered as decision-makers and change agents.

2.2.3 Challenges

Despite their success, these pedagogies face notable barriers:

- Assessment alignment with national standards can be difficult. Alternative pedagogies may not fit traditional metrics, making it hard to evaluate or legitimize their impact within formal systems.
- Time and resource demands are considerable. Project-based and experiential models often require extended timeframes, materials, and dedicated outdoor spaces, limiting feasibility for resource-strapped schools.
- Teacher training and professional development remain critical. Educators must be equipped to facilitate interdisciplinary, student-led learning, which is a significant shift from conventional teaching roles.
- Equity and accessibility issues can arise. Not all students have equal access to outdoor spaces, project resources, or community partners—raising concerns about inclusivity, particularly in individualized and place-based models.

- Scalability and policy recognition are limited. Many initiatives remain isolated or pilot-based, lacking system-wide support or integration into national strategies.
- Scalability and equity emerge as major issues, particularly for resource-intensive or tech-dependent initiatives like *Lab in a Box*, which may struggle to reach rural or underfunded schools without additional investment and support structures.

2.2.4 Transferability

Many of the approaches have strong potential for adaptation and replication:

- Modular, theme-based models, such as *Compost Bucket Challenge* or *Young & Old Gardeners*, are easily adapted to different school levels, contexts, or cultures, offering high transferability with minimal structural change.
- Problem-based and service-learning models are transferable where community challenges and partnerships can be localized. Their adaptability lies in their responsiveness to specific environmental or social contexts.
- Frameworks like project-based learning (PBL) are globally recognized and already embedded in many progressive curricula, making models like *The World We Want* readily transferrable with appropriate scaffolding.
- Individualized learning, such as *Social Plans*, may require significant systemic or administrative support to transfer effectively, including access to support staff, data tracking, and funding for equity interventions.
- Phenomenon-based learning depends on teacher capacity for interdisciplinary facilitation, making professional development a prerequisite for successful transfer.

In conclusion, these diverse pedagogical models demonstrate how sustainability education can be deeply embedded in meaningful, student-centered learning experiences. Whether through living laboratories, civic service, or outdoor classrooms, these approaches offer powerful alternatives to traditional instruction, fostering both ecological literacy and democratic engagement. While challenges remain in assessment, equity, and scale, the richness and variety of these practices show that with the right support, transformative learning for sustainability is not only possible but already thriving in classrooms across Europe.

2.2.5 Alignment with GreenComp

This collection of good practices of pedagogical transformations shows a high degree of alignment with the GreenComp framework, though with varying levels of emphasis across the four dimensions.

Embodying Sustainability Values

This dimension is strongly represented across all categories. Most initiatives, especially those involving gardens (*Our School Garden*), waste reduction (*Reducing Classroom Plastic Use*), and nature engagement (*Forest Classrooms*, *Sowing Seeds in an Eco-Sustainable Environment*), focus explicitly on cultivating values like care for nature, responsibility, and solidarity. Service learning and problem-based learning projects like *Next Stop SDG 2030* and *We Act Together for Nature and Man* are particularly effective in nurturing ethical awareness, empathy, and community responsibility. Individualized learning in *Social Plans* also reflects this dimension by prioritizing equity and inclusion, key sustainability values.

Embracing Complexity in Sustainability

This dimension is moderately to highly represented, especially in phenomenon-based learning, project-based learning, and more advanced problem-based initiatives. Projects such as *Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish Schools* and *The World We Want* expose learners to the interconnectedness of systems, helping them explore cause-effect relationships and societal trade-offs. Some problem-based learning initiatives, like *Engaging with Fishing* or *Tisza PET Cup*, also offer a lens into interdependent environmental, social, and economic factors. However, a few experiential and living lab projects tend to focus more on practical implementation than systemic analysis, which might limit deeper engagement with complexity unless explicitly scaffolded by educators.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures

This is one of the less consistently emphasized GreenComp dimensions across the good practices. While most projects involve reflection on the present and action in the now, fewer explicitly focus on futures thinking, scenario planning, or utopian/dystopian exploration. Some notable exceptions include *The World We Want* and *Escola da Ponte*, where students critically imagine and co-create alternative futures as part of long-term, student-directed projects.

Projects with design elements (*Participatory Design for the Creation of a School Herb Garden*) do offer creative envisioning opportunities but may not always connect them to long-term sustainable futures unless explicitly framed that way.

Acting for Sustainability

This dimension is exceptionally well represented across nearly all projects. Students are not just learning about sustainability, they are actively engaged in behaviors, advocacy, and community service that embody sustainable practices. Examples include implementing compost systems, organizing cleanups, installing water reuse systems, or participating in decision-making (*PAL-TIN, Green Mission*). Many of these initiatives promote student leadership, ownership, and direct action, fulfilling this GreenComp dimension with clear and tangible results.

Pedagogical Approach	Values	Complexity	Futures	Action
Living Laboratory	✓✓	⚠	⚠	✓✓
Problem-Based Learning	✓	✓✓	⚠	✓✓
Phenomenon-Based	✓	✓✓	⚠	✓
Experiential Learning	✓✓	⚠	⚠	✓✓
Project-Based Learning	✓	✓	✓	✓✓
Service Learning	✓✓	✓	⚠	✓✓
Individualized Learning	✓✓	⚠	⚠	✓

Table 3. Level of alignment of the good practice pedagogical approaches with the GreenComp framework’s dimensions

Overall, the pedagogical approaches showcased in these good practices align strongly with the GreenComp framework, especially in cultivating values and empowering action. To deepen the match—particularly with the “envisioning sustainable futures” and “embracing complexity” dimensions—educators could further scaffold future-oriented thinking and systems-level reflection within these otherwise well-designed, action-rich experiences. This would ensure learners not only act for change today but also understand and imagine the long-term implications of their choices in shaping a sustainable tomorrow.

2.2.6 Inclusiveness

Innovative pedagogies often embody inclusive potential by design, offering flexible, meaningful learning pathways—though outcomes depend heavily on teacher capacity and contextual responsiveness. Experiential, project-, and service-based pedagogies naturally lend themselves to inclusiveness, allowing students with diverse strengths (e.g., hands-on, interpersonal, creative) to engage deeply. Projects like *Young & Old Gardeners*, *Compost Bucket Challenge*, and *Brigada #MARVIVO* fosters intergenerational, cross-sectoral participation, enhancing social cohesion. *PAL-TIN* and *Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood* enable youth civic engagement and recognition of underrepresented community voices. Many experiential learning projects occur outside the conventional classroom, which can benefit learners who struggle in traditional settings. Informal and localized projects may lack structural support (e.g., inclusive pedagogy training, accessibility tools) unless inclusion is explicitly prioritized. Scaling and consistency of inclusive practice across settings may be uneven without guiding frameworks or training.

2.3 Good practices of curriculum innovation and educational policy initiatives

In recent years, education systems across Europe have increasingly prioritized curriculum innovation to address the urgent challenges of sustainability, digital transformation, and social inclusion. The following good practices showcase diverse and creative approaches to embedding these themes within school curricula, offering students meaningful, real-world learning experiences. From national green week programs and biomimicry-inspired entrepreneurship to digital STEM labs and inclusive language education, these initiatives reflect a shared commitment to equipping learners with the knowledge, skills, and values needed for a just and sustainable future. Collectively, they illustrate how curriculum can serve as a powerful lever for systemic change in education.

Good practice Category: Curriculum Innovations		
Good practice ID	Good practice title	Country
GP32	Sustainability Academy Bulgaria	Bulgaria
GP33	Natural Entrepreneurs (NatEnt) - Biomimicry-Inspired Learning for a Sustainable Future	Romania
GP34	SUMMEM: A Cooperative and Multilingual Learning Model for the 21st Century	Spain
GP35	MAPPA Multifunctional Tool for Teachers	Finland
GP36	The Recycling School: Teachers for a Clean Nature	Bulgaria
GP37	School Repair Guide	Finland
GP38	Technologies 2.0: Equipping Schools for a Digital Learning Environment	Spain
GP39	Programul Saptamana Verde - A National Green Week in Schools	Romania
GP40	Bringing GreenComp to Life: Sustainability Competence Week in Bozkir	Turkey
GP41	Second Chance Schools - Innovative Approaches to Inclusive Education	Bulgaria
GP42	Heritage Language Classes / Mother Tongue Education	Finland

GP43	<u>The World - I in it and it in me! Internship at the Vocational High School of Chemical and Food Technologies (PGHHT), Pazardzhik</u>	Bulgaria
GP44	<u>My Future Starts Today - Integrated Support for the socialization and Educational Inclusion of Roma Students in Sofia</u>	Bulgaria
GP45	<u>A Systematic Model for Active Inclusion in Preschool Education - Bridging Gaps through Early Educational Support in Bulgaria</u>	Bulgaria

Table 4. Good practices of curriculum innovations

Several initiatives, such as *Sustainability Academy Bulgaria*, *The Recycling School*, and *Programul Săptămâna Verde (Romania's National Green Week)*, incorporate environmental education directly into the formal curriculum, often through interdisciplinary projects and national campaigns. These programs engage students in hands-on learning about climate change, waste reduction, and sustainable living, aligning with broader educational policy goals.

Projects like *Natural Entrepreneurs* and *Bringing GreenComp to Life* focus on competence-based education, linking sustainability themes with 21st-century skills such as creativity, systems thinking, and entrepreneurial thinking. The use of the GreenComp framework reinforces curriculum coherence and alignment with EU sustainability competence standards.

Digital and technological innovation is another strong theme. *Technologies 2.0* demonstrate how digital tools can be leveraged to enhance access to STEM and environmental education. These initiatives promote active, inquiry-based learning, especially in underserved or remote schools.

Pedagogical innovation also stands out. *SUMMEM* and *MAPPA* present methodological models for cooperative and multilingual learning, offering adaptable frameworks that support inclusivity and learner agency. Likewise, the *School Repair Guide* provides curriculum resources for engaging students in school transformation projects, linking learning directly to their lived environment.

Finally, projects like *Second Chance Schools*, *My Future Starts Today* and *Heritage Language Classes* highlight the integration of inclusive practices into curricula, ensuring that marginalized groups and multilingual learners receive equitable learning opportunities that reflect their cultural and linguistic identities.

2.3.1 Frameworks

The GreenComp framework is central in the *Bringing GreenComp to Life* initiative, where it informs curriculum design through a focus on systems thinking, critical reflection, collaboration, and action orientation. The framework provides a shared language and goal structure, supporting alignment across diverse educational contexts. National curriculum mandates and public policy play a central role in cases such as *Programul Săptămâna Verde* and *The Recycling School*, where environmental themes are embedded directly into the official school calendar or subject-specific learning outcomes. These frameworks ensure wide participation and systemic legitimacy. Innovative pedagogical frameworks such as *SUMMEM*, which combines cooperative and multilingual learning, and *MAPPA*, a multifunctional planning and evaluation tool, demonstrate how methodological innovation can support inclusion, learner agency, and interdisciplinarity. Many cases also reflect a project-based, experiential learning framework, especially *Natural Entrepreneurs (NatEnt)* and the *School Repair Guide*. These encourage students to tackle real-world problems, blending sustainability with entrepreneurship, community engagement, and creative problem-solving.

2.3.2 Enabling factors

Successful integration of sustainability and inclusion into the curriculum is underpinned by multiple enabling factors:

- Supportive policy environments are key, as seen in Romania's *Săptămâna Verde* and *Second Chance Schools*. Government mandates ensure that even schools with limited resources or initial resistance take part, while also encouraging broader system transformation.
- Accessible, high-quality teaching tools like *MAPPA*, and the *School Repair Guide* empower educators by providing ready-to-use materials, guidance, and flexibility for adaptation. These tools reduce the burden on teachers and enhance professional confidence.
- Digital readiness and infrastructure are critical enablers in projects like *Technologies 2.0*, which equip schools with the hardware and software needed to facilitate inquiry-based, digitally mediated learning experiences.
- Cultural and community engagement plays a pivotal role in fostering a meaningful curriculum. Initiatives such as *Heritage Language Classes* and *NatEnt* highlight the

importance of locally rooted and culturally responsive approaches, which resonate more deeply with learners and build stronger school-community connections.

2.3.3 Challenges

Despite their promise, many of these initiatives face recurring challenges that must be addressed to achieve sustainable impact.

- Teacher capacity and time constraints are common barriers. Innovative curricula often require additional planning, training, and interdisciplinary coordination, which are difficult to sustain without adequate institutional backing or time within the school schedule.
- Institutional irritation and curricular rigidity can limit uptake. For example, ideas like biomimicry or sustainability entrepreneurship (e.g., in *NatEnt*) may not easily fit into existing subjects or assessment structures, making integration difficult.
- Assessment limitations persist, particularly in programs aiming to build transversal competences or values-based learning. The lack of robust evaluation tools for competences like ecological awareness or systems thinking means that impact may be under-recognized or inconsistently measured.

2.3.4 Transferability

Many of these good practices offer high potential for adaptation across contexts, though success depends on thoughtful implementation.

- Toolkit- and resource-based models such as *MAPPA*, *School Repair Guide*, and *Lab in a Box* are highly transferable due to their modular design, open access, and adaptability. These can be localized while preserving core pedagogical intent.
- Framework-aligned initiatives, particularly those using European tools like GreenComp, benefit from a shared regional context, making them more compatible with other EU curricula and education strategies.
- Policy-driven models, such as *Săptămâna Verde*, are useful templates for national adaptation—especially where central governments are pursuing education reforms linked to the European Green Deal, digital transition, or social inclusion.

- Culturally specific or identity-based programs (e.g., *Heritage Language Classes* or *NatEnt*) require localized adaptation and community buy-in. Their success hinges on cultural sensitivity and co-creation with learners and stakeholders.

2.3.5 Alignment with GreenComp

Embodying Sustainability Values

Curriculum-focused initiatives strongly promote sustainability values like care, responsibility, and equity. Projects such as *Sustainability Academy Bulgaria*, *Heritage Language Classes*, and *Second Chance Schools* embed social inclusion, biodiversity awareness, and ethics directly into learning objectives. The integration of environmental ethics and social justice across subjects and learning outcomes is the main strength.

Embracing Complexity in Sustainability

Several curriculum innovation projects explore sustainability from an interdisciplinary or systems-thinking perspective. *Natural Entrepreneurs (NatEnt)* and *Waste Processing in Finnish Schools* explicitly address interdependence between ecological, economic, and social systems. Competence-based and inquiry-led approaches support complexity awareness, however not all curriculum examples scaffold systems thinking explicitly across subjects.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures

Futures thinking is present in initiatives like *The World We Want* or *Green Week* projects but often remains implicit. Fewer curriculum initiatives provide structured opportunities for students to explore long-term scenarios or alternative futures. Lack of explicit tools or reflection structures to support scenario-building or visioning is a limitation.

Acting for Sustainability

Most curriculum innovations involve student-led projects or whole-school actions, such as composting (*From Waste to Growth*), water conservation (*Rainwater for Toilets*), and digital action (*Technologies 2.0*). These promote active citizenship and practical application of learning.

GreenComp Dimension	Curriculum Innovation
Embodying Sustainability Values	✓✓
Embracing Complexity	✓
Envisioning Sustainable Futures	⚠
Acting for Sustainability	✓✓

Table 5. Level of alignment of the good practice curriculum innovations with the GreenComp frameworks’ dimensions ✓✓✓ High ✓ Moderate high ⚠ Moderate

2.3.6 Inclusiveness

Curriculum innovations offer a solid foundation for inclusiveness, especially when aligned with equity policies, though stronger mechanisms for universal design and accessibility could enhance reach. Many curriculum-focused initiatives actively integrate equity and accessibility principles through differentiated learning models, multilingual approaches, or focus on underserved learners. Examples like *Social Plans* and *Second Chance Schools* address systemic exclusion by tailoring curriculum and support for at-risk or previously excluded students. The *SUMMEM* model supports multilingual and cooperative learning, creating inclusive classroom environments for linguistically diverse students. *Heritage Language Classes* promote cultural inclusion and identity validation—critical components of an inclusive education. While some initiatives are inclusive by design, others may focus primarily on mainstream school populations, with limited evidence of adaptations for students with disabilities or specific learning needs. Digital divided risks emerge in technology-enhanced programs (e.g., *Technologies 2.0*) without explicit strategies for equity in access.

2.4 Good practices of networks and accreditation

Accreditation systems and institutional networks play a crucial role in creating communities of practice for sustainability education by providing a structured framework for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and ongoing professional development. Accreditation bodies that recognize sustainability-focused programs set standards that institutions strive to meet, encouraging a collective approach to sustainability education across diverse contexts. These networks, whether national or international, offer platforms for educators, students, and industry experts to exchange good practices, resources, and research.

Good practice Category: Networks and Accreditation		
Good practice ID	Good practice title	Country
GP46	The Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network	Hungary
GP47	Hungary's Forest School Program	Hungary
GP48	Escoles Verdes: Building a Culture of Sustainability in Escola Pia de Catalunya	Spain
GP49	The Green Flag Programme	Finland
GP50	Eco-Schools Romania (Green Flag Programme)	Romania
GP51	Eco-Schools Programme	Portugal
GP52	Pilot Network of Green Schools (Romanian Recovery and Resilience Plan)	Romania
GP53	AGLT - Youth Driven Sustainability Education in Rural Romania	Romania
GP54	Sustainability: Growing with Care	Bulgaria
GP55	From Inclusive Education to Real Scale Transfer (FIERST)	Bulgaria

Table 6. Good practices of networks and accreditation

These good practices collectively highlight the vital role of institutional networks and formal recognition systems in advancing sustainability education across Europe. Several initiatives, such as the *Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network*, *Escoles Verdes* in Catalonia, and the *Eco-Schools Programme*, highlight how national and international networks can provide structure, peer

support, and scalability. These networks foster collaboration among schools and educators while ensuring continuity of environmental values and educational goals.

Accreditation mechanisms—like the widely recognized *Green Flag* award—are central to motivating schools to maintain high standards in sustainability practices. This is evident in the *Eco-Schools* and *Green Kindergarten* programmes, where clear criteria and periodic assessments lead to formal recognition, enhancing both credibility and commitment.

Other programs, such as Hungary's *Forest School Program* and *AGLT* in Romania, emphasize community-driven and non-formal education, where networking and peer learning substitute for rigid accreditation. These models are particularly effective in rural or decentralized contexts, promoting engagement through flexibility and inclusiveness.

Meanwhile, innovative frameworks like the *Pilot Network of Green Schools* and the *FIERST* project reflect a move toward policy alignment and system-wide integration, where networks are used as testing grounds for large-scale educational transformation.

2.4.1 Frameworks

Networks and accreditation schemes rely on well-defined frameworks that articulate goals, standards, and processes for participation and recognition.

- The Green Flag Programme, used by *Eco-Schools* globally and adopted in Romania, Hungary, and other countries, provides a tiered, criteria-based accreditation framework. It guides schools through a process of environmental self-assessment, planning, implementation, and review, ultimately leading to Green Flag certification—a visible, motivating achievement.
- The *Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network* and *Escoles Verdes* in Catalonia similarly follow national frameworks for accreditation, where schools or kindergartens apply for official titles (e.g., "Green Kindergarten" or "Escola Verda") through a structured application and evaluation process led by ministries or regional governments.
- Some initiatives, such as the *Pilot Network of Green Schools* (under Romania's Recovery and Resilience Plan), function as testing grounds for new frameworks, aligning with national policy goals while still evolving the criteria and processes for long-term institutionalization.

- The *FIERST project* and *AGLT* illustrate networked learning frameworks, where accreditation is less formal but based on peer recognition, shared values, and collaborative learning, particularly in youth-led and non-formal education settings.

2.4.2 Enabling factors

Networks and accreditation systems thrive when certain conditions and supports are in place:

- Strong institutional support and policy alignment are crucial. In cases like *Eco-Schools Romania* and *Escoles Verdes*, the active involvement of education ministries, local governments, or environmental agencies lends credibility, legitimacy, and resources to the network.
- Clear criteria and recognition pathways—such as those in the Green Flag model—offer tangible incentives for schools to participate, including increased visibility, reputational benefits, and community engagement.
- Capacity-building and peer learning are core strengths of these networks. Many, like *AGLT* and *Hungarian Forest Schools*, emphasize training, mentorship, and knowledge exchange among members, which strengthens practice and spreads innovation organically.
- Integration with global and regional movements, such as the international *Eco-Schools* program, connects local initiatives to broader advocacy efforts and funding opportunities, enhancing sustainability and visibility.

2.4.3 Challenges

Despite their strengths, network-based and accreditation-driven models also encounter several barriers:

- Resource disparities can limit participation. Schools in rural or underserved areas may lack the staff, funding, or infrastructure to meet accreditation requirements, as noted in various *Green Flag* and *Forest School* contexts.
- Administrative complexity and reporting burdens can deter engagement, especially in smaller schools or kindergartens with limited capacity. The formal processes associated with accreditation may feel overwhelming without streamlined support.

- Maintaining quality and consistency across a growing network poses ongoing challenges. As networks expand, ensuring that all members adhere to common standards—while allowing for local adaptation—requires robust monitoring and support mechanisms.
- Sustained motivation and renewal are essential. Accreditation frameworks that rely heavily on initial enthusiasm may struggle to maintain momentum unless there are regular opportunities for reflection, renewal, and recognition.

2.4.4 Transferability

One of the key strengths of these good practices lies in their adaptability and scalability—though this varies based on context:

- International frameworks like Eco-Schools are highly transferable due to their flexible design, multilingual resources, and global support structures. They can be tailored to national curricula and local environmental contexts while maintaining core principles.
- Nationally developed systems, such as *Hungary’s Green Kindergarten* or *Escoles Verdes*, can inform other regions looking to create their own accreditation schemes, provided there is policy support and stakeholder engagement.
- Youth-led or non-formal networks (e.g., *AGLT*) are adaptable in diverse community settings, especially where formal school systems are less flexible. Their peer-driven nature allows for cultural and local adaptation.
- Transferability is highest when frameworks are modular, low-cost, and supported by open training resources. However, initiatives deeply embedded in national systems (e.g., with language-specific criteria or centralized assessment) may need significant contextualization when transferred.

In conclusion, networks and accreditation frameworks are powerful levers for scaling sustainability in education. They foster collaboration, provide structure, and build shared identity across schools and communities. When supported by strong frameworks, enabling policies, and adequate resources, they can drive meaningful and lasting change. However, to realize their full potential, these models must address issues of equity, administrative burden, and long-term engagement. With thoughtful design and support, many of these initiatives offer valuable templates for replication and adaptation across Europe and beyond.

2.4.5 Alignment with GreenComp

Embodying Sustainability Values

Networks like *Eco-Schools*, *Escolas Verdes*, and the *Green Kindergarten Network* foster a culture of sustainability across entire institutions. Values are communicated through shared principles, eco-codes, and recognition systems. Clear articulation of values and visible commitment through titles or flags are the main strengths.

Embracing Complexity in Sustainability

While some networks incorporate systems-based learning (e.g., *Forest School*), others primarily emphasize environmental behavior change or reporting. Curriculum depth in addressing complexity thus varies across contexts.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures

Accreditation systems tend to focus more on current behaviors and outcomes (e.g., recycling, green spaces) than on futures literacy. Few of these require schools to engage in future-oriented thinking or long-term visioning exercises. Visioning is not embedded as a core criterion or encouraged in many network protocols.

Acting for Sustainability

This is the strongest dimension for networks and accreditation. Schools take on sustainability actions as part of structured plans (e.g., Eco-Committees, Green Week campaigns). Recognition (e.g., Green Flag) is contingent on these actions. There are clear, visible, and rewarding pathways for meaningful student and school-level action.

GreenComp Dimension	Networks & Accreditation
Embodying Sustainability Values	✓
Embracing Complexity	⚠

Envisioning Sustainable Futures	
Acting for Sustainability	

Table 7. Level of alignment of the good practice pedagogical approaches with the GreenComp frameworks’ dimensions Moderate to Low

2.4.6 Inclusiveness

Many national and international networks (e.g., *Eco-Schools*, *Escoles Verdes*) promote whole-school approaches that inherently include social, emotional, and civic learning components. Accreditation systems can incentivize inclusive practices, such as involving families, communities, and student voices in school planning and action. Initiatives like *AGLT* and *FIRST* focus explicitly on rural youth and inclusive scaling, using peer-led or community-based structures to reach marginalized groups.

Accreditation criteria in some cases may assume baseline capacity (e.g., staff time, facilities, reporting capability), which can unintentionally exclude under-resourced schools. Top-down frameworks risk neglecting local social inclusion priorities unless explicitly embedded in their criteria. Networks and accreditation schemes support inclusive culture-building but require intentional criteria and capacity-building to ensure all types of schools and students can participate meaningfully.

3. Conclusions and recommendations

These 55 good practices offer a compelling pan-European portrait of sustainability education in practice. They highlight a spectrum of pedagogical and institutional strategies, driven by diverse agents, adapted across educational levels, and spread through geographically and culturally varied landscapes. The diversity itself is a strength—illustrating that no single model dominates, but rather that sustainability in education is best approached through contextualized, flexible, and participatory frameworks.

Addressing the interconnected challenges of sustainability and inclusiveness in education calls for more than one-off solutions—it requires a coordinated, strategic mix of initiatives that collectively drive systemic change. One effective method for managing such complexity is the portfolio approach. In education, a project portfolio allows organizations to support a range of interventions—from proven, low-risk programs to innovative, high-potential experiments—all aligned with overarching goals. This structured diversity enables educational institutions, NGOs, or government bodies to balance short-term impact with long-term innovation, creating a dynamic and resilient system for advancing sustainability and equity. Such an approach encourages a distributed ownership of sustainability goals—aligning with the logic of diversified, risk-balanced portfolios. Diversification of effort minimizes over-reliance on a single project or strategy. Strategic alignment ensures all initiatives support common sustainability and inclusiveness goals. Each initiative (course, program, or collaboration) is framed as a contributor to core competencies. Learning and adaptation are built in, as high-risk projects yield insights even when they fall short. Scalability is made possible by identifying which successful projects can be expanded or replicated. Recognizing the importance of flexible adaptation and reflection becomes crucial in managing an evolving portfolio of educational projects.

Recommendation: Have a strategic mix of initiatives.

The good practices on pedagogical models demonstrate how sustainability education can be deeply embedded in meaningful, student-centered learning experiences. Whether through living laboratories, civic service, or outdoor classrooms, these approaches offer powerful alternatives to traditional instruction, fostering both ecological literacy and democratic engagement. Having a range of approaches supports the UDL that promotes diverse pathways for engagement, varied means of representation and flexible options to action and assessment. While challenges remain in assessment, equity, and scale, the richness and variety of these practices show that with the right support, transformative learning for sustainability is not only possible but already thriving in classrooms across Europe.

Recommendation: Have a multitude of pedagogical approaches.

The good practices on curriculum innovations illustrate the diverse ways in which curriculum can act as a powerful driver of change in education systems and reveal how embedding sustainability into educational content can transform both what students learn and how they engage with the world around them. By aligning with robust frameworks, enabling teachers through resources and training, and navigating the real-world challenges of implementation, these initiatives point to scalable, inclusive, and future-ready models of education.

Recommendation: Implement curriculum innovations to embed sustainability into educational content; align these with robust frameworks, enable teachers through resources and training and navigate the real-world challenges of implementation.

The good practices on networks and accreditation demonstrate how these mechanisms serve as powerful tools for institutionalizing sustainability practices in education. By creating structured pathways for collaboration, recognition, and capacity building, these initiatives help scale environmental education and ensure consistent quality across diverse contexts.

Recommendation: Use networks and accreditation to create structured pathways for collaboration, recognition and capacity building.

Curriculum reforms, institutional strategies, and strategic partnerships that help embed sustainability at a systemic level highlight whole-school or whole-institution approaches, with leadership buy-in and policy alignment being key enablers. Other good practices seem to be driven by motivated individuals—teachers, NGOs, or community actors—often working creatively despite institutional constraints. While both approaches are valuable, this contrast points to the need for both bottom-up innovation and top-down support to make sustainability education and inclusiveness widespread.

Recommendation: Provide top-down support to bottom-up innovations.

All three categories of good practices demonstrate strong alignment with the values and action dimensions of GreenComp. However, envisioning the future remains underdeveloped, particularly in networked models, which often focus on present-focused environmental action. Curriculum innovations fare better in complexity and futures thinking, especially when paired with EU-level frameworks like GreenComp or Key Competences. Strengthening these weaker

dimensions, especially futures literacy and systems awareness, could make these interventions more balanced and transformative in their approach to sustainability education.

Figure 5. Radar chart showing how each category of good practices aligns with the GreenComp framework dimensions.

Recommendation: Support the uptake of the GreenComp framework with special emphasis on the Embracing Complexity and Envisioning Sustainable Futures dimensions.

Across the good practices, inclusiveness is addressed to varying degrees and through different strategies.

Category	Inclusiveness Strengths	Challenges
Pedagogical Approaches	Flexible, student-centered, culturally and socially responsive	Requires trained, reflective educators to ensure all learners benefit
Curriculum Innovation	Tailored models for equity, language inclusion, re-engagement of excluded learners	Less focus on universal design, varied digital access
Networks & Accreditation	Whole-school inclusion ethos, potential to scale inclusive practices	Risks of exclusion in resource-poor schools unless inclusion is prioritized

Table 8. Inclusiveness strength and challenges of good practice categories

Recommendation: Take advantage of the above strengths and address the challenges.

While building a professional knowledge base of educational good practice (tested, shared and adapted) is necessary, it still needs to be supplemented with a culture of improvisation and experimentation in teaching. Good practice in education is always contested at least from two perspectives: on the one hand, there is the issue of reliability of the evidence base; on the other hand, there is the irreducible challenge of adapting good practices to contexts, which requires modifications in the original practice. Hannon (2006) proposes the concept of "next practice"—innovative, teacher-led experimentation that complements tested good practices. Next practices complement, rather than conflict with, well-established good practices that are supported by strong evidence. They introduce room for freedom and creativity within the evidence-based framework of teaching, encouraging experimentation that starts with teachers. In this way, next practices serve as a foundation for future good practices by fostering creativity and adaptability within teaching. **Recommendation: Allow for and support next practices.**

While the terms *good practice* and *next practice* may suggest forward-thinking approaches in education, they are grounded in a particular vision of innovation that carries implicit value judgments about what is deemed "best" or worth pursuing next. The focus on "what works" often reflects specific priorities—such as efficiency, effectiveness, or quality—that are shaped by underlying values. Biesta (2010) contends that educational desirability cannot be determined solely through measurable outcomes or proven success. Rather, education should be understood as a form of transformative praxis—an ongoing process of critical reflection and action that questions prevailing norms and redefines what constitutes "good" education by examining and challenging the social conditions that influence these judgments.

Recommendation: Critically reflect on innovations and good practices.

4. Compendium of good practices

Pedagogical Approaches

1. [PT] Oeiras Experimenta

Thematic area of the good practice	Environmental Monitoring and Awareness; Participatory Science and Community Engagement; Education for Sustainable Development
Good practice title	Oeiras Experimenta
Good practice content	<p>"Oeiras Experimenta" is a pioneering citizen science project designed as a "living laboratory" that actively involves the local community in scientific research and environmental monitoring. The initiative empowers students, residents, and local institutions to collaborate on gathering, analyzing, and interpreting environmental data, particularly focusing on air quality and biodiversity in the municipality of Oeiras.</p> <p>The project fosters active involvement across generations—from school children to elderly citizens—creating a diverse and inclusive learning environment that strengthens community bonds and promotes lifelong learning while enabling participants to co-create knowledge and data by directly contributing to scientific data collection and analysis, thus transforming citizens into co-researchers and valuing local knowledge alongside academic expertise to democratize science; "Oeiras Experimenta" integrates formal school curricula with informal community settings, maximizing reach and impact by linking practical scientific inquiry with educational goals and focusing on relevant local environmental issues such as air pollution and biodiversity loss to make sustainability concepts concrete and relevant, thereby motivating community action and policy dialogue, all supported by user-friendly digital tools and open data platforms that enhance transparency, accessibility, and citizen empowerment to facilitate broader participation and real-time monitoring. Through workshops, outdoor activities, and digital platforms, "Oeiras Experimenta" creates a multi-layered dialogue between researchers, educators, citizens, and policymakers, bridging the gap between science and society. This hands-on approach not only generates valuable local data but also nurtures an informed and initiative-taking citizenry.</p>
Financial data	The project is financed by the European Union under the IMPETUS program, which supports citizen science initiatives focused on environmental

	<p>monitoring and sustainable development. While specific budget details are not publicly disclosed, EU-funded projects of this nature typically operate with multi-year funding ranging from several hundred thousand to over a million euros, covering coordination, materials, training, and community engagement.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Map and align with SDGs: Explicitly connect project activities with Sustainable Development Goals — particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land) — to frame local action within global sustainability frameworks and attract broader support.</p> <p>Strengthen Multi-Sector Partnerships: Formalize collaborations between schools, universities, municipal bodies, NGOs, and EU programs to secure resources, expand expertise, and ensure continuity beyond project cycles.</p> <p>Develop Robust Impact Assessment Tools: Implement comprehensive evaluation metrics to measure scientific contributions, educational outcomes, social inclusion, and policy influence, using qualitative and quantitative data.</p> <p>Enhance Digital Engagement and Training: Invest in training facilitators and participants on digital tools and scientific methods to improve data quality, participant confidence, and long-term engagement.</p> <p>Expand to New Themes and Demographics: Consider broadening the scope to additional environmental and social topics, as well as targeting diverse community groups such as early childhood, underserved neighborhoods, and adult education.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yvnqJh2zi84, https://www.cienciacidada.pt/project/33, https://www.itqb.unl.pt/science-and-society/ciencia-cidada/oeiras-experim-nta-laboratorio-vivo</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>"Oeiras Experimenta" started around 2022 (ongoing) as part of a Oeiras Municipal Council together with IMPETUS initiative and has been running continuously since then, adapting and expanding its activities. The project duration aligns with EU funding cycles, often spanning 3 to 5 years, with plans</p>

for continued sustainability through integration in local educational and environmental policies.

OEIRAS EXPERIMENTA

CIÊNCIA + CIDADÃ

Oeiras Experimenta: Climate-Smart Crops for Sustainable Food Production is a citizen science initiative that brings researchers and local communities together to study alternative and underused crops, addressing climate change and contributing to Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals.

2. [ES] Rainwater for Toilets: A Practical Approach to Water Conservation in Schools

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainable Resource Management and Environmental Education
Good practice title	"Rainwater for Toilets: A Practical Approach to Water Conservation in Schools"
Good practice content	<p>This sustainability initiative involves collecting and reusing rainwater to flush toilets in Escola Pia schools. The project was implemented as a real, hands-on example of how schools can reduce water consumption and promote sustainable resource use.</p> <p>Key features include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Installation of a rainwater collection system on the school's roof. ● Storage tanks that hold the collected rainwater. ● Pipes and filtering systems that redirect the rainwater to supply toilets. ● Educational signage and student-led presentations explaining the system to the whole school community. ● Integration of the project into science and environmental education, where students learn about the water cycle, resource efficiency, and sustainable infrastructure. <p>This project not only reduces the school's environmental footprint but also serves as a living lab where students can see sustainability in action.</p>

<p>Financial data</p>	<p>The initial investment includes:</p> <p>Installation of gutters, tanks, filters, and plumbing: approximately €5,000 – €8,000 depending on the school’s size and existing infrastructure.</p> <p>Annual maintenance costs are minimal (around €100–€200 per year), mostly related to cleaning filters and monitoring water use.</p> <p>Funding has come from a combination of school budgets and occasional support from environmental grants or local sustainability initiatives.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Assess your building structure beforehand to plan for effective water collection and storage.</p> <p>Engage students in the process—include them in planning, awareness campaigns, and ongoing monitoring.</p> <p>Combine technical implementation with curricular content to maximize educational value.</p> <p>Work with local plumbers or environmental engineers to ensure proper installation and maintenance.</p> <p>Share the impact—post savings in water use and CO₂ reduction to encourage community pride.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Escola Pia de Catalunya – Sustainability Projects: https://www.escolapia.cat</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>Ongoing since its installation in selected schools around 2020.</p> <p>It is a permanent infrastructure improvement with long-term sustainability and educational impact. Monitoring and maintenance continue each academic year, often tied to student projects.</p>

3. [HU] Tisza River PET Cup for Youth (“Tiszai PET Kupa”)

Thematic area of the good practice	waste collections, water management, community-driven initiative
Level of the good practice	regional, following the River Tisza in Hungary
Good practice title	Tisza River PET Cup for Youth (“Tiszai PET Kupa”)
Good practice content	<p>The “Tiszai PET Kupa” is a creative, community-led environmental initiative. Launched in 2013 by the non-profit Természetfilm.hu, the initiative mobilizes teams to remove plastic waste—primarily PET bottles—from the Tisza River, from Lake Tisza and then use the collected bottles to build functional, human-powered boats. These vessels compete in a multi-day “regatta for the river,” drawing attention to the pollution problem while celebrating ingenuity, teamwork, and sustainability. There are various voluntary initiatives to collect plastic bottles from Hungarian rivers like Tisza or Bodrog, but there is one dedicated for students specifically.</p> <p>The program is structured across multiple rounds. To qualify for participation, teams of school groups or youth clubs must first complete a three-round online quiz competition in spring, followed by the submission of a motivational video. The organizers assess not only factual knowledge, but also creativity, enthusiasm, and environmental commitment. The top 10 teams, nearly 100 young participants in total, are selected to advance to the live competition. These have included teams from both Hungary and neighboring countries such as Romania and Ukraine. One or two supporting educators accompany each youth team.</p> <p>Before setting sail, the teams—nicknamed “PET pirates”—receive thorough safety training from the Upper Tisza Region Rescue and Diving Association, a long-standing partner of the event, and from experienced water-tour guides. The training focuses on safe navigation and water conduct, ensuring that all participants are confident and protected during the full length of the event. The clean-up covers the Dinnyéshát–Kisköre river section and includes both canoe- and bicycle-based waste collection, extending the impact onto adjacent floodplains.</p> <p>What makes the PET Cup unique is its blend of environmental clean-up, public education, and playful competition. Teams are awarded not just for collecting the most waste, but also for fairness and creativity. All boats are ceremonially dismantled and their materials recycled at the end. Through</p>

	<p>strong visual storytelling, including short films and social media campaigns, the initiative amplifies its environmental message far beyond the riverbanks. Since its inception, the PET Cup has removed more than 150 tons of waste from the Tisza and its tributaries. A single race often yields 5–8 tons of collected waste, sorted and partially recycled during and after the event. Over 60 PET boats have been constructed and dismantled in the spirit of reuse and circularity. The initiative is regularly covered in national and regional media, reaching hundreds of thousands of viewers via social media, short documentaries, and news features. Its educational impact is further amplified through the PET Kupa’s public workshops, community days, and collaboration with national parks and local governments.</p>
Financial data	<p>The event is a civil initiative, it is supported by the Ministry of Public Administration and Regional Development, State Secretariat for Active Hungary.</p>
Recommendations	<p>A vast collaborative network ensures the success of the event. Waste management is coordinated by the Association of Environmental Service Providers and Manufacturers, a key professional partner of the PET Cup, while Tisza Public Waste Management Nonprofit Ltd. assists in the proper transport and disposal of municipal waste. Environmental education elements are enriched by expert presentations from the Middle Tisza District Water Directorate, the Humusz Waste Prevention Alliance, the Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research, the Szolnok Local Food Basket Community, the Hungarian Ornithological and Nature Conservation Society, Tiszavirág Ecotours, and geographer Péter Balogh, who introduces the cultural and natural landscape of the Tisza region.</p> <p>To support cleanup logistics and real-time engagement, a Hungarian-language mobile app and an online Tisza River waste map were used for waste mapping. Konasoft provides digital infrastructure and mobile app development. On the water, safety was ensured by the Upper Tisza Region Rescue and Diving Association. Key corporate partners include Henkel, a long-standing supporter of river cleanups; DHL Global Forwarding Hungary, the event’s logistics partner; and Tisza Shoes, offering eco-friendly product sponsorship.</p>
Further information	<p>https://petkupa.hu/eng/</p>
Duration of the program.	<p>Since 2013 – continuously active and expanding</p>

4. [PT] Brigada #MARVIVO

Thematic area of the good practice	Marine sustainability, civic engagement, youth leadership
Good practice title	Brigada #MARVIVO
Good practice content	<p>Brigada #MARVIVO is a dynamic coastal initiative that promotes ocean literacy and environmental citizenship through hands-on, student-led activities focused on marine conservation. Rooted in the Alentejo region, the program mobilizes schools and youth groups to organize beach clean-ups, conduct scientific monitoring of marine biodiversity and pollution, and engage in awareness campaigns aimed at fostering sustainable attitudes toward the ocean.</p> <p>This initiative stands out for its emphasis on empowering young people as leaders in environmental action, equipping them with critical scientific thinking skills and a sense of responsibility toward their local coastal ecosystems. Students learn to identify and report on pollution sources, understand the ecological importance of coastal resilience, and advocate for sustainable practices both locally and beyond. By integrating educational components with community involvement, Brigada #MARVIVO effectively bridges formal learning and real-world impact, supporting the development of active, informed citizens capable of influencing environmental policies and behaviors.</p>
Financial data	The program is supported by a partnership of local authorities, environmental NGOs, and the Eco-Schools framework, ensuring sustainable funding and resource sharing. This multi-stakeholder approach enables consistent delivery of activities and access to educational materials, logistical support, and outreach channels.
Recommendations	<p>Strengthen connections with national and international ocean conservation campaigns to increase visibility and share Good practices.</p> <p>Expand monitoring and clean-up activities to operate year-round, incorporating seasonal biodiversity assessments and pollution tracking.</p> <p>Develop training modules for youth leaders to enhance their skills in scientific</p>

	<p>data collection, public speaking, and project management.</p> <p>Encourage collaboration between schools across different coastal regions to foster a network of young ocean ambassadors.</p> <p>Use digital platforms for wider dissemination of data and campaign outcomes to engage the broader community and policymakers.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Brigada #MARVIVO 2025 Praia de Caxias Oeiras – Eco-Escolas</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>Since 2019 – ongoing</p>

5. [ES] Fishing for Sustainability (Galicia)

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The project focuses on transforming the social and environmental reality of the local environment.</p> <p>Keywords: Education for Sustainable Development, Environmental Sustainability, Social Transformation, Marine Environment, Local Community Engagement, Resource Preservation and Conservation, Critical Thinking and Civic Consciousness, Sustainable Habits and Practices, Agenda 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 8 (economic growth), 13 (climate action), and 14 (life below water)</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>Engaging with Fishing: Transforming the Social and Environmental Reality of the Surroundings Through Education for Environmental Sustainability</p> <p>Spanish title: Enredando en la pesca: Transformando la realidad social y ambiental del entorno a través de la educación para la sostenibilidad del medio</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The project, implemented by CEIP Torre Illa, aims to introduce students to the rich natural and socioeconomic environment of A Illa de Arousa and emphasize the crucial need for its preservation. The island's economy and social structure are deeply rooted in the sea, through artisanal fishing and shellfish gathering. The project seeks to address the threats to the island's natural environment, such as the rise of tourism, overexploitation of marine resources, and pollution, by fostering a social transformation towards sustainability. It was designed to counteract a perceived loss of cultural connection and knowledge of the marine environment among students.</p> <p>The project adopted an Integrated Documentary Project methodology, involving all teachers and students through various learning and service-learning projects. This approach fostered collaborative work and aimed to develop students' knowledge of natural and social sciences, geography, history, and culture, specifically in relation to A Illa de Arousa. It also promoted the ethical and safe use of information and communication technologies, critical thinking, and students' capacity to be active agents of</p>

change for environmental and social sustainability. Key competencies worked on included linguistic communication, digital competence, personal, social, and learning-to-learn competence, and civic competence.

Main activities included:

- **Regeneration of a clam nursery** in Riasón beach as a service-learning project, in collaboration with local fishing guilds.
- **Visits to the A Illa de Arousa fish market** to understand its operations and the production/sales cycle.
- Creation of a **monographic school magazine** compiling local fishing anecdotes, oral traditions, research on marine species, and journalistic works by students.
- **"And you, which beach are you going to?"**, an activity to visit and learn about different coastal areas, promote beach care, and create a large mural showcasing local beaches.
- **A monographic study by 6th-grade students on productive sectors**, highlighting the importance of the sea sector in the locality.
- **"Women of the Sea"**, where 4th-grade students analyzed roles in sea trades and interviewed shellfish gatherers for the school radio.
- An investigation by 6th-grade students into **"Native flora and invasive species"**.
- Linking school calendar commemorations to the project's themes.
- Activities like **"You really are a good fish."** and **"Click on your sandwich"** from the "Eat well" program, connecting the project with healthy eating and marine conserves.
- **"Fishing for Books"** from the school library, promoting project-related bibliography and student creations.
- **"Pull the net"**, an initiative to compile classroom works on oral tradition and the sea.
- An **exhibition of student-produced materials** at the Museum of Interpretation of Preserves of A Illa de Arousa, which had a significant impact on the educational and local community.
- The **creation, editing, and publication of a "Calendar of endangered flora and fauna of A Illa de Arousa"** by 5th-grade students, which was widely

	<p>distributed by the local City Council.</p> <p>The project's success was significantly bolstered by the active involvement of all teachers and students, as well as key local agents such as the Fishermen's Cooperative of A Illa de Arousa, the Department of Tourism of A Illa de Arousa, and the Producers' Organisation OPP20. Families were also highly involved.</p>
Financial data	Fishermen's guilds and European funds.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Based on the project's success and findings, the sources offer several recommendations for similar initiatives and the continuation of this project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensitize students to environmental care through activities that allow them to understand the unique characteristics, ecosystems, and native flora and fauna of their environment. ○ Identify the most urgent local needs as a starting point to prioritize actions for sustainable development. ○ Secure the active involvement of the entire educational community (teachers, students, families) and local agents (institutions, businesses) tied to sustainable development to maximize the project's impact. ○ Integrate learning situations and project-related content into the curriculum of various subject areas, alongside planning complementary activities. ○ Disseminate the project through social media, the press, associations, and involved stakeholders to raise awareness and potentially gain support from other organizations. ○ Maintain and consolidate this collaborative project in the future, particularly by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Collaborating with the City Council on local and global sustainability actions, such as the European program "Clean Energy for Islands EU". ■ Continuing with in-house projects focused on education for sustainable development, like an ecological school garden, composting, and promoting healthy eating with local products.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further exploring and valuing the sociocultural richness and diversity of the local environment through school commemorations and classroom curriculum work.
Further information	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://sites.google.com/view/enredandocoapesca/inicio</p> <p>Virtual visits to the "O Canto do Mar" Interpretation Classroom: https://opp20.com/o_canto_do_mar</p> <p>Project in the Web Seminar "The Comprehensive School Approach to Sustainability": https://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/mc/sgctie/educacion-para-sostenibilidad/seminario-enfo-que-integral/experiencias-educativas/16-marzo.html</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>The project's initial evaluation, design, and task distribution took place at the beginning of the school year. The development of the activities was carried out throughout the entire school year, with the month of June dedicated to its dissemination through an exhibition at the local museum.</p>

6. [GR] We act together for Nature and Man

Thematic area of good practice	Environmental Education, Sustainability, Health and Consumption, Human Rights, Community and NGO Cooperation
Level of good practice	School, School Group
Good practice title	"We act together for Nature and Man"
Good practice content	<p>The Primary School of Nea Fokea designed and implemented a program of actions aimed at cultivating environmental awareness, strengthening fundamental values and activating students as responsible and sensitive citizens. Through experiential experiences, the students came into direct contact with the natural environment, participated in actions that upgraded the school and local space and took an active role in addressing contemporary social and ecological issues.</p> <p>The active participation of the local community, such as municipal authorities, parents' associations and cultural institutions, contributed substantially to the enhancement of the value of the actions for the local community. The activities incorporated elements of Education for Sustainable Development, and were directly supported by individual Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), such as Quality Education (SDG 4), Climate Action (SDG 13), Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11) and Justice and Equity (SDG 10 & 16).</p> <p>The implementation of the program at the Primary School of N. Fokea was based on a holistic, pedagogically differentiated and interdisciplinary approach, which highlighted the connection between cognitive fields such as environmental education, art, nutrition education and social empathy. These educational practices encouraged collaboration, self-activity and active involvement of students at all stages of the actions – from planning to implementation and evaluation.</p> <p>The teaching approach included experiential and exploratory activities and the implementation of projects, exploiting the dynamics of the school</p>

community. Actions such as the renovation of the school garden, the experiential visits to KEPEA of Thermi, the action "From wheat to bread", the coastal cleaning campaign and the interventions with the Itinerant Library, were functionally linked to the learning objects as well as to attitudes and behaviors that promote sustainability.

The program was designed for students aged 7 to 12 years old and pedagogical criteria were used that considered the needs and characteristics of each age group. The course of implementation was prioritized starting from simple and targeted information and awareness actions, while it resulted in more demanding forms of active participation and initiative by the students of the older classes. The proper planning and careful implementation of the activities ensured the systematic participation of all members of the school community.

The main objective of the program was to strengthen children's environmental perception, cultivate social responsibility and highlight their role as future active citizens, through a pedagogical approach based on experiential experience and action.

The actions were implemented with the cooperation of the teaching staff, students, parents, local bodies and the Education Consultant.

Specifically, the following were implemented:

- Educational action for the protection of the environment in collaboration with the NGO Cleaningans, during which the students actively participated in experiential activities and proceeded to the cleaning of residential areas of Nea Fokea, enhancing their environmental awareness through practice.
- "A flower of love": creative action on Mother's Day, with plantings and handmade creations.
- Voluntary cleaning of the coast of N. Fokea with the participation of iSea and the school community.
- Upgrading of the school garden with planting of aromatic plants, cleaning and artistic interventions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informative action on fire safety and fire prevention in collaboration with the Fire Department. • Action with the Itinerant Library of the Network for Children's Rights on the Environment. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An awareness action on healthy eating, with experiential activities and a celebration dedicated to proper eating habits, responsible consumption and their impact on the environment and climate change. • Nutrition education and environmental awareness actions for the younger classes. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational excursion to KEPEA Thermi with activities in nature to understand the concept of sustainability. • Experiential workshop on "From wheat to bread" with emphasis on nutritional self-sufficiency and respect for the earth. <p>The action strengthened the ecological sensitivity of the students and contributed substantially to the creation of a school environment of cooperation and responsibility.</p>
Financial data	<p>The actions were designed in such a way as to be economically viable, utilizing volunteerism, sponsorships from the Parents' Association, the support of the Municipality of Nea Propontida and the active participation of the local community. Material needs were mainly met by recyclables, offerings and resource reuse.</p>
Recommendations	<p>The implementation of the action plan contributed to the formation of a school environment that promotes environmental responsibility and active citizenship.</p> <p>For the implementation of such interventions, the following are proposed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilization of innovative technological tools through which the interest and participation of students will increase. 2. Systematic involvement of the local community and institutions (Municipalities, associations, scientific and cultural institutions) to support and enhance participation in actions of environmental interest.

More information	Director of Dim. Figure. N. Fokeas: Krassas Apostolos Tel. School: +302374081242
Duration of the program.	Dissemination throughout the school year.

7. [GR] Our Sustainable School

Thematic area of good practice	General education on sustainability
Level of good practice	A first-level school with the possibility of expanding at local and national level
Good practice title	Our Sustainable School
Good practice content	<p>Actions were carried out with the aim of promoting environmental awareness and sustainability. Through these actions, teachers take an active role in shaping a pedagogical culture that supports sustainability and responsible citizenship, positively influencing the entire school community.</p> <p>The selection of axes based on the Sustainable Development Goals is chosen from the beginning of the school year.</p> <p>Indicatively, we mention the following actions:</p> <p>Tree plantings were carried out (olive trees, fruit trees, ornamental shrubs)</p> <p>Within the framework of the "Active Citizen" curriculum, we dealt with the olive tree and more specifically, in addition to planting new trees, pruning and harvesting fruits was carried out on the already existing olive trees.</p> <p>Recycling actions were carried out throughout the school year (plastic, paper, caps and even clothes)</p> <p>School yard cleaning</p> <p>Cleaning actions on the beach</p> <p>Food collection for the Social Grocery of the Municipality</p> <p>The actions focus on two important goals: sustainable cities and communities, where students are informed and motivated about urban issues and cultural heritage, and responsible consumption and production, with an emphasis on waste reduction and sustainable consumption.</p> <p>Participating in these programs is a unique opportunity to inspire our students to become responsible citizens and contribute to the creation of a</p>

	<p>sustainable and better world.</p> <p>It is helpful to organize informative events for parents and students to raise their awareness about sustainable development and the Global Goals, as well as information on the actions implemented by the local community.</p>
Financial data	<p>Participation in the programmes is based on the contribution of human resources, including teachers who will coordinate the actions, pupils who will actively participate in the activities and parents who will support environmental and social actions. The necessary materials include items for workshops, such as recyclable materials, planting equipment, and digital media such as computers and interactive whiteboards. Infrastructure, such as classrooms and outdoor spaces, will host the activities.</p> <p>The cost of the activities was supported by the Parents and Guardians Association, the Municipality of N. Propontida and the teachers</p>
Recommendations	<p>It would be good to have flexibility in terms of securing financial resources for actions.</p> <p>It is important to involve as many teachers as possible in the school unit.</p> <p>It is essential to exchange information between schools, to create a Sustainability network and possibly a "bank" of good practices, so that there is support for teachers.</p> <p>An important element is the common targeting of the school, with the creation of a vision that will attract children, parents/guardians and the local community.</p>
More information	<p>School Director: Anastasia Poukoulidou</p> <p>Contact Phone: +302373 350414</p>
Duration of the program.	<p>The program was implemented throughout the year.</p>

8. [TR] Eco-Friendly Classroom Initiative

This initiative was implemented in Karaali Lower Secondary School in Beyşehir, a rural area in Konya, Türkiye. The classroom-wide campaign aimed to reduce the use of single-use plastics and raise awareness of waste sorting among students. Activities included designing posters, peer-led education sessions, and setting up labeled recycling bins in classrooms.

This good practice aligns with Türkiye's 'Sıfır Atık' (Zero Waste) policy spearheaded by the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change. The Zero Waste movement promotes waste reduction, recycling, and sustainable practices, especially in educational settings. It also supports the Ministry of National Education's (MoNE) 2023–2025 Strategic Plan, which encourages eco-schools and environmental education. The initiative is particularly important in rural areas like Beyşehir, where access to structured environmental education is limited, and local ownership of sustainability efforts creates long-term impact.

Thematic area of the good practice	Waste Management and Environmental Awareness
Good practice title	Reducing Classroom Plastic Use via Student Leadership
Good practice content	The students actively led the process of reducing plastic use by initiating awareness campaigns, designing informative materials, and monitoring plastic waste in the classroom. Teachers facilitated by aligning these activities with science and social studies curricula. The campaign involved weekly class discussions on environmental responsibility, and students took turns in managing the recycling bins.
Financial data	No additional financial cost was incurred. Existing school materials were reused, and recycling bins were provided by the local municipality. Teacher facilitation was done within regular lesson hours.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Encourage student-led environmental campaigns to enhance ownership and responsibility.- Integrate sustainability themes into subject-based learning to maximize curriculum impact.

	- Leverage local municipality support for material supply and recognition.
Further information	Initiative summary, student posters, and visual documentation are available in the school's local report. Focus group transcripts also include feedback from teachers and parents on its impact.
Duration of the prog.	Ongoing since March 2024

9. [GR] Young & Old Gardeners

Thematic area of good practice	General education on sustainability at national level.
Level of good practice	National
Good practice title	"Young & Old Gardeners: Sustainable and Sustainable Education through Nature"
Good practice content	<p>It is included in the actions of the active citizen in Axis 11 "Sustainable Cities and Communities" and concerns the national action of strengthening active citizenship in the context of the development of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and is addressed to students of six (6) age levels, grades A to F of Primary School and includes proposals for actions and programs to achieve the expected learning outcomes of the Active Citizen Actions Curriculum.</p> <p>Topics: Sustainable development, Education for sustainability, Environmental education, School garden, Development of green spaces in urban areas, Ecological awareness, Collaborative and experiential learning, Outdoor education, Responsibility.</p> <p>Within the framework of the holistic school approach and based on the principles of sustainability, the school community undertook initiatives for the creative and functional reconfiguration of the schoolyard. The aim of the action was to transform a traditional, typical courtyard space into a hospitable, natural and educationally usable space that enhances experiential learning, environmental awareness and social interaction. It is an experiential action, which helps in the social-synesthetic development of children, has a catalytic effect on the adoption of an environmentally responsible behavior, cultivates skills and attitudes, enhances good practices for recycling old objects and certainly creates a more colorful, lively and pleasant school environment.</p> <p>The intervention was implemented with the cooperation of teachers, students, parents, local bodies and the Education Consultant. It included,</p>

	<p>among others, the recycling of materials for new creative uses, plantings, acquaintance with the herbs and ornamental plants of our country, school tree care work, constructions with natural or recyclable materials, creation of relaxation and play corners, bird feeders, as well as the integration of elements of environmental education in the space and in the planning of educational work.</p> <p>The action "Young & Old Gardeners" was an essential experiential learning experience that strengthened the students' contact with the natural environment, promoting their ecological awareness and understanding of the principles of sustainability. Through the cultivation and care of plants and trees, the students took an active role in the protection and promotion of their school space, developing responsibility, consistency and team cooperation.</p> <p>The result of this collective effort was the aesthetic and functional upgrade of the school space, which was transformed into a living place of learning, observation and inspiration. A school that is not just a place of education, but an organization that learns, evolves and transforms through collaboration, creativity and connection with nature.</p> <p>During the week of action, the choice of the topic and the way it is presented allows more teachers to participate in the teaching and educational process.</p> <p>It is proposed to organize visits to Education Centers for the Environment and Sustainability, the Botanical Garden in Thessaloniki, the Water Supply Museum in Thessaloniki, the Kazakis Viticultural House in N. Gonia, Halkidiki, and the Gerovassiliou estate in Epanomi.</p> <p>On the Environment Day (5 June), the school was established to implement environmental volunteer actions, tree planting, cleaning of coasts and parks, as well as recycling and reuse of materials, actions for the protection of biodiversity and the organization of joint actions with local associations.</p>
Financial data	Financial support from the Municipality of N. Propontida and with donations from the Association of Parents and Guardians and the School's benefactors.

Recommendations	
More information	<p>Principal of the Primary School: Vogiatzis Christos</p> <p>School Phone: +302399023985</p> <p>Action team: Vogiatzis Christos, Kotsopoulou Elissavet, Evgeniadou Violetta, Sarvanis Nikos</p>
Duration of the program.	Dissemination throughout the school year.

10. [GR] We are joining our forces for water

Thematic area of good practice	General education on sustainability at national level
Level of good practice	National
Good practice title	We are joining our forces for water
Good practice content	<p>Topics: Water, climate change, water scarcity, water conservation, water purification, nanotechnology</p> <p>At the 3rd Board of Directors of the Prefecture of Moudania, an action plan was prepared in the framework of the Collective Planning of Educational Work entitled "Act and Learn". One of the actions of this plan concerned the value of water, the visible risk of water scarcity and the ways to clean and save this precious commodity. This action is related to Goal 6 "Clean Water and Sanitation" and Goal 13 "Climate Action" and was included - like the entire Action Plan - in the Active Citizen Actions under the terms of the holistic school approach.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → The action was attended by students of grades 4-6 who, on World Water Day (March 22nd), were informed by their teachers about the serious problems of global water scarcity. → Afterwards, a teleconference was held with the National Center for Research in Natural Sciences "Demokritos" to inform them about nanotechnology methods regarding purification and water conservation. Thus, they were informed about the nanoscale and the research orientation of this scientific field, were informed about the nanomaterials used to purify water and acquired knowledge about the connection of nanotechnology with everyday life using devices, such as water filters. → The students of the sixth grade then conducted a poll with printed questionnaires to the students of grades C-F regarding the use of water and the waste that is carried out inside and outside the school

	<p>by them to record the trends that exist regarding the attitude of the student population. They processed the results and posted them on the school's website as well as published them in the school newspaper.</p> <p>→ At the end, all the students involved held a painting exhibition and posted drawings and posters with messages about the value of water.</p>
Financial data	No financial resources were required for this action.
Recommendations	
More information	<p>Principal of the Primary School: Kalogeraki Artemis</p> <p>Tel. School: +302373025880</p> <p>Action team: Skarmoutsos Ioannis, Kremmyda Agoritsa, Tsanasidou Evdokia</p>
Duration of the action	2 weeks

11. [ES] Efficient with the Environment (Murcia)

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The overarching thematic area of this good practice is Education for Sustainable Development. The project specifically focuses on promoting sustainability and environmental care within an educational center. It aims to foster the responsible and efficient use of natural resources and serve as a model for environmental stewardship and care. The practice's core identity is the defense and protection of the environment from a sustainable perspective.</p> <p>Keywords for this thematic area include sustainable development, environmental Care/Protection, climate Change/Crisis, efficient Use of Resources, energy Efficiency, Eco-auditing, Recycling, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle (3Rs), Carbon Footprint, Sustainable Development Goals (ODS), Community Involvement/Education, Renewable Energy and Zero Waste</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>Efficient with the Environment</p> <p>Spanish title: Eficientes con el medio ambiente</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The project is implemented by the IES Eduardo Linares Lumeras in Molina de Segura, Murcia. Its goal is to become a leading example in environmental stewardship, addressing the challenges posed by climate change through responsible and efficient resource use. The core philosophy is to "think globally, act locally".</p> <p>Point of Departure (Challenges): The project began by acknowledging several weaknesses and threats within the educational center:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scarcity of economic resources for long-term environmental education plans. ● Absence of a dynamic and participatory pedagogical model for environmental education. ● Lack of family support or real concern for natural environment conservation. ● Student disconnection from activities during semi-presential learning.

- **Inadequate building orientation**, leading to hot classrooms, unusable sports fields, and cold areas.
- **Inefficient heating and cooling systems** with high repair costs.
- **Imperfect building insulation** with inadequate materials.

Objectives: The project established fundamental objectives to address these challenges and promote sustainability:

1. **Acquire knowledge, values, and practical skills** for responsible participation in environmental problem prevention and solution, and environmental quality management.
2. **Understand and practically develop eco-audits** within the educational center and family environment.
3. **Develop student research skills**, facilitating resource and idea exchange, and promoting reflection.
4. **Foster teamwork and research** as fundamental pillars for development, contributing to engaged citizens committed to sustainability.
5. **Disseminate the work** to encourage similar proposals in other educational centers.

Methodology: The project employs a **multidisciplinary approach**, involving various didactic departments. Students are central to the transformation, seen as the driving force for sustainable development. The aim is to involve students in acquiring responsibility and environmental awareness through local actions to achieve a sustainable quality of life and contribute to global transformation in line with the ODS. Key competencies developed include literacy, mathematics, science, technology, engineering, digital, personal, social, learning to learn, citizenship, entrepreneurship, and cultural awareness and expression.

Main Activities and Workshops:

- **Eco-auditing:** Studying utility bills, gathering data on water and electricity consumption, and conducting field work and analysis.
- **Vocabulary Development:** Creating a dictionary with necessary vocabulary for the project.

- **Responsible Consumption ("3Rs"):** Activities centered on **reducing, reusing, and recycling:**
 - Designing a garden and tables with recycled materials.
 - "Recycling Christmas" workshop and decorating classrooms with recycled materials.
 - Designing a reusable snack container to reduce plastic and aluminum foil.
 - Publicity campaigns on energy saving (Mural "SOS", versioned paintings, stop motion advertisements).
 - Language department activities including vocabulary puzzles, water saving murals, songs about renewable energy, and signage about waste and its lifespan.
 - **Gamification:** Creating sustainability-themed games like "¡Caída genial!" and "Mi entorno me cuida, yo cuido de él".
 - **Sustainable School Garden:** Constructing "Mi tahullica verde" with local government and foundation support, involving field, classroom, and center activities.
 - **Field Trips:** Excursion to the Mar Menor with an environmental awareness workshop.
 - **Program Participation:** Involvement in the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training's Environmental Education Centers Program, focusing on circular economy.
- Innovative Aspects:** The project highlights several innovative measures:
- Pioneering the **use of solar panels** as a clean energy source.
 - **Reduced electricity consumption** through the installation of thermal films and LED lights in classrooms.
 - Creation of **outdoor classrooms** (Aula Verde and Aula Atrio) to foster student connection with nature.
 - Planting new trees adapted to the climate to act as **CO2 sinks**, along with updating the old irrigation system.

Financial data	<p>The sources indicate a scarcity of economic resources for implementing medium and long-term environmental education plans. It is also noted that the lack of economic endowment or investment from institutions to foster this ecological transition is insufficient. No specific financial figures are provided.</p>
Recommendations	<p>The project outlines several future objectives and recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Achieve greater family involvement. ● Maximize the potential of the newly inaugurated ecological garden. ● Immerse in new environmental education projects that involve collaboration with the Erasmus commission. ● Continue to foster a strong environmental commitment in students through the Tutorial Action Plan and teaching efforts. ● Advance in energy-saving measures, such as installing flow restrictors (perlizadores) in all faucets. ● Promote activities and presentations focused on environmental improvement and clean energies, not only in the center but also in students' homes, through the School Health Education Plan. ● Urge greater involvement and support from institutions. ● Register with the carbon footprint, compensation, and CO2 absorption projects registry of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge. ● Reach the goal of zero waste, especially plastics. <p>The project also provides "inspiring elements" for others to replicate the experience, emphasizing that the value of innovation lies in encouraging others to copy it. This involves:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awareness: Empowering students by making them conscious of the educational center's environmental footprint. 2. Continuous Improvement: Once the community understands that challenges can be met collaboratively, fostering a desire for more contact with nature, environmental protection, and awareness.

	<p>3. Collaborative Action: Forming student and teacher working groups to identify new projects, seek more training, and increase the involvement of the entire educational community in small actions to reduce the ecological footprint.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-7-eficientes-con-el-medio-ambiente_182266/</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>The activities described in the project were carried out during the 2020/2021 and 2021/2022 academic years. The project's timeline was divided into phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Phase I (Prepare): October 2020 (1st trimester 2020-2021). ● Phase II (Action): November - January 2020-2021 (1st and 2nd trimester). ● Phase III (Results/Calculations): February 2020-2021 (2nd trimester). ● Phase IV (Measures Undertaken): 2nd and 3rd trimester 2020-2021. ● Phase V (Consolidation Measures): During the 2021-2022 academic year.

12. [ES] Birds, Let's Fly Together! (Catalonia)

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), Sustainability, Inclusive Education, Sustainability Competences, Environmental Education, Biodiversity, Ecosocial Issues/Problems, Climate Change, Green Transition, Sustainable Development Goals (ODS/SDGs), GreenComp Framework, School Education, Educational Reforms, Policy Innovation, Inclusive Pedagogy/Practices, Natural Environment as Pedagogical Resource, Experiential Learning, Project-Based Learning (PBL), Citizen Science, Teacher Preparedness/Training, Rural Areas/Schools</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>Birds, Let's Fly Together!</p> <p>Spanish title: Proyecto pájaros. ¡Volemos juntos!</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The school implementing it has the Escola Verda (Green School) distinctive and is part of the Xarxa d'Escoles Sostenibles de Catalunya (Network of Sustainable Schools of Catalonia). The project aims to leverage natural school spaces to awaken scientific interests, favor biodiversity, and foster knowledge, respect, and esteem towards nature.</p> <p>It emerged from an interest in improving the environment and providing solutions to an environmental problem, specifically addressing the decreasing populations of birds. It is closely linked to Sustainable Development Goals (ODS), particularly ODS 15 (Life on land) for favoring biodiversity, ODS 3 (Health and well-being) for creating a more natural and pleasant space, and ODS 4 (Quality Education) for offering a rich learning environment. The school is described as sensitive to ecosocial problems. A key aspect is using the natural environment as a pedagogical resource.</p> <p>The project involves transforming outdoor school spaces into a favorable habitat for birds. This includes several phases and activities that have been</p>

introduced over different school years:

Fase 1: Introduction of feeders to provide food during winter and attract birds, and nest boxes to favor nesting conditions. Scientific method is applied to problems related to feeders, and students experiment with bird behavior in experimental nests. Research extends to the forest to find natural nests and identify birds by their songs.

Fase 2: Construction of a bird observatory for direct and indirect observations using camera traps, allowing for registration of species and individual counts.

Fase 3: Planting peanuts and cereals in the vegetable garden to provide food for the birds, aiming for self-sufficiency and giving purpose to plant cultivation.

Fase 4: Participation in a citizen science initiative by providing data on nests to the Asociación Nius.

The project also includes a bird ringing workshop. The project aims for students to become sensitive, critical, and active individuals who know, respect, and act for environmental conservation. It utilizes methodologies such as Problem-Based Learning (ABP), Service-Learning (ApS) (through citizen science), and the scientific method. Content from various curriculum areas is integrated, including Natural Sciences (species, biodiversity, bird biology/ecology, population trends, human impact, citizen science, ecosocial awareness), Language (oral/written expression, scientific nomenclature), Technology/ Digitalization, Art Education (plastic/visual art, design), Civic and Ethical Values (empathy, collaboration, rigor, respect), Physical Education (motor skills, interaction with environment), and Mathematics (number sense, spatial sense, algebraic sense, stochastic sense). It also focuses on developing key competencies: linguistic, STEM, digital, entrepreneurial, personal/social/learning-to-learn, and citizen competency. The project involves the entire educational community, including teachers, students, and families, as well as external agents like naturalist entities.

<p>Financial data</p>	<p>The project collaborated with La Roca Village, which provided discarded materials to build structures like the observatory and the insect hotel, to optimize resources and reduce waste. However, no specific financial costs or budget information is provided in the sources.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>The section "¿TE ANIMAS?" (Are You Up For It?) provides a series of steps for others to follow, which can be seen as recommendations:</p> <p>Step 1: Observe your environment and think about naturalizing school outdoor spaces.</p> <p>Step 2: Seek complicities by sharing your idea with the team and creating an impulse group.</p> <p>Step 3: Get advice from naturalist entities or people with training in natural sciences.</p> <p>Step 4: Present and share the idea with the entire educational community.</p> <p>Step 5: Plan and program, suggesting inspiration from their project and acting in phases, starting with placing feeders and nest boxes.</p> <p>Step 6: Act, putting the project into motion.</p> <p>Step 7: Evaluate and continue advancing based on the results.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-17-proyecto-pajaros-volemos-juntos_184925/</p>

Duration of the prog.	<p>Multiple academic years.</p> <p>The project started in 2019 as part of the previous Plan of Education for Sustainability (PES) (2019-2022) and is included in the current PES (2023-2027). It has been developing course after course in the school's annual action plans. Activities are carried out throughout the school year, with specific timings depending on the activity (e.g., nest box exposure in autumn, feeder experiments in winter, nest observations in spring). Therefore, it is an ongoing project that began in 2019 and continues year-round.</p>
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13. [RO] PAL-TIN

Thematic area of the good practice	Youth civic engagement, democratic participation, environmental awareness, non-formal education
Good practice title	PAL-TIN – Youth Participation Councils for Sustainable and Inclusive Communities
Good practice content	<p>PAL-TIN is a long-standing Romanian initiative that fosters youth participation in local decision-making. Since 1994, PAL-TIN has developed a model of local youth councils across Romania, involving secondary school students in structured discussions, democratic simulations, and sustainability projects in cooperation with local authorities, schools, and NGOs.</p> <p>The councils serve as platforms for civic dialogue where young people identify problems in their communities—including environmental, climate, and inclusion issues—and propose practical solutions. Activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public debates with local leaders • Community mapping and sustainability audits • Awareness campaigns (e.g., water conservation, recycling) • Youth-led urban greening or clean-up actions • Participatory budgeting workshops <p>The councils promote competences aligned with GreenComp, especially political agency, futures thinking, and collective action. PAL-TIN supports training of youth facilitators, provides digital tools (consultation forms, planning templates), and helps integrate youth ideas into local planning documents.</p> <p>This model has been recognized for bridging the gap between young people and decision-makers, empowering marginalized youth, and creating inclusive spaces for civic and sustainability education.</p>
Financial data	<p>Operates through a combination of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local council support (venue, logistics) • National youth grants • EU-funded projects (e.g., Erasmus+, European Solidarity Corps) • Volunteer facilitators and partnerships with schools and NGOs
Recommendations	Ideal for municipalities or schools seeking to boost youth voice in

	<p>sustainability and policy matters.</p> <p>It can be adapted as a permanent civic education project in schools.</p> <p>Success depends on facilitator training and institutional openness to youth proposals.</p> <p>Encourage collaboration with environmental NGOs to provide topic-specific mentorship.</p>
Further information	<p>https://www.eea4edu.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/ROMANIA-Building-democratic-school-cultures_EN.pdf</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>Active since 1994; ongoing with national reach and international collaborations.</p>

14.[FI] Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish School

Thematic area of the good practice	Approach and related activities to promote sustainability in school
Good practice title	Waste Processing and Recycling in Finnish School
Good practice content	<p>Phenomenon-based learning (PhBL) is a key feature of Finland’s forward-thinking strategy for education for sustainable development. This comprehensive approach connects academic learning with real-life issues, helping students build strong critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In PhBL, a central theme—such as <i>sustainability</i> or <i>poverty</i>—is explored from different subject perspectives, encouraging interdisciplinary understanding of complex topics. The 2016 Finnish National Core Curriculum requires schools to dedicate 1–2 weeks each year to PhBL projects, underlining its significance in bridging school learning with real-world contexts.</p> <p>In an innovative initiative, Finn Minta and Alteredu Nonprofit Kft. collaborated to develop video-based teaching materials that illustrate how PhBL supports sustainability education. As part of the project, teachers designed and carried out a themed PhBL week on sustainability, with the entire process documented through video. These recordings demonstrate how multiple subjects are integrated and how students’ problem-solving abilities are nurtured. The project’s success in Finland led to its replication in Hungary, where the teaching activities were again recorded to showcase the process.</p> <p>The practice mentioned in this section uses the phenomenon-based approach to education, both Hungarian and Finnish first- and second-graders learn about waste processing and recycling in an interactive way applying multidisciplinary approaches. Students learned about responsible consumption and environmentally conscious decisions through hands-on experiences.</p> <p>Based on Finnish and Hungarian good practices we aim to provide support for</p>

	teachers in sustainability education through Phenomenon-Based Learning method.
Financial data	Unavailable
Recommendations	<p>-Teaching responsible consumption and making environmentally conscious decisions is at the core of promoting sustainability practices for young children (grades 1-2)</p> <p>-Give opportunities to students in class to demonstrate sustainability competences through hands-on activities to enhance their manual abilities and problem-solving skills</p> <p>-Collect and use as much recycled material (from school and home) as possible to make the classroom activity-based, hands on, interactive, creative and at the same time sustainable</p>
Further information	Waste Processing and Recycling Hulladékfeldolgozás és Újrahasznosítás
Duration of the prog.	2022-23
What SDG goals does it support?	SDG 7, SDG 12
Which sustainability dimensions does it cover?	<p>Environmentalsustainability</p> <p>Economic Sustainability</p>

15. [TR] Forest Classrooms and Nature Journaling

Implemented by Vali Kemal Katitaş Primary School in Bozkır, this initiative created a 'forest classroom' in a nearby wooded area. Students participated in weekly outdoor learning sessions focused on biodiversity, ecosystems, and seasonal cycles. Each child maintained a nature journal, combining writing, drawing, and scientific observation. The activity aimed to foster eco-literacy and emotional connection with the local environment, integrating both cognitive and affective learning.

This practice reflects Türkiye's 2023 Education Vision emphasizing holistic and experiential learning. It supports Green Flag School goals and aligns with Türkiye's National Biodiversity Strategy. Outdoor education is especially meaningful in rural areas like Bozkır, where access to nature is immediate and cultural knowledge about the land can be re-integrated into learning. Furthermore, it resonates with the 'Doğa Temelli Eğitim' (Nature-Based Education) principles recently encouraged by the Turkish Ministry of National Education.

Thematic area of the good practice	Outdoor Education, Biodiversity, Environmental Awareness, Eco-literacy
Good practice title	Forest Classrooms: Connecting Learning with Nature
Good practice content	<p>Key features of the programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of a nearby forest as a natural learning environment - Weekly nature walks and observational learning - Cross-curricular integration (science, arts, language) - Student-created nature journals with reflective prompts - Encouragement of mindfulness, empathy, and curiosity about nature
Financial data	No infrastructure was built; natural space was used. Journals were made from recycled paper. Volunteers from the local forestry authority provided support in some sessions. No external budget required.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utilize local natural spaces for regular outdoor education. - Foster emotional engagement with the environment through arts and journaling.

	- Link observations with curriculum objectives in science and language courses.
Further information	Photos and samples of journals are stored in the school archive. Teacher interviews indicated increased motivation and student curiosity. Parents reported greater awareness among children about environmental issues at home.
Duration of the prog.	Ongoing – launched in October 2023 and continued weekly through the academic year.

16. [HU] Compost Bucket Challenge

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainability education – composting, circular economy, parental engagement
Level of the good practice	Local level (Dunaújváros)
Good practice title	“Compost Bucket Challenge” – Engaging Families in Urban Biodiversity Actions
Good practice content	<p>As part of the BiodiverCity project, implemented under the URBACT programme, the Municipality of Dunaújváros has launched a hands-on sustainability initiative in local kindergartens, with a focus on early childhood education for environmental awareness and community involvement. The initiative began with a child-friendly, interactive presentation on composting, designed to introduce the basic principles of organic waste decomposition, soil health, and the importance of reusing natural materials. The sessions were adapted to the needs of young children and were held in a playful and engaging manner.</p> <p>Following the educational introduction, children, teachers, parents, and representatives of the municipality jointly participated in an outdoor community activity. They collected fallen leaves, seeds, nuts, fruits, and other biodegradable natural materials from nearby green areas. This communal leaf-gathering event not only provided the raw materials for composting but also symbolized shared responsibility for urban nature and green space care.</p> <p>Each child then received a personal composting bucket to take home. Together with their families, children were encouraged to collect kitchen scraps such as vegetable peels, fruit remains, and other compostable materials in their buckets. To incentivise continued participation and build motivation, the programme introduced a sticker reward system: each time a bucket was returned filled with compostable material, the child earned a new sticker, fostering a sense of achievement and continuity.</p> <p>The collected materials are transported back to the kindergarten’s own composting station, where they are processed into compost and later used in the school’s gardening and green education activities. These include planting flowers, herbs, or vegetables, helping children see the full life cycle of waste transformed into soil and growth.</p> <p>The programme successfully combines education, action, and community-building, making sustainability a tangible and collective</p>

	<p>experience. It fosters intergenerational learning, builds bridges between the home and the educational institution, and supports the city's broader environmental objectives. It also introduces the concept of the circular economy in a simplified, age-appropriate way, empowering even the youngest citizens to take part in environmentally responsible behaviors. This practice is easily adaptable, scalable, and aligns with both GreenComp competences and broader municipal sustainability strategies.</p>
Financial data	<p>Low-cost implementation. Buckets, stickers, and event organization supported through municipal and URBACT project funds. Main costs are educational materials and event logistics.</p>
Recommendations	<p>Foster strong collaboration with parents and local government. Use playful motivation systems (stickers, rewards). Align with municipal green strategies for scaling and sustainability. Combine environmental education with action-based learning.</p>
Further information	<p>This practice was created under the Biodiversity URBACT Action Planning Networks.</p> <p>https://dunaujvaros.com/gallery/zold_ertekek_az_aranyalma_tagovodaban https://dunaujvaros.hu/doc/35731</p>
Duration of the program.	<p>Since 2023</p>

17. [TR] From Waste to Growth: Composting for a Greener School

Implemented at Vali Kemal Katitaş Primary School in Bozkır, this initiative introduced students to sustainable food cycles through composting. Students collected biodegradable waste from school lunches and turned it into compost using a small-scale garden setup. Teachers guided students in understanding the science behind composting and its environmental benefits. The resulting compost was used to grow vegetables in the schoolyard.

This practice supports Türkiye’s National Strategy for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services and aligns with the Green Reconciliation Initiative (Yeşil Mutabakat Çağrısı) targeting climate action in education. Furthermore, the Ministry of National Education’s 2023 Circular calls for practical environmental activities in schools. Composting is especially relevant in rural Türkiye, where students are often more familiar with agricultural practices. The initiative merges traditional knowledge with scientific learning, promoting sustainable living through experiential education.

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainable Agriculture, Food Waste Reduction, Environmental Science Education
Good practice title	From Waste to Growth: Composting for a Greener School
Good practice content	The school established a compost area using simple bins made from wooden pallets. Students rotated in weekly teams to manage waste collection, observe decomposition, and record changes. Science teachers designed mini lessons around decomposition, soil health, and ecosystems. The school integrated the compost process with its gardening club, allowing students to see tangible results of their environmental efforts.
Financial data	Minimal cost initiative. Compost bins were built with repurposed wood and school garden tools were reused. The municipality supported soil testing and advice. Parental contributions included leftover vegetables and garden tools.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use composting as a hands-on learning tool in science education. - Involve students in ongoing care and data collection for real-world

	<p>learning.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partner with local municipalities or agricultural experts for technical support.
Further information	<p>Photos of compost setup, garden development logs, and student reports were archived by the school. Interviews from the focus group highlighted increased environmental awareness and enthusiasm for outdoor learning.</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>November 2023 – April 2024 (with plans for continuation)</p>

18. [GR] School and Family: Together for a Green World

Thematic area of good practice	General education for sustainability at school level, Environmental Education, School-Family-Community Cooperation.
Level of good practice	School
Good practice title	School and Family: Together for a Green World / Our school garden, a field of learning and creation.
Good practice content	<p>The Good practice of our school focuses on the use of the school garden as a tool for experiential learning and development of environmental awareness in combination with the Skills Workshops (Thematic Circles: Environment – Caring for the Environment / Living Better – Wellbeing). Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Planting of Vegetables and Aromatic Plants: Planting of vegetables and aromatic plants was carried out with the active participation of parents of the students of the first grade. ● Student Cooperation and Volunteering: Sixth grade students participated voluntarily, helping and guiding their younger classmates in the planting processes. ● Specialized Guidance: The supervision and guidance of the planting actions was done by specialized agronomists (parents of students or partners from institutions such as the EEEEEK of Potidea), ensuring the scientific approach and the provision of valid knowledge. ● Planting Aromatic Plants by the Reception Class: The students of the Reception Class planted aromatic plants (oregano and rosemary) in the school garden, developing a love for nature and experiential learning. ● Soil Treatment and Preparation: Systematic treatment of the garden soil, including cleaning and preparation, was carried out in collaboration with the EEEEEK of Potidea and a teacher of Physical Education. ● Informative Actions: After planting and care, the students created informative signs, informing the rest of the students and the community about the actions of the Reception Department. ● Manufacture of feeders for stray animals and birds from recyclable

materials (e.g. yogurt cups and sticks)

- Connection with the Community: The action strengthened the connection of students with the natural environment, cultivated responsibility and cooperation and upgraded the school space aesthetically and functionally, contributing substantially to the creation of a school that learns, evolves and inspires. Elements such as acquaintance with the herbs and ornamental plants of our country, tree planting, cooperation with local agronomists and farmers were included.

Results/Benefits:

The implementation of these practices had multiple benefits:

- Enhancing environmental awareness and love for nature in students.
- Cultivating skills of cooperation, responsibility, initiative and active participation.
- Aesthetic and functional upgrade of the school space, making it more attractive and environmentally friendly.
- Promotion of cooperation between school, family and local bodies (such as EEEK of Potidea), creating a unified educational community.
- Provision of experiential learning that complements theoretical knowledge.

Innovative elements

- Integration of the program into courses (Language, Environmental Studies, Mathematics).
- Use of recyclable materials for constructions (signs, watering cans, etc.).
- Working with local farmers and agronomists for guidance and support.
- Creation of a digital archive with photographic material and recipes based on the vegetables produced.

Success Factors/Difficulties:

The main success factors included:

- The active participation and enthusiasm of the students.
- The valuable assistance and guidance of parents and experts (agronomists). The actions were supported by the Parents and

	<p>Guardians Association, with sponsorships in items (plants, tools, pots) and volunteer work.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cooperation with local bodies (EEEEK of Potidea) that offered know-how and support. • The commitment of the educational staff and school principals. <p>There are no specific difficulties in the implementation of the actions, suggesting effective organization and management.</p> <p><u>Next steps/Recommendations:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuation and expansion of planting actions with new plant species and expanded participation of parents (participation of parents of all grades is expected). • Incorporating more elements of environmental education and sustainable development into the daily schedule. • Organization of a food week with meals that include garden products. • Establishment of actions during the Environment Day (5 June): the school will implement environmental volunteering actions (tree planting, cleaning, care). • Cooperation with local social feeding units for the donation of surpluses. • Investigation of the organization of visits to relevant sites (e.g. Botanical Garden in Thessaloniki, Water Supply Museum of Thessaloniki, Kazakis Viticultural House in N. Gonia, Halkidiki), so that students can acquire further knowledge and experience.
Financial data	With the financial support from the Municipality of N. Propontida and with donations from the Association of Parents and Guardians and the School's benefactors.
Recommendations	
More information	<p>Principal of the Primary School</p> <p>Tel. School: +302373041571</p> <p>Action group: Students from grades A to F, teachers, parents, volunteers from the local community.</p>
Duration of the	This action has been started for two years for the entire school year and will

program.	continue in the following years.
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Title	Our school garden, a field of learning and creation
Thematic area of good practice	General education on sustainability at national level
Level of good practice	National
Good practice title	Our school garden, a field of learning and creation
Good practice content	<p>It is included in the actions of the active citizen in Axis 11 "Sustainable Cities and Communities" and concerns the national action of strengthening active citizenship in the context of the development of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and is addressed to pupils of four (4) age levels, Kindergarten up to grade C of Primary School, D to F grade of Primary School, Junior High School and High School and includes proposals for actions and programs to achieve the expected learning outcomes of the Active Citizen Actions Curriculum.</p> <p>.Topics: School garden, climate change, development of green spaces in urban areas, etc., water management, composting, drought, etc.</p> <p>Within the framework of the holistic school approach and based on the principles of sustainability, the school community has undertaken initiatives for the creative and functional reconfiguration of the school yard. The aim of the action was to transform a traditional, typical courtyard space into a hospitable, natural and educationally usable space that enhances experiential learning, environmental awareness and social interaction.</p> <p>The intervention was implemented with the cooperation of teachers, students, parents, local bodies and the Education Consultant. It included, among other things, planting, getting acquainted with the herbs and ornamental plants of our country, planting trees, constructions with natural or recyclable materials, creation of relaxation and play corners, bird feeders, as well as the integration of elements of environmental education in the area,</p>

	<p>collaboration with local agronomists and farmers.</p> <p>The action strengthened the connection of students with the natural environment, cultivated responsibility and cooperation and upgraded the school space aesthetically and functionally, contributing substantially to the creation of a school that learns, evolves and inspires.</p> <p>During the week, choosing the topic and presenting it allows more teachers to participate in the teaching and educational process.</p> <p>It is proposed to organize visits to the Botanical Garden in Thessaloniki, the Water Supply Museum of Thessaloniki, the Kazakis Viticultural House in N. Gonia, Halkidiki.</p> <p>On the Environment Day (5 June), the school will be established to implement environmental volunteering actions (tree planting, cleaning of the forest, parks and organization of joint actions with local cultural associations, etc.)</p>
Financial data	With the financial support from the Municipality of N. Propontida and with donations from the Association of Parents and Guardians and the School's benefactors.
Recommendations	
More information	<p>Principal of Lakkoma Primary School</p> <p>Chrysoula Zelilidou</p> <p>Tel. School:+302399051260</p>
Duration of the program.	Dissemination throughout the school year.

19. [GR] Participatory Design for the creation of a school Herb Garden

Thematic area of good practice	General education on sustainability at national level
Level of good practice	School
Good practice title	Participatory Design for the creation of a school Herb Garden
Good practice content	<p>The program is addressed to all age groups of the Primary School and can be adapted according to the class. The innovation of the program is based on participatory design processes: the active involvement of students in every step of the project, from design and research to planting, harvesting and care.</p> <p>At Big Bang School, the action was carried out by 22 students of the second grade (7-8 years old). The wider community was part of the project as the installation of the herb garden was done in collaboration with the local community body "Trelis Pomegranate". The program was completed in 4 basic meetings with the community while the class team also worked autonomously on manual (watering, weeding, natural enrichment of soil with ash and crushed wood) but also exploratory work (study of the needs of herbs to make the appropriate choice, research on their properties and utilization when harvested). The 1st meeting included getting to know the people who guided the group, the herbs through our senses, the space where the herb garden will become through drawings, recordings, photographs and measurements from the length of the flower bed to the pH of the soil. The class group until the 2nd meeting carried out experiments to get to know the composition of the soil, Study and selection of herbs, group design of the herb garden utilizing knowledge and imagination. At the 2nd and 3rd meeting, the planting of herbs took place. In the 4th meeting, through group research and presentations, the students deepened the value of their work by learning about the basic properties of herbs and what they offer to humans.</p>

	<p>In the group's council, the topic of the herb garden was approached with interest both for the next steps and for the emotions and the rich experience that its creation offered.</p> <p>Key skills cultivated: imagination and creativity, observation, classification, cooperation, patience and responsibility.</p> <p>Related topics: Improving nutrition, Sustainable farming, Sustainable water management, Soil</p> <p>Cross-curricular exploitation of the project:</p> <p>in mathematics for a) measurements (length and area), b) problem solving</p> <p>in the language for a) production of written language: describing my herb b) love of reading: stories, myths and fairy tales about herbs</p> <p>in the environmental study for a) the life cycle of the plants b) the composition of the soil c) the local flora</p> <p>The children enriched their knowledge of plants, learned the basic characteristics of the most important herbs of the country and were able to delve deeper into the design steps. Creativity and imagination were cultivated in the design part as well as collaboration and responsibility as the children were part of the process from the beginning. At the end of the year, in the cycle we did on the theme of the herb garden, they recognized the value of their efforts, they wondered how the plants will be taken care of while they are missing and they expressed their impatience to see their herbs grow. Personally, a very important lesson has to do with the positive attitude to failure and the flexibility needed when we encounter obstacles and difficulties (hard soil, stopping planting due to a storm).</p>
Financial data	<p>The cost of the activities was supported by the school and the gardening team (teachers and children) who collected income through the realization of a farmer's market with the harvest of the school vegetable garden.</p>
Recommendations	<p>The Ministry of Education should secure the financial resources for this activity and should develop guidelines for the activities. Teachers do not necessarily have the knowledge to carry out the activities related to</p>

	sustainable development, so they need support from specialized bodies of the local community.
More information	<p>It is important to highlight</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that all activities from acquaintance, planning and research were supported with worksheets. - that the process was framed by reflection and completion of questionnaires. - At the end of the year, the project was presented to the parents with the description being entirely done by the students. At the end of the event, they presented their work live and sang with them in front of the garden. - The class team organized and implemented a knowledge quiz (game code: 04153236) about herbs, through their own experience.
Duration of the program.	<p>The program took place from 29/4 to 3/6.</p> <p>Creating a herb garden provides an opportunity to engage the community in a long-term process as it is a living project that has needs and at the same time returns resources to the community.</p>

20.[ES] Sowing Seeds in an Eco-sustainable Environment (Balearic Islands)

Thematic area of the good practice	<p>The overarching aim of this collection is to address global challenges such as inequalities, poverty, climate crisis, and environmental crisis by transforming society into a more just, inclusive, peaceful, and solidary one, and improving relationships with each other and the environment to maintain planetary limits. The specific project aims to achieve a sustainable municipality by educating young children in contact with nature to contribute to a sustainable future.</p>
Good practice title	<p>Sowing seeds in an eco-sustainable environment with all the strengths of the educational community Producers' Organisation</p> <p>Spanish title: Sembrando semillas en un ambiente ecosostenible con todas las fortalezas de la comunidad educativa</p>
Good practice content	<p>The project is implemented by the Escuela Infantil (EI) de Entidad Local (EL) Ses Païsses, an early childhood education center located in a rural area of Sant Antoni de Portmany, Ibiza. The center is described as open and innovative, with a long pedagogical history, and is part of various eco-environmental programs and networks in the Balearic Islands, including the Program of Eco-environmental Centers and the Educational Network for Social Transformation.</p> <p>The project's starting point was the realization that traditional schoolyards were not optimally utilized for learning. This led to a desire from various sectors of the educational community, including families and educators, to transform the outdoor space into an additional learning environment that would foster motor skills, interaction with nature, socialization, and creativity through different forms of play. A key aspect was also to connect the center with its socio-educational context and establish strategic alliances with local institutions and organizations.</p> <p>The project explicitly aligns with the Agenda 2030 and its Sustainable</p>

Development Goals (ODS), particularly emphasizing their impact on children's well-being and rights. The specific ODS addressed are: **ODS 3 (Good Health and Well-being)**, **ODS 4 (Quality Education)**, **ODS 5 (Gender Equality)**, **ODS 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy)**, **ODS 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities)**, and **ODS 13 (Climate Action)**.

The **objectives** included improving outdoor spaces to be welcoming and free, promoting collaboration and participation among all resources, emphasizing **free play, experimentation, and autonomous learning**, and fostering **integral ecological education** by incorporating natural and recycled materials.

The **methodology** involves organizing educational content into three main areas: "Growth in Harmony," "Discovery and Exploration of the Environment," and "Communication and Representation of Reality". These are integrated through **meaningful and stimulating learning situations** that primarily take place in the transformed outdoor "patio" space, using play, experimentation, and movement to develop children's capacities. The project also focuses on key competencies related to cognitive, instrumental, and attitudinal dimensions, emphasizing knowledge and mastery of one's body, social interaction, and language use within a respectful, participatory, and equal environment.

Transversal principles guiding the project include providing an education that fosters integral formation, recognizing children as protagonists, and operating as an **ecosocial school** guided by principles of public education, Ibizan identity, diversity, inclusivity, and consciousness.

Main activities included creating **different experimental and play environments** (e.g., symbolic play, mindfulness, stories, music) within the divided patio spaces, which were adapted initially due to COVID-19 restrictions. Children engaged in playing, experimenting, meditating, and reading, always supported by adults who ensured safety and autonomy. After COVID-19, students can now enjoy the spaces heterogeneously with free circulation.

The success of the project relied heavily on the **active participation and**

	<p>commitment of the entire educational community—including families, educators, children, technicians, and local staff (such as gardening personnel and the Balearic Institute of Nature, IBANAT). This involvement was facilitated through initial meetings with pedagogical staff and families, leading to collaborative workdays for collecting materials and building furniture.</p>
<p>Financial data</p>	<p>Regional and municipal funding.</p> <p>The project overcame this by relying on collaborative efforts, material donations, and a significant amount of volunteer work.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>The project offers a recipe for replicating the educational experience, highlighting several inspirational elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Step 1: Contextualize and Experiment by having participants explore the outdoor space through play to discover new inspirations and opportunities. ● Step 2: Engage in Collective Participation and Debate among educators to analyze tasks and make decisions on materials (emphasizing natural and recycled materials like wood, rocks, ropes, plants, logs, varied textures), furniture, spaces, budgets, resources, viability, and legal regulations. Spaces should be creative, challenging, and allow for autonomy, free play, and experimentation. ● Step 3: Implement Proposals involving the entire educational community for subsequent use by all children. ● Step 4: Conduct Professional Self-Evaluation by the project implementers, including proposing improvements and embracing continuous learning ("unlearning to relearn"), while maintaining enthusiasm for education and new learning.
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-9-sembrando-semillas-en-un-ambiente-ecos</p>

	ostenible-con-todas-las-fortalezas-de-la-comunidad-educativa_184056/
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>The project commenced in the first trimester of the 2021-2022 school year with initial meetings and discussions within the educational community. Contact with various institutions began in the second trimester, and the project was implemented and put into use during the third trimester of that same academic year. It has been instated since that course, implying an ongoing presence in the school's educational approach.</p>

21.[GR] Looking For The Present In The Past

Thematic area of good practice	"ACTION CONCERNING LOCAL HISTORY, CULTURE, CULTURAL HERITAGE AND SUSTAINABILITY"
Level of good practice	DIMOTIKO SCHOLEIO NEON PLAGION HALKIDIKI
Good practice title	Looking for the present in the past: I learn the history of my country and the value of archaeological finds, I preserve, create, evaluate and become an active citizen.
Good practice content	<p>It is included in the actions of the active citizen in Axis 4: Quality Education and Axis 15: Life on Land and concerns the national action of strengthening active citizenship in the context of the development of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and is addressed to students of Fourth Grade and Sixth Grade and includes proposals for actions and programs to achieve the expected learning outcomes results of the Active Citizen Actions Curriculum.</p> <p>.Topics: I know the history of my country, I become an archaeologist, conservator and creator.</p> <p>During the visit to the "Justinian" Center of Byzantine Culture in Nea Flogita, Halkidiki, students will have the opportunity to get to know in an experiential way and with the help of archaeologists and conservators the archaeological excavation and the art of conservation.</p> <p>There will be an excavation square prepared, with buried objects. The students, after being divided into groups (archaeologists, photographers, workers, conservators) with the help of the teacher and by random lottery, begin the excavation with the guidance of the archaeologists. Then, after getting to know the Art of Conservation by attending the open workshops that exist in the space, they will conserve and restore their own findings and finally they will decide, evaluating the object, its exhibition space.</p> <p>All students will first go through the recording stage, having the role of archaeologists - scholars, i.e. they will have in front of them the object that</p>

has been found and preserved, which they will have to record and place on it a tag where the object will be described, it will have a photo before and after its conservation and will have a registration number of the object on it.

Then the students will undertake the design and exhibition of the objects that have been recorded in the previous stage in the museum exhibition and will place the objects in cases, choosing how many and which finds will be exhibited, how they will be grouped, how they will be placed inside the cases, writing if they wish and captions with brief information about each object in the exhibition.

At the end we encourage the students to express their thoughts on the exhibition they organized.

The students will gather, organize, clarify and consolidate everything they learned during their visit to the educational program.

The students make up the vocabulary of excavation and conservation, identify the tools used and describe in the correct order the stages of an archaeological find's journey from the soil to the Museum

The students write their own version of the story of the find. They think about how it might have been used, what might have happened to it and found it buried, what its future story might be.

They make their own clay pots under the guidance of a pottery teacher.

Students can

- Hold a photography exhibition at the school with the photographs of the team of photographers during the archaeological excavation,
- present the stories they made about the history of the subject to the rest of the students
- organize local history festivals where they present the knowledge they have acquired and the historical value of the "Justinian" Byzantine Culture Center.

In the context of the holistic school approach and based on the principles of sustainability, students acquire identity and values, starting from the

	<p>acquaintance with their place and then the promotion of knowledge and attitudes at a global level. The child learns to care, to love, to be interested in his place and consequently in global issues. He acquires an emotional connection with his place and forms an opinion through his active action on both local and global issues. The school community took initiatives for the creative and functional remodeling of the schoolyard. The aim of the action was to transform a traditional, typical courtyard space into a hospitable, natural and educationally usable space that enhances experiential learning, environmental awareness and social interaction.</p> <p>The intervention was implemented with the cooperation of teachers, students, parents, local bodies and the Education Consultant. It included, among other things, planting, getting acquainted with the herbs and ornamental plants of our country, planting trees, constructions with natural or recyclable materials, creation of relaxation and play corners, bird feeders, as well as the integration of elements of environmental education in the area, collaboration with local agronomists and farmers.</p> <p>The action strengthened the connection of students with the natural environment, cultivated responsibility and cooperation and upgraded the school space aesthetically and functionally, contributing substantially to the creation of a school that learns, evolves and inspires.</p> <p>During the week, choosing the topic and presenting it allows more teachers to participate in the teaching and educational process.</p> <p>It is proposed to organize visits to the Botanical Garden in Thessaloniki, the Water Supply Museum of Thessaloniki, the Kazakis Viticultural House in N. Gonia, Halkidiki.</p> <p>On the Environment Day (5 June), the school will be established to implement environmental volunteering actions (tree planting, cleaning of the forest, parks and organization of joint actions with local cultural associations, etc.)</p>
Financial data	<p>With the financial support from the Municipality of N. Propontida and with donations from the Association of Parents and Guardians and the School's benefactors.</p>

Recommendations	
More information	Principal of the Primary School of Nea Plagia, Halkidiki: Stathorou Aglaia Tel. School: +302373031205 Action team: Stathorou Aglaia, Akasi Maria, Vaiou Argyri
Duration of the program.	Dissemination throughout the school year.

22.[TR] Turning Waste into Value

Conducted at Derviş Mustafa Öztunç Primary School in Bozkır, this practice involved organizing a series of creative workshops using recyclable materials. Students collected clean waste (paper, plastic, fabric) and created new usable or decorative items under teacher guidance. The workshops aimed to increase student engagement with sustainability while also supporting creativity and fine motor skills.

The practice supports Türkiye’s commitment to environmental education, as emphasized in the National Education Vision 2023 and Green School Initiatives. It also aligns with the Circular Economy Action Plan of Türkiye, which aims to raise awareness on reducing and reusing waste. In rural areas like Bozkır, such low-cost, community-based initiatives foster hands-on sustainability education and enable inclusive participation, especially among young learners and families with limited resources.

Thematic area of the good practice	Circular Economy, Creative Reuse, and Student Engagement
Good practice title	Turning Waste into Value: A Creative Sustainability Approach
Good practice content	Teachers integrated recycled design workshops into visual arts and science classes. Parents were also invited to attend some sessions, increasing school-community collaboration. Students showcased their creations during a ‘Sustainability Day’ fair, where the broader school community was educated about the importance of reducing waste and reusing materials.
Financial data	Workshops utilized free materials—waste products donated by families. Basic supplies such as glue and scissors were already available in classrooms. No extra funding was required.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Encourage interdisciplinary planning (arts, science, values education).- Include families to build a stronger sustainability culture.- Link student products to school-wide events to reinforce motivation and recognition.

Further information	Photos of products, student testimonials, and event posters were documented and shared on the school’s social media page. Focus group notes confirm high motivation and parent satisfaction.
Duration of the prog.	Conducted monthly between October 2023 – May 2024

23.[ES] The World We Want (Zaragoza)

Thematic area of the good practice	Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), SDGs, community participation, school sustainability, biodiversity, environment, energy, water, recycling, networking, childhood and youth.
Good practice title	<p>The world we want. A globalising experience through project-based learning.</p> <p>Spanish title: El mundo que queremos. Una experiencia globalizadora a través del aprendizaje basado en proyectos</p>
Good practice content	<p>The good practice describes a project implemented at CEIP Maestro Monreal, a public school in the rural municipality of Ricla, Zaragoza. The project's goal was to envision a sustainable municipality and raise awareness of the necessary actions to conserve and improve the local environment. It utilized Project-Based Learning (PBL) as its methodology, allowing students to engage with a central theme based on their interests and prior knowledge. The ODS served as the backbone connecting different curricular learnings.</p> <p>The project involved students from different educational levels, specifically 2nd, 5th, and 6th grades, working collaboratively. Younger students (2nd grade) focused on environmental care and materials, which led to the creation of a model of a sustainable city. Older students (5th and 6th grade) were motivated by technology and developed multilingual QR codes providing information about monuments and buildings in Ricla to value local heritage and help integrate newcomers. The project integrated content from various subjects, including Natural Sciences, Social Sciences, Language, and Artistic-Plastic Education. It also fostered transversal skills like road safety, equality, environmental education, and emotional education.</p> <p>A significant aspect was the involvement of the community, particularly the collaboration with the Ricla Town Hall, and the channeling of student initiatives through structures like the Sustainability Committee and the Municipal Council of Children. This allowed students to engage in public life and contribute proposals for local improvement. The project was motivated</p>

	by participation in the regional "Realidad Sostenible" program and received recognition, such as an award for creativity.
Financial data	School budget and local partnerships.
Recommendations	<p>Recommendations for replicating the educational experience. The steps are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Include proposals in school improvement plans. ● Know your students: Understand their interests, strengths, and weaknesses to plan a motivating project that aids their development. ● Pose a challenge: Present a stimulating and achievable task for the students. ● Help them expand their knowledge: Offer diverse activities and experiences, encourage exploration of the environment, and facilitate collaboration with local institutions and entities. ● Design a final activity: Conclude the project with a collaborative creation where students can apply their acquired skills and knowledge. Teamwork is highlighted for developing personal autonomy, responsibility, empathy, and respect. ● Share your project: Disseminate the students' final product through various means (social media, exhibitions, videos, etc.) to provide feedback, recognize their effort, and involve the community, especially families. <p>A crucial overarching recommendation is the importance of building collaborative networks within the local environment, identifying allies like the Town Hall.</p>
Further information	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-5-el-mundo-que-queremos-una-experiencia-globalizadora-a-traves-del-aprendizaje-basado-en-proyectos_180706/</p>

Duration of the prog.	"El mundo que queremos" was a year-long project during the 2020/2021 school year. Its final activities, such as debates, posters, an outing, and the creation of a model and QR codes, were completed in the third trimester.

24.[PT] Escola da Ponte

Escola da Ponte	A public school with a democratic governance model, project-based learning, and an inclusive curriculum grounded in autonomy, social justice, and sustainability.
Thematic area of the good practice	Inclusive education, participatory democracy, sustainable values
Good practice title	Escola da Ponte
Good practice content	Escola da Ponte is a public school distinguished by its democratic governance model and an innovative, student-centered approach to education. Students actively co-create their learning pathways and participate collectively in decision-making processes, embodying principles of participatory democracy within the school community. The curriculum is project-based, addressing authentic social and environmental challenges that foster critical thinking, autonomy, and responsibility. At the heart of the school's philosophy lies a commitment to social justice and sustainability, encouraging students to develop not only academic skills but also ethical values that support equitable and sustainable societies. This model challenges traditional hierarchies in education by promoting collaboration, inclusivity, and empowerment for all learners.
Financial data	Escola da Ponte is a public school fully funded by the Portuguese State, which ensures its basic operation including infrastructure, teaching and administrative staff, and daily functioning. Alongside this core public funding, the school has also received financial and logistical support from European Union-funded projects, particularly those focused on promoting democratic participation, inclusive education, and sustainable development. These EU funds enable specific activities such as continuous teacher training, international exchanges, and the documentation and dissemination of the school's Good practices. Public funding guarantees the school's sustainability as part of the national education system. Examples of EU support include the European Social Fund (ESF), which backs initiatives promoting social inclusion, quality education, and equal opportunities. Teacher training and pedagogical innovation projects at Escola da Ponte have potentially been

	<p>supported by the ESF. Additionally, while not directly linked to Escola da Ponte, projects like IMPETUS (Improving Public Engagement in Science and Innovation in Portugal and Spain) operate in related fields—citizen science and participatory education—and may share methodologies or partnerships that the school explores.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Promote pilot initiatives to implement democratic and autonomy-based learning models in traditional public schools, adapting Escola da Ponte’s methodologies to different contexts.</p> <p>Invest in comprehensive teacher training programs that focus on autonomy-driven pedagogies, collective decision-making, and project-based learning techniques to ensure fidelity to the model.</p> <p>Encourage the establishment of networks and partnerships among schools practicing democratic education to share knowledge, resources, and Good practices.</p> <p>Embed sustainability and social justice explicitly within curricular frameworks to align with global Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) goals.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>https://www.escoladaponte.pt</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>Since 1976 – ongoing</p>

25.[BG] Different Together

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The thematic scope of this Good practice is within the domain of Educational Integration, Prevention of Discrimination, and Promotion of Intercultural Dialogue in School Settings.</p> <p>It directly supports the objectives of educational policies aimed at the socialization of children from different ethnic, cultural, and linguistic backgrounds. Furthermore, it contributes to the enhancement of civic competences, anti-discrimination education, and the development of socio-cultural sensitivity among students.</p> <p>Key thematic priorities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intercultural Education and Socialization; • Prevention of Discrimination and Promotion of Tolerance; • Non-Formal Learning for Civic Competences; • Support for Educational Integration of Children from Refugee and Migrant Backgrounds; • Artistic Expression as a Tool for Social Inclusion.
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>“Inclusive Community through Creativity – Non-Formal Educational Practices for Intercultural Dialogue at 66th Secondary School ‘Filip Stanislavov,’ Sofia”</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The “Different Together” project, implemented by 66th Secondary School “Filip Stanislavov” in Sofia with financial support from the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM), presents a comprehensive approach to fostering intercultural understanding and social cohesion in an educational setting characterized by ethnic, cultural, and linguistic diversity.</p> <p>The school operates within a community comprising students of Bulgarian, Roma, Turkish, Ukrainian, refugee, and immigrant backgrounds. The diverse composition of the student body outlines a natural context for the implementation of targeted educational measures to support integration and prevent social isolation.</p> <p>The project is structured around three main strategic objectives:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>● Ensuring Effective Socialization: By creating structured opportunities for interaction among students from different ethnic backgrounds, the project fosters the formation of socio-cultural competences and a sense of belonging within the school community.</p> <p>● Raising Awareness and Preventing Discrimination: Through targeted activities, the project enhances students’ sensitivity to discrimination and equips them with knowledge and skills for preventing and addressing discriminatory behaviors.</p> <p>● Promoting Non-Formal Education with Civic Education Elements: Implementation of non-formal educational formats strengthens civic competences, critical thinking, and personal expression among students.</p> <p>Key interventions under the project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>● Club-Based Non-Formal Learning Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>○ Cinema and Theater Club: Utilizes dramatization and scene recreation to explore and address contemporary social issues, particularly focusing on conflict resolution and acceptance of differences.</p> <p>○ Bulgarian Literary Classics in the Theater Club: Supports the development of communication skills and proficiency in literary Bulgarian, identifying and nurturing students' artistic talents through theatrical interpretation of classical works.</p> <p>○ Creative Workshop “Rainbow”: Engages students of different ages and ethnic backgrounds in creative group tasks, utilizing traditional techniques such as modeling, appliqué, weaving, and mosaic making. The works reflect both Bulgarian traditions and those of the students' countries of origin, fostering intercultural respect and shared identity.</p> <p>● Musical and Artistic Initiatives: The formation of the “Cricket” Singing Group and the “Zvezdichka” Cheerleading Band provides additional avenues for creative expression, cooperation, and community building through art and performance.</p> <p>● Use of Innovative Pedagogical Approaches: The project applies a diverse range of methods including simulation, situational analysis, brainstorming, teamwork, storytelling, visual arts,</p>
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	<p>observation, individualized support, and game-based learning, ensuring the active engagement of students and the relevance of the educational content.</p> <p>The total number of direct participants is 68 students, with a diverse ethnic composition reflecting the project’s intercultural integration goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29 students of Bulgarian ethnic origin; • 23 of Roma origin; • 5 of Turkish origin; • 6 from other national backgrounds (including Ukrainian); • 3 from other ethno-cultural communities.
Financial data	<p>The project is financed through the funding mechanisms of the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM).</p> <p>While exact budget figures are not explicitly stated, the funding ensured coverage of the following cost categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement of materials for creative workshops, theater performances, and artistic activities. • Support for the organization of extracurricular clubs and non-formal educational activities. • Human resources, including facilitators and experts leading club activities and pedagogical initiatives. • Logistical costs related to the implementation of events, workshops, and performances. • Awareness-raising materials and communication efforts associated with the project. <p>The financial allocation supported the achievement of the project’s strategic goals, particularly in enhancing intercultural dialogue and fostering social cohesion through creative and civic education.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Creativity as a Tool for Integration: Using artistic expression and creative workshops proves effective in fostering

	<p>intercultural dialogue, enhancing personal expression, and breaking down cultural barriers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>Integrate Non-Formal Education with Formal Learning: Extracurricular activities, when strategically linked with formal educational goals, reinforce civic competences and social skills among students.</p> <p>Foster Inclusive School Communities through Targeted Activities: Organizing club-based activities with mixed groups of students from different backgrounds promotes mutual understanding and collective identity formation.</p> <p>Apply Innovative Educational Methods: Employing varied pedagogical approaches such as simulation, role-playing, and visual arts ensures active participation and meaningful engagement of students.</p> <p>Sustain Multicultural Activities as Part of School Strategy: Long-term commitment to multicultural education initiatives within schools' official development plans is essential for sustaining the results achieved by such projects.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p> Reference Materials and Project Reports: Additional information on implemented activities, project outcomes, and integration practices may be accessed through official school publications and reports on the CEICSEM portal.</p>

Duration of the prog.	<p>Although no specific duration is mentioned, the project is implemented within the framework of CEICSEM’s typical project cycles, which generally cover one academic year (approximately 9–12 months).</p> <p>The project timeline allowed for the comprehensive organization of club activities, artistic performances, and educational workshops, following a structured and continuous engagement model with participating students. The activities appear to be sustained throughout the academic calendar, aligning with school-based extracurricular programs.</p>
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26. [BG] The Game Library

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The thematic focus of this good practice lies within the domain of Early Childhood Education, Family Engagement, Social Inclusion, and Community-Based Learning.</p> <p>The initiative is aimed at fostering educational inclusion of children from ethnic minorities by increasing parental involvement, enhancing motivation for learning, and supporting early childhood development. It directly addresses issues such as social inequality, access to quality education for marginalized groups, and strengthening the family-kindergarten partnership for better learning outcomes.</p> <p>Key thematic areas include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Childhood Education and Pre-School Readiness; • Educational Integration of Ethnic Minority Children; • Parental Engagement and Capacity Building; • Non-Formal Education through Play; • Digital Inclusion and Remote Learning Support.
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>“Together in Learning and Play: The Game Library Model for Early Educational Inclusion in Kindergarten ‘Barborino,’ Sredets”</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The “Game Library” project was initiated by Kindergarten ‘Barborino’ in Sredets, Burgas Region, under the financial support of the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM) through the project “Together in Learning and Games.”</p> <p>The project aims to motivate children from ethnic minorities to engage actively in the educational process by involving their families and creating a supportive environment for learning both in the kindergarten and at home.</p> <p>Key Objectives and Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parental Involvement for Educational Support: The initiative strengthens the capacity of parents—especially from the Roma community—to support their children’s adaptation to kindergarten activities and enhance their motivation to learn.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creation of the “Game Library”: The library was established as a resource center within the kindergarten, providing a variety of didactic games and educational materials developed jointly by teachers and parents. These resources can be borrowed by families, facilitating continued learning at home and encouraging parental involvement in their children's education. ● Capacity Building of Parents and Mediators: Parents who participated in the creation of educational games received training and were empowered to act as peer mediators, motivating other parents to engage in kindergarten activities. Assistant educators and educational mediators played active roles in outreach and supporting children’s inclusion. ● Community-Based Activities and Creative Initiatives: Through initiatives like “Teacher for a Day” and “Let’s Read a Fairytale Together,” parents became active participants in the life of the kindergarten, contributing to building a cohesive educational community. ● Joint Creative Productions: Collaborative productions such as “Grandmother’s Tale” and “Stop at Red” involved children, parents, and teachers, demonstrating inclusive community engagement. These were showcased to the local community, including municipal authorities and children with disabilities. ● Remote Learning Adaptation during Emergency Situations: A digital extension of the Game Library was developed for remote access, utilizing the Smart Classroom platform. Parents were trained to use this platform, ensuring continued learning and interaction in a digital environment during emergencies, thus promoting digital literacy among parents and children alike. ● Systematic and Coordinated Implementation: The project employed a structured methodology involving clear roles for teachers, assistant educators, mediators, and parents, based on system-oriented, object-oriented, and resource-oriented approaches combined with modern interactive teaching methods.
Financial data	The financial support for the project was provided by the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM) within the framework of the “ Together in Learning and Games ” project.

	<p>Although specific budgetary figures are not provided, the funding covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of educational and didactic materials for the Game Library. • Organization of training sessions for parents, teachers, and mediators. • Logistical support for creative workshops, community events, and digital platform implementation. • Development of the remote learning component and access facilitation through the Smart Classroom platform. • Provision of educational kits, worksheets, and supplementary materials for home use by vulnerable children. <p>The financial contribution ensured the sustainability and broad reach of the intervention, fostering both institutional capacity and community involvement.</p>
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Strengthen Parental Engagement as a Core Component of Early Education: Active parental participation enhances children’s motivation and facilitates smoother educational integration, particularly in marginalized communities.</p> <p>Leverage Play as a Learning Tool: Educational play, both within kindergarten and at home, fosters cognitive, social, and emotional development and should be promoted as an essential educational strategy.</p> <p>Use Peer Education Models Among Parents: Empowering parents as mediators and trainers of other parents contributes to community cohesion and extends the impact of educational initiatives.</p> <p>Incorporate Digital Tools for Inclusive Learning: Platforms like Smart Classroom provide valuable opportunities for remote learning and should be integrated into educational strategies for ensuring access during emergencies or for long-term digital literacy development.</p> <p>Promote Creative Community-Based Activities: Joint artistic and educational initiatives strengthen the link between kindergartens, families, and the wider community, fostering a shared sense of purpose and inclusion.</p>

	<p>Ensure Systematic Planning and Clear Role Allocation: Defining responsibilities and coordinating activities among stakeholders—teachers, assistant educators, mediators, and parents—ensures the efficient delivery of inclusive educational practices.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kindergarten “Barborino” Official Information: The kindergarten actively engages in community-based education projects and is recognized within the Sredets Municipality for its innovative practices in early childhood education and integration. • Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM): https://coiduem.mon.bg The Center offers programs and funding opportunities supporting educational inclusion and parental engagement in early childhood education. • Digital Platform – Smart Classroom: The platform was adapted to meet the needs of children and parents during emergency situations, offering educational games and materials for remote learning.
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>The project was implemented within the standard operational cycle of CEICSEM-funded initiatives, typically spanning one academic year (approximately 9–12 months).</p> <p>However, the practice demonstrated the potential for sustainability beyond the project’s official duration, particularly through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ongoing operation of the Game Library within the kindergarten; • Continued parental involvement and peer training; • The established remote learning component, which can be utilized for long-term educational support. <p>The structure of the project suggests a design suitable for both short-term impact and long-term community benefits, with prospects for replication in other educational institutions.</p>

27. [ES] Next Stop SDG 2030: A Very Real Path (Segovia)

Thematic area of the good practice	Key themes include promoting social, environmental, and economic sustainability and contributing to the fulfillment of the Agenda 2030 and its Sustainable Development Goals (ODS/SDGs). It specifically addresses the need to act on challenges like inequalities, poverty, and the climate and environmental crisis.
Good practice title	Next Stop SDG 2030: A Very Real Path Spanish title: Próxima Estación ODS 2030: Un camino muy Real
Good practice content	<p>The Good practice was awarded in the Sustainable Development category of the 2021 National Good practices Contest organized by the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, in modality A. CEIP La Pradera in Valsaín (Segovia), promotes actions aimed at fostering social, environmental, and economic sustainability, encouraging responsible, critical, active, and democratic citizenship. To achieve this, the different groups at the school work on the SDGs by carrying out service-learning activities, imagined as intersecting metro lines.</p> <p>The project uses the concept of Service-Learning (Aprendizaje Servicio) as a core element. It focuses on utilizing the local environment and valuing its cultural and natural heritage. The school implementing it is a Community of Learning, holds a Centro Educativo Sostenible (Sustainable Educational Center) seal, and is part of the UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network. It emphasizes fostering responsible, critical, active, and democratic citizenship.</p> <p>This project, implemented by CEIP La Pradera, is a Community of Learning and a Sustainable Educational Center. It aims to contribute to the Agenda 2030 and the ODS through Service-Learning. The project emerged from the interests of 5th and 6th-grade students and needs detected in their local environment. The core activity involves valuing the cultural and natural heritage of Valsaín, specifically the ruins of the 16th-century Palacio del</p>

	<p>Bosque built by Felipe II, and addressing the issue of littering in the surroundings.</p> <p>The project was structured as a network of projects, with each classroom group ("línea de metro") focusing on a specific ODS or set of ODS. Each group developed its own final product that contributed to the overall project's final product.</p> <p>Activities included creating an eco-field journal, designing route signage, making fabric bags for waste collection, producing informative brochures, developing a project website, and collaborative tasks like creating a logo and slogan, and researching local history, legends, and traditional jobs.</p> <p>The methodology included Service-Learning [5, etc.] and utilized active methodologies, dialogic learning, and the use of outdoor spaces as learning environments. The content was integrated across various curriculum areas.</p> <p>The project significantly involved the entire educational community (teachers, students, and families) and collaborated with external agents like regional education bodies, an environmental center (CENEAM), and the local town council. Students were central to the project as protagonists.</p> <p>Key ODS worked on include ODS 4 (Quality Education) as the main transversal objective and ODS 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) as the main thread. Others incorporated were ODS 17, 15, 13, 3, 5, 12, and 10. Education was considered key to achieving many ODS.</p> <p>The project was designed during the confinement period of the COVID-19 pandemic (2019/2020) and implemented during the subsequent school year (2020/2021), facing challenges related to health measures but also leading to increased use of outdoor spaces.</p>
Financial data	<p>The project was financed by the Junta de Castilla y León through the Dirección General de Innovación y Formación del Profesorado.</p>

<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>The source provides a "Receta para replicar la experiencia educativa" (Recipe to replicate the educational experience), outlining the steps to follow:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define the final product of the Service-Learning project. 2. Choose the ODS to work on. 3. Specify the key competencies to develop. 4. Establish a network of interweaving actions. 5. Define the final products of each network/group and their contribution to the main project product. 6. Specify individual and collective actions that foster a sense of unity in the project. 7. Find the necessary personal and material resources. 8. Ensure there is a coordinating team involved in the design, implementation, and follow-up. 9. Conduct follow-up throughout the process to improve, inform, and monitor progress. 10. Disseminate the experience. It is also recommended to start from the needs of the protagonists (students) and to plan thoroughly but be prepared to adapt to unforeseen issues.
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-6-proxima-estacion-ods-un-camino-muy-real_181947/</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>The project began in the 2019/2020 school year with planning and design. It was then implemented during the 2020/2021 school year. It is presented as an ongoing project that has been developing "course after course".</p>

28.[ES] Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood (Asturias)

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The overarching thematic area of this good practice is Education for Sustainable Development. The project specifically addresses the need to act upon challenges like existing inequalities, poverty, and the climate and environmental crisis, aiming to transform society into one that is more just, inclusive, peaceful, and solidary. It promotes improved relationships among people and with the environment to maintain planetary limits and ensure inclusion at all levels. The project embodies transformative learning for the survival of current and future generations, emphasizing the immediate need to learn and act in defense of our planet.</p> <p>Education for Sustainable Development, Environmental Crisis, Planetary Limits, Transformative Learning, Defense of the Planet, Sustainable Development Goals (ODS), Responsible Production and Consumption, Green Spaces/Areas, Resource Efficiency, Sustainable Lifestyles, Circular Economy, Community, Involvement/Participation, Socio-emotional Well-being, Change Agents</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>Well-living in a Sustainable Neighborhood</p> <p>Spanish title: Bienvivir en un barrio más sostenible</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The project is implemented by the IES Rosario de Acuña, a Compulsory Secondary Education (ESO) and Baccalaureate institute located in the southern part of Gijón. Established in the 1990-1991 academic year, the center has made significant efforts to adapt to its current definitive location since 1997-1998. It is known for its attention to diversity, its involvement with vulnerable students, and its participation in projects, having been a finalist in the Sustainability category of the National Service-Learning Awards. The institute comprises 70 teachers, 560 students, and nine non-teaching staff members.</p> <p>Point of Departure (Challenges and Needs Detected): The project emerged</p>

from the center's annual service-learning initiatives, adapting to contemporary needs. Following the pandemic, the educational community began to **value local environments and resources more**. Surveys highlighted the need to utilize nearby **green spaces** for **physical and emotional health activities**. Specific needs identified through student surveys of families included a **scarcity of sustainable uses in green spaces**, a **lack of community involvement** in managing and caring for public and green areas, and an **absence of playful elements** that foster contact with nature. Adolescents specifically expressed a need to enjoy green and open spaces to counter sedentary lifestyles and digital leisure, as well as a need for community spaces to share experiences and overcome loneliness. The existing school garden was also recognized as an opportunity to engage more vulnerable students, increasing their key competencies.

Objectives: The project established four main objectives:

- To **improve group cohesion** and the **sense of belonging** to both the center and the neighborhood.
- To **enhance oral and written expression skills** and promote **contact with nature**.
- To contribute to the **improvement of the community's emotional state**.
- To **bring green spaces closer to people's daily lives** and foster a **scientific culture**.

Methodology: The project employs a **multidisciplinary approach**, involving various didactic departments and students from all levels of ESO and Baccalaureate, as well as Primary and Infant students from adjacent schools. It emphasizes student participation as a driver for sustainable development, promoting local actions to achieve a sustainable quality of life and contribute to global transformation in line with the ODS. The project's transversal theme is the promotion of **health and well-being**, aiming to build a more welcoming and inclusive environment.

The project focuses on developing key competencies:

- **Social and Civic Competence:** Teamwork, consensus-building, initiative, entrepreneurship, and active engagement with nature in the community.
- **Linguistic Communication Competence:** Analysis of complex texts, script production, oral expression, and selection of texts about nature's benefits.
- **Learning to Learn Competence:** Improved organization and coordination, text structuring, and designing emotional activities in green areas.
- **Cultural Awareness and Expression Competence:** Analysis of texts from different cultures/times and valuing Asturian oral/written tradition.
- **Mathematical and Science, Technology, Engineering Competence:** Assembly of cultivation structures, analysis of statistical data, and preparation of diffusion posters.
- **Digital Competence:** Use of technical media for podcasts, blogs, and project diffusion.

Main Activities and Workshops:

- **Gardening in the neighborhood:** Activities focused on planting and maintaining urban gardens in the surroundings of the center, promoting self-consumption of fresh produce.
- **A window to green areas:** Creation of a video to analyze and propose improvements for neighborhood green spaces, including building cultivation terraces and birdhouses.
- **The feeling of the neighborhood community:** Designing and analyzing surveys to understand green space usage and community demands, fostering active participation.
- **Sayings and idioms:** Searching and selecting texts related to nature's influence on daily life.
- **The colors of the garden:** Studying pigments in fruits, leaves, and flowers, and creating informative posters for public display.
- **Our identity and info panel:** Designing logos and posters for project diffusion, including a temporary/permanent information panel for sharing activities.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reading point: Installing a book-crossing booth in the adjacent park to promote reading in green areas. ● Vertical garden: Creating and placing planters made from recycled materials on the center's fences. ● Sense space: Creating a dedicated area in a neighborhood park for sensory experimentation with nature. ● Music: Selecting music for class changes to enhance the emotional well-being of the educational community and neighborhood. <p>Innovative Aspects: The project highlights several innovative elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The collaboration of the neighborhood association in the development and maintenance of activities. ● The support from the Gijón City Council in providing technical materials for the community garden, which helps ensure the project's continuity. ● The incorporation of this project into individualized work plans for students with Specific Educational Support Needs, which is considered a very powerful lever for inclusion. ● The initiation of collaboration with other nearby educational centers, leading to new joint activities and prompting other centers in Asturias to seek assistance.
Financial data	Municipal and community program support.
Recommendations	<p>The project, which has been in effect since the 2021-2022 academic year, continues to evolve with various actions planned for the 2022-2023 academic year. The authors express confidence that the project will continue to evolve, contributing to the improvement of student teaching-learning processes, the center's context, and the lives of neighborhood residents.</p> <p>To inspire and enable replication of this successful project, the following steps are shared:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Step 1: Analysis of Neighborhood Needs: Utilize methods like forms,

	<p>surveys, or assemblies to identify needs, followed by brainstorming feasible actions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Step 2: Project Ownership: Conduct in-class activities to encourage all student groups to reflect on the use of neighborhood green spaces, and collectively choose a name and motto for the project. 3. Step 3: Design of Actions: Establish necessary coordination and temporal planning. Students should design specific actions for green spaces and propose required resources. 4. Step 4: Coordination and Networking: Collaborate with various entities and institutions, such as the CP Evaristo Valle, EEI Alejandro Casona, Neighborhood Association, AMPA, and Gijón City Council. Implement interdisciplinary work involving various subjects. 5. Step 5: Neighborhood Diffusion: Organize a celebration day to present the project to the community. Invite participating centers, institutions, neighborhood associations, city council representatives, and the press. Prepare exhibitions, guides, and informative leaflets to explain and promote the project. <p>The project's success is attributed to its ability to provide greater motivation for student learning, foster competential development in various skills, and offer significant learning by demonstrating the concrete purpose of their work. The positive evaluation from collaborators has encouraged further actions, and the implemented initiatives continue to be respected and utilized by the entire community.</p>
Further information	<p>Castellano - SGCTIE Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes</p> <p>https://www.libreria.educacion.gob.es/libro/buenas-practicas-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-no-8-bienvivir-en-un-barrio-mas-sostenible_183895/</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>The project was developed during the 2021-2022 academic year. It began as a small school garden project but has since grown. The project continues to</p>

be in effect with various actions in the 2022-2023 academic year.

29.[HU] Green Mission

Thematic area of the good practice	Secondary education for disadvantaged young people in the context of sustainability and inclusion.
Level of the good practice	school- level
Good practice title	Green Mission in the Petzelt József Technical and Vocational School Vác, Hungary
Good practice content	<p>The Green Mission Group was set up following a visit to the Szentendre Zoo Foundation. The Foundation takes in, cares for and treats orphaned or injured animals on a temporary or permanent basis. Inspired by this visit, the idea emerged to create a space where plants could receive care, regenerate, and be returned to their homes. Many people wish to keep houseplants but face challenges in doing so, often due to environmental factors or a lack of knowledge.</p> <p>In our school in Szentendre (Pezzelt József Technikum and Vocational School in Vác), both the facilities and personnel are well-suited to take in struggling plants from the school grounds or from the homes of our students and colleagues, placing them in a sunny place, watering them regularly and taking care of them.</p> <p>The programme mainly involves members of the Eco-working group and two groups of students who are on flexible learning pathways. The Career Guidance Department and the Workshop School welcome young people who either do not yet have a clear idea of the specific field in which they would like to pursue their secondary education or are mostly disadvantaged teenagers, who are not yet of compulsory school age but do not yet have 8 years of primary education. For both groups of pupils, our colleagues place a strong emphasis on competence development, including in emotional intelligence, in the design of the curriculum.</p> <p>Theoretical knowledge about plants, complemented by regular practical activities (transplanting, watering, fertilizing, removing dead parts, "tidying up" the plant), is an excellent complement to the development of personality and competence in these classes. The meeting of pedagogy and ecology takes place.</p> <p>The care of the plants has been ongoing since September, During the Advent period before Christmas (and since then, due to the great success), some of the transplanted and propagated plants are auctioned off for charity by the students and school staff. The proceeds were used to support several social initiatives (Szentendre Zoo Foundation - symbolic adoption, "Nemluxustáska campaign" - donation of toiletry for girls and women living in extreme poverty) on Earth Day we bought and planted a tree (ginkgo biloba) and established an Ecological Award (certificate and gift - Gardena pruning shears)</p>

Financial data	The investment costs of the programme (potting soil, flower pots of various sizes) are minimal and can be covered by donations from staff and parents. Our institution has also received a small grant from the Jane Goodall Foundation's Roots and Shoots group, which was awarded through a competitive bidding process.
Recommendations	<p>Expected environmental and social impacts</p> <p>Developing a relationship with the environment involves not only knowledge but also emotions. A knowledge-based approach alone cannot influence the deep-rooted values that drive individuals to change their behaviour. Environmental education through direct care of plants is emotionally focused: it culminates in connecting young people with nature through interactive experiences.</p> <p>Caring becomes a creative activity and the resulting sense of achievement builds the self-esteem, social competences and initiative of disadvantaged young people to think and take responsibility at an ecological level.</p> <p>The activities outside the classroom, the varied stimulus environment, not only serve recreational purposes, but also prepare young people's nervous systems to absorb and integrate shockingly different information more effectively.</p> <p>Through our project, we can give our teachers a new non-formal educational tool that they can experiment with and integrate into the professional/educational programme of the institution, enriching the methodological culture in the field of environmental education.</p>
Further information	Andrea Nánási, consulting psychologist, environmental psychologist enanasiandrea@gmail.com
Duration of the program.	It is recommended to implement the programme for at least one school year, but it is best to run it continuously.

30.[ES] Social Plans: Ensuring Equal Educational Opportunities for All Students

Thematic area of the good practice	Educational Equity and Social Inclusion
Good practice title	"Social Plans: Ensuring Equal Educational Opportunities for All Students"
Good practice content	<p>The <i>Planes Sociales</i> (Social Plans) initiative of Escola Pia de Catalunya is designed to guarantee access to quality education for students from economically vulnerable backgrounds. This program ensures that no child is excluded from the educational community due to financial hardship.</p> <p>Key aspects of the program include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partial or full financial aid for school fees, books, materials, meals, and extracurricular activities. ● Confidential and respectful process, led by each school's social committee or care team, in collaboration with families. ● Individualized support plans, tailored to the student's needs and context. ● Integration with external social services and local NGOs when necessary. ● Monitoring and accompaniment by school professionals to ensure well-being and academic continuity. <p>The project reflects Escola Pia's commitment to inclusive education and social justice, grounded in the values of solidarity and care for the most vulnerable.</p>
Financial data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The program is funded mainly through Escola Pia's internal solidarity

	<p>fund, which is sustained by contributions from families, alumni, foundations, and supportive organizations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Each school allocates a percentage of its budget to support the program. ● The level of support varies depending on the family’s socio-economic assessment.
<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Institutional commitment is key—social equity must be a core value, not a secondary effort.</p> <p>Ensure confidentiality and dignity in all support processes to maintain student and family trust.</p> <p>Build partnerships with social entities and public institutions to increase impact and resources.</p> <p>Include emotional and academic support, not just financial aid, to foster real inclusion.</p> <p>Promote a culture of solidarity within the school community to sustain long-term engagement.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Escola Pia de Catalunya – Social and Inclusion Programs: https://www.escolapia.cat</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>This is a long-term structural program, deeply embedded in the school network’s identity and social mission. It continues to evolve in response to changing economic and social conditions.</p>

31. [PT] Lab in a Box – Oeiras

<p>Lab in a Box – Oeiras</p>	<p>Lab in a Box is an educational project of Instituto Superior Técnico and INESC-ID designed to foster critical thinking and scientific curiosity. With the support of Oeiras City Council, this project reshapes the current educational landscape in science teaching by providing participating classes with a scientific kit containing all the materials for the practical exploration of curriculum content.</p> <p>The program has trained approximately 114 teachers (74 in Oeiras and 40 in Principe Island) and engaged around 3560 students, focusing on STEAM low-cost practices and environmental sustainability.</p>
<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>Scientific literacy, sustainability, experimental learning</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>Lab in a Box – Oeiras</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The program integrates active, experimental methodologies by incorporating hands-on, inquiry-based learning approaches such as Project-Based Learning (PBL) and citizen science directly into the curriculum, which fosters deeper engagement and understanding; it emphasizes clear educational goals including scientific literacy, student autonomy, and critical thinking skills that are essential for developing informed and responsible future citizens, while also maintaining a strong sustainability focus through the careful selection of materials that prioritize environmental sustainability and promote eco-friendly practices and awareness among students.</p> <p>With enormous potential for expansion to other municipalities, Lab in a Box offers accredited teacher training in experimental education, empowering educators to guide students in scientific discovery. Encouraging collaboration, teachers and students are involved in co-creating activities, for a more engaging learning experience.</p> <p>Beyond the classroom, Lab in a Box creates a community of teachers dedicated to experimental sciences, interacting through annual meetings, workshops, and shared experiences. The project also promotes lifelong learning, instilling a love for science that lasts a lifetime.</p>

Financial data	Funded by the Municipality of Oeiras and supported by Instituto Superior Técnico and INESC-ID
Recommendations	<p>Curricular Integration: Formally incorporate environmental literacy and sustainable thinking competencies within the educational framework to ensure systemic adoption.</p> <p>Impact Indicators: Track key metrics such as the number of teachers trained, kits distributed, classes involved, and instances of collaborative reuse to measure reach and effectiveness.</p> <p>Partnership Development: Leverage existing partnerships with Gulbenkian Institute, the Municipality, and school networks, and explore collaborations with environmental NGOs and higher education institutions to enrich resources and broaden impact.</p> <p>Scalability Plans: Build on existing success by expanding the program’s reach to include preschool, extracurricular activities (AEC), and secondary education levels, ensuring age-appropriate adaptations.</p>
Further information	https://educacao.oeiras.pt/atividades_projetos/lab_in_a_box/Paginas/default.aspx
Duration of the prog.	Since 2019 in Oeiras – ongoing

Lab in a Box

Curriculum Innovations and Educational Policy Initiatives

32.[BG] Sustainability Academy Bulgaria

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainable education Sustainable business
Good practice title	Sustainability Academy Bulgaria
Good practice content	<p>The Sustainability Academy is a dedicated education platform for micro, small and medium enterprises, initiated by Social Innovations Solutions and the Coca-Cola Foundation, providing free access to courses, proven know-how and tools for sustainability. The platform was launched in 2023 in Romania, attracting over 13,000 participants in the first 12 months. Thanks to successful regional expansion, the platform is now available to businesses in Bulgaria, Serbia and Croatia.</p> <p>In Bulgaria, the platform was launched in 2024 in partnership with Cleantech Bulgaria and United Bulgarian Bank, with two core courses in Bulgarian – “Introduction to Sustainability” and “Sustainability in the HoReCa Industry” – and will expand its resources gradually, in line with the specific needs and requirements of businesses in the country.</p> <p>The online training courses are free of charge and aim to support businesses in the process of aligning with applicable EU regulations, as well as providing access to information and practical advice on the impact and benefits that new sustainability requirements add to any business.</p>
Financial data	Funded by Social Innovations Solutions and the Coca-Cola Foundation
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leverage their expertise in vocational education and training (VET) and industry partnerships. If your sustainable education project targets older students (high school, vocational, or university level), consider integrating practical skills relevant to green jobs and sustainable business practices. ● Integrate both environmental sustainability and digital skills into your educational content. Explore how digital tools can support sustainable practices or how sustainability can be embedded in technological advancements. ● Seek out collaborations with businesses and industry, even for projects primarily aimed at schools. Cleantech Bulgaria's

	<p>"Sustainability Academy" is a prime example of a successful public-private partnership (with Coca-Cola Foundation, Social Innovation Solutions, and United Bulgarian Bank).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design educational modules that explicitly address circular economy concepts (e.g., waste reduction, recycling, resource efficiency, sustainable product design). ● Encourage students to think innovatively about solving environmental challenges and explore entrepreneurial opportunities within the green sector.
Further information	https://cleantech.bg/en/project/sustainability-academy-bulgaria/
Duration of the prog.	2023-ongoing

33.[RO] Natural Entrepreneurs

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainability education, STEAM, biomimicry, entrepreneurial skills, interdisciplinary learning
Good practice title	Natural Entrepreneurs (NatEnt) – Biomimicry-Inspired Learning for a Sustainable Future
Good practice content	<p>The Natural Entrepreneurs (NatEnt) project, funded by Erasmus+, offers a nature-inspired entrepreneurship education model for students aged 14–18. It encourages young people to explore local environmental challenges (e.g., waste, water, energy, biodiversity) and respond with sustainable business ideas grounded in the principles of biomimicry—designing solutions by observing how nature works.</p> <p>At the core of the project is a free, multilingual online platform (learning.natent.eu), guiding students and teachers through a six-stage innovation process:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Framing sustainability challenges 2. Observing nature 3. Ideating sustainable solutions 4. Designing eco-business models 5. Testing and feedback 6. Sharing results with peers <p>Students work in national or international teams, supported by digital tools, instructional videos, and educator guides. The platform links real-world sustainability issues to SDGs and GreenComp competences, including systems thinking, critical thinking, adaptability, and collective action.</p> <p>Romania is a full partner in the project via Focus Eco Center, supporting pilot schools and co-developing materials. Teachers and students from rural and urban areas alike participate through classroom-based and extracurricular activities.</p>
Financial data	Funded by the Erasmus+ KA2 Strategic Partnership for School Education (2022–2024). Project materials and platform access are free of charge. Schools only need internet access and guidance from a trained facilitator or teacher.
Recommendations	A strong model for blending entrepreneurship with sustainability

	<p>competences.</p> <p>Can be implemented as an interdisciplinary project, eco-club activity, or classroom module.</p> <p>Teacher facilitation is essential; training sessions and guides are available.</p> <p>Great for encouraging student agency and linking school learning to real-life innovation.</p>
Further information	https://natent.eu/en
Duration of the prog.	2022–2024 (with open access platform and tools continuing after project close)

34.[ES] SUMMEM

Thematic area of the good practice	Innovative Pedagogy and Competency-Based Learning , with an emphasis on collaboration, communication, and real-world problem solving.
Good practice title	"SUMMEM: A Cooperative and Multilingual Learning Model for the 21st Century"
Good practice content	<p>SUMMEM (short for <i>“SUport al Model Metodològic Escola Pia”</i>) is a pedagogical model developed by Escola Pia de Catalunya to promote a more active, meaningful, and inclusive learning experience. It is designed to help students acquire key competencies through cooperation, multilingual communication, and interdisciplinary approaches.</p> <p>Key elements of the model include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cooperative Learning: Students work in structured groups to promote mutual help, shared responsibility, and communication skills. ● Multilingualism: Content is delivered in multiple languages (Catalan, Spanish, English), encouraging flexible communication and cultural awareness. ● Global Competencies: The curriculum is organized around global challenges and real-life situations, helping students connect learning to everyday life. ● Interdisciplinary Projects: Students engage in cross-subject learning tasks that integrate knowledge and skills from different domains. ● Formative Assessment: Continuous feedback and student self-assessment are central to the learning process. ● Teacher Collaboration: Teachers plan together and share practices, building a strong professional learning community.

	SUMMEM is implemented progressively from early childhood to secondary education, adapting the methodology to each stage.
Financial data	<p>The model is funded through the school’s own resources, with some support from internal professional development structures.</p> <p>Key investments include:</p> <p>Teacher training and coaching</p> <p>Collaborative planning time</p> <p>Educational materials and digital tools</p> <p>Estimated annual cost varies depending on the size of the school and the stage of implementation. It can range from €3,000 to €10,000 per school, mainly covering teacher training and coordination.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Invest in teacher training and coaching: A solid understanding of cooperative learning strategies and interdisciplinary planning is essential. -Foster a culture of collaboration: Shared planning time and peer observation help strengthen consistency across classrooms. -Adapt gradually: Introduce changes in phases to ensure teacher confidence and student adaptation. -Encourage student voice: Involve students in evaluating and improving learning processes. -Ensure leadership support: School leadership must champion the model and allocate time and resources effectively.
Further information	SUMMEM official page (Escola Pia de Catalunya): https://www.escolapia.cat
Duration of the prog.	<p>Ongoing since 2016.</p> <p>The program is designed as a long-term institutional change. Schools</p>

	implement SUMMEM over several academic years through a phased process, and it continues to evolve with ongoing reflection and feedback.
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35. [FI] MAPPA Multifunctional Tool for Teachers

Thematic area of the good practice	Resource hub for teachers to implement ESD practices
Good practice title	MAPPA Multifunctional Tool for Teachers
Good practice content	<p>MAPPA.fi is a versatile platform and resource hub for teachers, centered on sustainability education. It provides access to over 300 tools and materials aimed at building sustainability competencies, including educational content, training opportunities, and support services. Teachers and educators can also contribute by uploading their own materials.</p> <p>The platform organizes resources by target audience, learning objectives from the basic and upper secondary education curricula, as well as by topics and themes—making it easy to find relevant content. No registration is needed for basic use. Users can search with keywords, explore thematic folders, or check the calendar for upcoming events.</p> <p>Registered users can bookmark favorite resources, create custom folders, and develop complete learning modules. MAPPA also highlights real-life school projects and outcomes, encouraging the exchange of proven ideas and successful practices.</p> <p>The platform is managed by the Union of Finnish Nature and Environmental Schools and is funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture.</p>
Financial data	Unavailable
Recommendations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Modular & interdisciplinary learning: Use backpacks and MOK-tool (<i>Monialainen Oppimiskokonaisuus</i>—Interdisciplinary Learning Module) to build cross-topic modules to introduce ESD learning 2. Encourage outdoor, experiential, nature-based activities 3. Have teachers showcase their good practices to peers to encourage replication of effective practices. Promote co-creation and sharing of resources among school staff which saves time and enhances collaboration culture in school.

	4. Activities designed for ESD, including assessment, should always be in line with the existing curricular goals and themes, and not in addition to them.
Further information	https://mappa.fi/
Duration of the prog.	Ongoing
What SDG goals does it support?	SDG 7, SDG 12
Which sustainability dimensions does it cover?	Environmental sustainability Cultural Sustainability

36.[BG] The Recycling School: Teachers for a Clean Nature

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainable education
Good practice title	The Recycling School: Teachers for a Clean Nature
Good practice content	<p>"Recycling School: Teachers for a Clean Nature" is a professional online platform designed exclusively for teachers of students from grades 1 to 12.</p> <p>This platform offers a wealth of educational materials focused on crucial topics such as separate waste collection, recycling, waste utilization, environmental protection, and sustainable development. Teachers who register gain access to a variety of valuable resources to support their activities, including sample lessons, games, and competitions that can be conducted both during and outside of class time.</p> <p>The primary goal of "Recycling School: Teachers for a Clean Nature" is to foster a professional community where educators can exchange ideas, share Good practices, provide recommendations, and offer their experiences. Ultimately, the platform aims to support and enhance environmental education by enriching it with current topics and up-to-date information.</p> <p>Serving as both a resource and a hub for communication, the platform provides a vital space for teachers to exchange information and connect with peers who share a passion for environmental education.</p>
Financial data	Funded by EcoPack
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create comprehensive, accessible online educational materials that are tailored for different age groups (e.g., K-12, or specific grade bands). ● Integrate online learning with opportunities for hands-on, real-world experiences. ● Design lessons and activities that encourage students to apply what they learn in their daily lives, leading to tangible actions like proper waste separation. ● Develop resources and support mechanisms specifically for teachers, empowering them to deliver the content effectively

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaborate with organizations that are actively involved in the sustainable practices being taught (e.g., waste management companies, renewable energy providers). ● Invest in creating a dedicated online platform or "Educational Centre" (physical or virtual) that serves as a single point of access for all educational materials and related activities.
Further information	https://www.ecopack.bg/retsiklirashtouchilishte/
Duration of the prog.	2021-ongoing

37. [FI] School Repair Guide

Thematic area of the good practice	Educational tool to help schools and teachers integrate ESD in schools
Good practice title	School Repair Guide
Good practice content	<p>"The Repair Guide – Towards Carbon Neutrality" is an educational tool designed to help schools promote climate action and support well-being. It offers (i) a handbook outlining how the school community can engage in climate work, (ii) 42 climate-related tasks or competence badges for students, usable across different subjects, (iii) a roadmap model featuring four competence badges for the whole school community, and (iv) a carbon calculator available both as an Excel file and an online tool.</p> <p>The roadmap guides schools toward achieving carbon neutrality by 2030. It begins with setting a vision, assessing the current situation, and choosing practical climate actions—eventually forming a school-wide climate action plan.</p> <p>The guide also integrates climate competence development for students and helps identify climate-related perspectives within various subjects. Student activities include evaluating the school’s climate footprint, collecting data, envisioning future goals, exploring past developments, and planning climate-friendly actions.</p>
Financial data	Unavailable
Recommendations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage the whole school Use Repair Teams and workshops for collective buy-in 2. Follow a clear roadmap Map, envision, and act toward carbon neutrality

	<p>3. Embed sustainability Across food, waste, energy, mobility, culture</p> <p>4. Develop competencies Via student and community badge activities</p> <p>5. Leverage tools Carbon calculator to track progress</p> <p>6. Connect with peers Learn from other schools' journeys</p> <p>The mentioned recommendations emphasize community involvement, structured planning, skill-building through badges, data-informed decision-making, and peer exchange—creating a cohesive strategy for embedding sustainable development deeply into school culture.</p>
Further information	https://koulunkorjausopas.fi/en/
Duration of the prog.	2021–2030
What SDG goals does it support?	SDG 4, SDG 7, SDG 12
Which sustainability dimensions does it cover?	<p>Economic Sustainability</p> <p>Environmental sustainability</p>

38.[ES] "Technologies 2.0: Equipping Schools for a Digital Learning Environment"

Thematic area of the good practice	Digital Transformation and Educational Innovation
Good practice title	"Technologies 2.0: Equipping Schools for a Digital Learning Environment"
Good practice content	<p>The <i>Tecnologies 2.0</i> project is an institutional initiative by Escola Pia de Catalunya to digitally equip all schools and integrate technology into teaching and learning processes. The project responds to the growing need for digital competencies, personalized learning, and modern infrastructure in education.</p> <p>Key components include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1:1 device models for students, especially in secondary and vocational education. ● Upgraded internet infrastructure, including high-speed Wi-Fi across all classrooms and learning spaces. ● Interactive digital boards and projectors to enhance classroom interaction. ● Teacher training on digital tools, blended learning, and pedagogical uses of technology. ● Centralized platforms for communication, assessment, and learning management (e.g., Moodle, Microsoft Teams, G Suite for Education). ● Promotion of digital citizenship, responsible use of technology, and ethical behavior online. <p>The project supports not just technological access but also pedagogical innovation, encouraging collaborative, student-centered, and adaptive learning.</p>
Financial data	<p>The program required significant investment in infrastructure and training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initial phase (equipment + connectivity): approx. €50,000 – €150,000 per school (depending on size).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annual maintenance, updates, and training: €5,000 – €20,000. ● Funding sources include school operational budgets, family contributions (for student devices), and external support in some cases (e.g., digital education grants or partnerships with tech providers).
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Start with a clear vision of how technology will enhance learning, not just access. ● Invest in teacher training first, to ensure meaningful integration of tools into pedagogy. ● Create a support structure—technical and pedagogical support teams are essential. ● Engage families and provide guidance on digital use at home. ● Ensure equity by offering solutions for students who may lack access or support outside school.
Further information	<p>Escola Pia de Catalunya – Digital Innovation Projects: https://www.escolapia.cat</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>Launched around 2018 and ongoing</p> <p>Tecnologies 2.0 is a long-term digital transformation strategy, with continual updates and improvements aligned with technological and pedagogical developments.</p>

39.[RO] Programul „Săptămâna Verde” – A National Green Week in Schools

Thematic area of the good practice	Climate change education, environmental literacy, whole-school sustainability, GreenComp active learning
Good practice title	Programul „Săptămâna Verde” – A National Green Week in Schools
Good practice content	<p>The “Săptămâna Verde” program, launched in the 2022–2023 school year via Ministerial Order 3629/2023 and developed in collaboration between the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Environment, promotes a national week of sustainability activities. For five consecutive school days, each pre-university education unit engages students, teachers, and families in inter- and transdisciplinary learning focused on climate change, resource management (waste, water, energy), biodiversity, environmental justice, and green civic action saptamanaverde.edu.ro.</p> <p>The initiative emphasizes hands-on learning—from eco-projects like tree planting, recycling workshops, and debates, to outdoor lessons in protected areas, community cleanup actions, and creative STEM activities. Schools utilize the free online platform (saptamanaverde.edu.ro), developed in collaboration with Code for Romania, which offers lesson plans, digital libraries, municipal maps, and sustainable activity guides edu.ro.</p> <p>Participating schools receive support from central ministries, local authorities, NGOs (e.g., Viitor Plus), and civic tech organizations. The program aims to cultivate environmental attitudes, critical and systemic thinking, adaptation skills, civic engagement, and collective action—closely aligned with GreenComp competences.</p>
Financial data	Funded through the Fondul pentru Mediu , with a dedicated 100 million lei (~€20M) allocated via Ministerial Order 7133/2024 for 2024–2025 implementation. Technical and educational support is provided pro bono by Code for Romania and NGOs like Viitor Plus
Recommendations	<p>Formalize post-week reflection and evaluation sessions to reinforce learning.</p> <p>Integrate local community partners and NGOs to enrich the curriculum.</p> <p>Collect common output metrics (e.g., number of trees planted, hours outdoors) to assess impact.</p> <p>Offer follow-up teacher training for deeper integration of GreenComp</p>

	competences.
Further information	https://www.saptamanaverde.edu.ro/
Duration of the prog.	Launched in February 2023; ongoing and scheduled during the 2024–2025 school year (5-day period selected by schools). Legally mandated through May 2025 and planned for continuation into future academic years.

40.[TR] GreenComp Integration Days

Organized by Derviş Mustafa Öztunç Primary School in Bozkır, the GreenComp Integration Days were designed as thematic project weeks aligned with the EU's GreenComp framework. Each day focused on a different sustainability competence, incorporating class activities, group projects, and interactive workshops. Topics included critical thinking, systems thinking, environmental impact awareness, and collective action. The school adapted these competences to appropriate age levels, creating simple yet impactful activities.

This initiative supports Türkiye's Lifelong Learning Strategy and the new curriculum (Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli), which emphasizes transversal competences including environmental responsibility. The activity also operationalizes Türkiye's 2023 Education Vision, which encourages school-wide projects with interdisciplinary approaches. By translating abstract EU-level GreenComp competences into classroom practice, this model bridges policy and pedagogy in a rural Turkish school setting.

Thematic area of the good practice	Sustainability Competence Development, Curriculum Innovation, Whole-School Approach
Good practice title	Bringing GreenComp to Life: Sustainability Competence Week in Bozkır
Good practice content	<p>Each grade level engaged in daily themed activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Grade 1-2: Storytelling and drawing on protecting nature- Grade 3-4: Sorting waste and visiting local recycling points- Grades 5 and above: Group discussions on local environmental issues and mini action plans <p>Teachers were provided with templates and lesson plans developed collaboratively by the school sustainability team. The programme culminated in an eco-fair showcasing students' work, inviting parents and local officials.</p>
Financial data	School used existing classroom materials. Posters and exhibition materials were made by students using recycled items. No external funding was required. The local municipality supported printed flyers and transportation for the recycling center visit.

Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use GreenComp as a guiding framework for thematic weeks. - Adapt sustainability concepts to the developmental level of students. - Involve the whole school and local stakeholders for greater engagement and visibility.
Further information	Lesson plans and activity guides developed during the event were saved in the school's digital archive. Focus group results noted improved teacher confidence in integrating sustainability into subjects.
Duration of the prog.	1 week – 13 to 17 May 2024 (repeated annually)

41. [BG] Second Chance Schools - Innovative Approaches to Inclusive Education

Thematic area of the good practice	Inclusive education, lifelong learning, reducing early school leaving (ESL), addressing "educational poverty," social inclusion.
Good practice title	Second Chance Schools - Innovative Approaches to Inclusive Education
Good practice content	<p>This project, part of the Erasmus+ S2CENE (STRENGTHENING SECOND CHANCE NETWORKS IN EUROPE) project, explores and promotes the concept of "Second Chance Schools" in Bulgaria. These schools offer an innovative approach to education, particularly for individuals who have left the traditional education system.</p> <p>The project aligns with the European Pillar of Social Rights, emphasizing the right to quality and inclusive education, training, and lifelong learning for all citizens. It seeks to provide knowledge and skills to help individuals find their place in society, especially addressing challenges related to the Fourth Industrial Revolution and high ESL rates in Bulgaria (12%).</p>
Financial data	Erasmus+ KA2
Recommendations	<p>Requires broad educational reforms and cross-sectoral discussions to integrate education policy with other policies, adapting good practices from other sectors to education. Addressing resource allocation, teacher training, attitudes, infrastructure, and policy implementation are key challenges for successful inclusive education.</p> <p>Partners believe that Second Chance Schools' approach is strategic for the capacity building and social, cultural and professional inclusion of young European adults. Thus, the investment on the creation and reinforcement of the social and politic status of SCS reveals to be strategic for the promotion of social inclusion, equal opportunities, and justice among European citizens</p>
Further information	https://s2cene.eu/
Duration of the prog.	2020-2023

42. [FI] Heritage language classes

Thematic area of the good practice	Promoting inclusion in schools and society
Good practice title	Heritage language classes/Mother tongue education
Good practice content	<p>Everyone living in Finland has the right to preserve and develop their own heritage language/mother tongue and cultural identity. The aim of mother tongue education is to foster active multilingualism and spark a lasting interest in improving language skills. Learning one's native language also supports integration into Finnish society. Instruction is based on students' active participation, allowing them to draw on their language abilities and other strengths. Schools are encouraged to embrace and incorporate cultural and linguistic diversity across all activities.</p> <p>Opportunities for language development outside the classroom are also used to enhance learning. Students are encouraged to apply their own languages not only during language lessons but also across various subjects and other school settings.</p> <p>Mother tongue instruction can be provided when there are at least four students with the same language background in a municipality. Financial support is available for up to two hours of weekly instruction per qualifying group, continuing throughout the students' primary and lower secondary education.</p>
Financial data	Unavailable
Recommendations	-
Further information	https://www.oph.fi/en/education-and-qualifications/education-and-support-pupils-migrant-and-multilingual-background
Duration of the prog.	Incorporated into the national school curriculum in 1994, ongoing.

What SDG goals do it support?	SDG 4
Which sustainability dimensions does it cover?	Social Sustainability Cultural Sustainability

43. [BG] The world – I in it and it in me!

Title	Internship at the Vocational High School of Chemical and Food Technologies (PGHHT), Pazardzhik – "The world – I in it and it in me!"
Thematic area of the good practice	Educational Integration and Intercultural Competence Development of Students from Ethnic Minorities in the Context of School Education.
Good practice title	Innovative Approaches to Socialization and Intercultural Competence Development of Students from Ethnic Minorities through Non-Formal Educational Methods and Entrepreneurial Activities.
Good practice content	<p>The project "The world – I in it and it in me!" implemented at the Vocational High School of Chemical and Food Technologies (PGHHT) in Pazardzhik, Bulgaria, represents a comprehensive model for fostering the educational integration and socio-cultural competence of students from various ethnic backgrounds, notably Roma (57%), Turkish (18%), and Bulgarian (25%) communities. The practice is distinguished by its holistic approach that combines non-formal educational methods with social psychology, leadership development, and entrepreneurship education.</p> <p>Key components of the practice include:</p> <p>Conducting a specialized social psychology course titled "I, the person," which focuses on the dynamics of interpersonal and group relationships, motivations, and social behaviors, aiming to build communication skills, leadership, independence, and personal responsibility among students.</p> <p>Establishing a social theater initiative under the concept of a "Theater of Provocation," entitled "Socialize," aimed at enhancing civic engagement, human rights awareness, and the active socialization of students within their communities.</p> <p>Developing entrepreneurial projects like "My Bakery," which integrate business planning, marketing strategy, and real-life project execution, fostering creativity, initiative, and socio-economic skills.</p> <p>Organizing a public presentation event – the "Festival of Friendship – Blue Summer," involving students, parents, and the wider community, to showcase the outcomes of the project and reinforce the inclusion process.</p>

	<p>Applying diverse educational methods such as surveys, interviews, observation, social network content analysis, case studies, and game-based learning to support the experiential learning process.</p> <p>This multidimensional approach has contributed to:</p> <p>Reducing the risk of early school leaving.</p> <p>Strengthening intercultural dialogue and understanding among students.</p> <p>Promoting active citizenship and respect for diversity.</p> <p>Enhancing teacher competences for working in intercultural environments.</p> <p>Preserving and valuing cultural identities within the educational process.</p>
Financial data	<p>The project is financed by the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities, under a grant supporting activities fostering educational integration.</p> <p>Total participants: 30 students</p> <p>Project duration: 9 months</p> <p>Funding covers educational activities, training materials, project implementation, organization of public events, and dissemination activities. (Exact financial amounts are not explicitly provided in the source text.)</p>
Recommendations	<p>For Educational Institutions: Adopt comprehensive models that combine formal education with non-formal learning methods, specifically tailored to the socio-cultural characteristics of the student body, aiming at both academic and personal development.</p> <p>For Teachers and Trainers: Invest in continuous professional development focused on intercultural competence, inclusive teaching methods, and innovative educational tools.</p> <p>For Policymakers: Ensure sustainable funding mechanisms and supportive policies that promote intercultural dialogue, educational integration, and equal access to quality education for students from ethnic minorities.</p> <p>For Stakeholders: Encourage the involvement of families and communities in educational activities to enhance the impact and sustainability of integration efforts.</p>

	<p>For Project Implementers: Combine socio-psychological training with practical entrepreneurship projects and civic engagement initiatives to maximize student motivation and community impact.</p>
<p>Further information</p>	<p>Project updates and materials are regularly published on the PGHHT official website: PGHHT Website Link.</p> <p>Dissemination is ensured via publications by partner organizations, including Center Amalipe for Interethnic Dialogue and Tolerance, director meetings, national pedagogical conferences, and collaborative initiatives with other schools.</p> <p>Example of entrepreneurship project developed: “My Bakery” business initiative available at the school's website link provided above.</p> <p>The project has been recognized for its innovative approach within national educational networks.</p>
<p>Duration of the prog.</p>	<p>Total duration: 9 months</p> <p>The program includes sequential and integrated activities over this period, combining educational sessions, practical project development, and community events, aiming at sustained impact on students' socio-cultural competences and school environment improvement.</p>

44.[BG] My Future Starts Today

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>The thematic area of this good practice is "Educational Integration and Socialization of Students from Ethnic Minorities with a Focus on Roma Communities."</p> <p>The practice is directly related to the promotion of equal access to education, intercultural dialogue, and social inclusion. It addresses the challenges of educational segregation and supports the formation of civic, social, and intercultural competences among students belonging to ethnic minority groups, particularly Roma. It also fosters active citizenship, personal development, and inclusive educational practices.</p>
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>"From Margins to Opportunities: Integrated Educational Support for Roma Youth at 106th Primary School 'Grigoriy Tsamblak,' Sofia"</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The Good practice presents a comprehensive and multifaceted educational support model applied at 106th Primary School "Grigoriy Tsamblak," located in the "Vasil Levski" district of Sofia. Most students are of Roma origin, residing predominantly in the "Hristo Botev" neighborhood.</p> <p>The intervention is based on an integrated support approach aimed at ensuring access to value-oriented education and fostering the socialization of students from marginalized communities. The project encompasses the following key elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Psychological and Pedagogical Support: Provision of individual and group consultations with a psychologist, pedagogical counselor, and social skills trainer to support personal development, conflict resolution, and prosocial behavior. ● Creative Workshops for Personal and Intercultural Development: Activities dedicated to forming personal and ethno-cultural identity, enhancing knowledge in civic education, intercultural dialogue, health awareness, and environmental education. These workshops serve as a platform for creative expression, fostering a sense of belonging and mutual respect. ● Intercultural Exchange and Mobility: Organization of intercultural exchanges with students and teachers from other schools (notably with "Pencho Slaveikov" Primary School in Dimitrovgrad), promoting mutual understanding, exposure to different educational environments, and breaking social barriers.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Involvement of a Roma Educational Mediator: Appointment of a mediator from the Roma community to facilitate communication between the school, students, parents, and the community, thereby enhancing trust and participation. ● Extracurricular Club "Who am I?": Through this club, students engage in activities promoting civic competences, creative tasks, role-play, and discussions aimed at fostering national self-awareness, intercultural tolerance, and personal identity building. ● Use of Non-Formal Educational Methods: The project emphasizes non-formal learning by integrating interests, sports, organized recreation, and digital tools (including tablets), contributing to increased student motivation and improved educational outcomes. <p>The holistic approach of the project successfully blends formal education with non-formal and informal learning methods, focusing on individualized support, peer learning, intercultural dialogue, and active participation.</p>
Financial data	<p>While specific financial figures are not disclosed in the materials provided, it is known that the project was funded under the competitive procedure 33.18-2019 of the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM).</p> <p>This suggests that the funding covers activities such as human resources (psychologist, pedagogical counselor, mediator), materials for workshops, logistics for mobility and exchange activities, equipment for creative and digital workshops, and organizational costs related to extracurricular activities.</p> <p>The financing ensured sustainability and comprehensiveness of the interventions over the project period.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holistic Support Approach: Combining formal, non-formal, and informal learning interventions proves effective for the socialization and educational inclusion of Roma students. Other institutions may adopt a similar model emphasizing psychological support, creative workshops, and intercultural exchange. ● Involvement of Community Mediators: The appointment of an educational mediator from the local community enhances trust and strengthens the link between school and family, which is critical for sustaining student engagement.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fostering Intercultural Exchanges: Cross-school and cross-community mobility activities help students overcome social and territorial isolation and foster a sense of belonging within the broader civic community. ● Investing in Non-Formal Education: Extracurricular activities and clubs focused on civic, creative, and intercultural competences development are recommended as tools for enhancing student motivation and supporting socialization. ● Sustainable Partnerships: Collaborative work between schools, local authorities, civil society, and minority communities ensures the sustainability of such interventions.
Further information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Official Project Website of the School: https://106ou.info/proekti/proekt-az-ucha-az-uspyavam-finansiran-ot-coiduem-po-konkursna-procedura-33-18-2019.html ● Video Presentation of the Project on Facebook: https://bg-bg.facebook.com/100057156533652/videos/1696084914173622 <p>The project is part of a broader national strategy supported by CEICSEM, aiming to promote the educational integration of children and students from ethnic minorities in Bulgaria.</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>Although the exact duration of the project is not explicitly stated in the provided information, it is implemented under CEICSEM’s annual call for proposals, which typically spans one academic year (approximately 9 to 12 months).</p> <p>The nature of the activities — including regular extracurricular sessions, psychological-pedagogical support, creative workshops, and organized exchanges — suggests that the project was designed as a medium-term intervention aligned with the school calendar.</p>

45.[BG] Active Inclusion in the Preschool Education System

<p>Thematic area of the good practice</p>	<p>Good practice belongs to the thematic area of Early Childhood Education, Educational Inclusion, and Social Cohesion Policies.</p> <p>It focuses on ensuring equitable access to preschool education for children from vulnerable social, economic, and ethno-cultural backgrounds, particularly those living in poverty or belonging to minority communities. The practice directly addresses key challenges related to social integration, early childhood educational outcomes, and reducing the risk of educational exclusion through early intervention measures.</p> <p>Thematic priorities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early childhood development and education. • Social inclusion of children from vulnerable groups. • Prevention of discrimination and overcoming negative societal attitudes. • Strengthening institutional capacity for inclusive education. • Parental involvement and empowerment.
<p>Good practice title</p>	<p>“A Systematic Model for Active Inclusion in Preschool Education – Bridging Social Gaps through Early Educational Support in Bulgaria”</p>
<p>Good practice content</p>	<p>The project “Active Inclusion in the Preschool Education System” was implemented by the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Bulgaria (MES) in partnership with the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM/TSOIDUEM). The project was financed under the Operational Programme "Science and Education for Smart Growth" 2014–2020, with the MES acting as the contracting authority and project promoter.</p> <p>This large-scale, systemic initiative aimed to address the multifaceted causes of preschool educational exclusion among children from vulnerable groups. It focused on reducing the barriers related to socio-economic status, ethno-cultural background, and parental disengagement. The project's core elements included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of Additional Bulgarian Language Training: Tailored linguistic support for children whose mother tongue is different from

	<p>Bulgarian, promoting their integration into the educational system and enabling participation in peer activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>● Elimination of Financial Barriers: Full coverage of fees for full-day kindergarten attendance to remove economic constraints that often prevent families from enrolling their children in preschool education.</p> <p>● Parental Motivation and Engagement: Active involvement of parents through motivational activities, awareness-raising campaigns, and structured interventions to strengthen family-kindergarten cooperation.</p> <p>● Development of Specialized Methodology for Bulgarian Language Learning: Creation of a comprehensive methodology, including training for kindergarten teachers, ensuring both the quality of language acquisition processes and the sustainability of the intervention.</p> <p>● Early Identification of Learning Difficulties and Provision of Support: Introduction of screening tests for early detection of potential learning disabilities, coupled with individualized support mechanisms through the appointment of additional pedagogical staff.</p> <p>● Training for Pedagogical and Non-Pedagogical Staff: Building professional capacities of kindergarten teachers and non-pedagogical staff in methodologies for working with children and parents from vulnerable groups.</p> <p>● National Awareness Campaigns: Two national campaigns were conducted to motivate parents and reduce negative societal attitudes, thus fostering an inclusive environment and promoting the value of preschool education.</p> <p>● Development of a National Information System for Project Management: A digital platform offering registered users access to categorized educational materials—ranging from language exercises to game instructions—tailored by age group (3–4, 4–5, and 5–6 years old). This tool supports both educators and parents in enhancing children's learning experiences.</p> <p>● Parental Involvement at National Level: A total of 120 parental meetings were held across 28 regions, involving over</p>
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	<p>1000 parents, to discuss the benefits of preschool education and to encourage active parental participation.</p> <p>This multifaceted project represents a sustainable model for systemic support, addressing the root causes of preschool exclusion through a combination of financial support, capacity building, early intervention, and community engagement.</p>
Financial data	<p>The project was financed through the Operational Programme "Science and Education for Smart Growth" 2014–2020, managed at national level with European structural funding support.</p> <p>Although exact budgetary figures are not specified, the financial scope evidently covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and dissemination of specialized methodologies and training materials. • Fees for full-day kindergarten attendance for children from vulnerable groups. • Training sessions and capacity-building workshops for pedagogical and non-pedagogical staff. • National-level communication campaigns and community engagement events. • Development and maintenance of the Information System for project management. • Logistical and administrative support for regional and national project activities. <p>The scale and systemic nature of the project suggest a significant budget allocation, reflective of its multi-component interventions and nationwide reach.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt a Holistic Systemic Approach: Combining policy measures, financial support, professional training, and community engagement ensures a sustainable impact on preschool inclusion. • Invest in Early Language Support: Tailored language acquisition programs for children with a different mother

	<p>tongue are essential for their successful integration into the educational system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address Socio-Economic Barriers Directly: Removing financial obstacles by covering kindergarten fees facilitates access and prevents exclusion due to poverty. • Engage Parents as Active Stakeholders: Implement structured programs to motivate parents, emphasizing the long-term benefits of preschool education for their children’s development. • Institutionalize Early Detection Mechanisms: Implement screening tests in early childhood settings as standard practice for timely identification of learning needs. • Leverage Digital Platforms for Inclusive Education: Utilize information systems for resource dissemination, enabling easy access to learning materials and fostering broader stakeholder engagement. • Promote Awareness and Counteract Discrimination: Conduct targeted campaigns to overcome societal biases and promote the value of inclusive preschool education as a societal norm.
Further information	<p>Managing Authority Website (Operational Programme): https://www.eufunds.bg/en/opseig</p> <p>Information System for Project Management: Access provided via user registration (project-specific system developed under the initiative; details subject to official guidance by the MES and CEICSEM).</p> <p>Reference to the National Campaigns and Parental Involvement Activities: Further details are accessible via publications by the Ministry of Education and Science and the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities.</p>
Duration of the prog.	<p>Given its scale and integration into national policy, the project likely covered a three to five-year period, ensuring sufficient time for systemic capacity building and sustainable impact realization.</p>

Networks and Accreditation

46.[HU] The Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network (Zöld Óvoda Hálózat)

Thematic area of the good practice	Early childhood education, environmental awareness, and sustainability education
Level of the good practice	National – implemented in over 1,100 kindergartens across Hungary
Good practice title	The Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network (Zöld Óvoda Hálózat)
Good practice content	<p>The Hungarian Green Kindergarten Network is a nationally recognized and locally adaptable model for embedding sustainability in early childhood education. It emerged in the early 2000s as a grassroots initiative, led by environmentally committed educators and supported by the Hungarian ministries responsible for environmental protection and education. Recognizing the potential of kindergartens to lay the foundations of lifelong environmental awareness, a multi-stakeholder team, including experts from ministries and universities, developed a comprehensive framework for implementation.</p> <p>In 2006, the first national call for kindergartens to apply for the "Green Kindergarten" title was launched. To qualify, institutions had to demonstrate alignment with a 20-point criteria and indicator system that covers everything from teaching methods to infrastructure, community involvement, and sustainable resource use. These criteria were not intended to impose rigid rules but to inspire a holistic, developmentally appropriate approach to education for sustainable development (ESD).</p> <p>Green Kindergartens are places where environmental education is woven into daily life. Children learn through play, observation, and interaction with nature – planting herbs, feeding birds, sorting waste, and exploring local ecosystems. The activities are experiential and age-appropriate, fostering curiosity and care for the environment. Teachers are trained to apply child-centered, participatory, and inclusive methods. The program also emphasizes health, equity, and social-emotional learning as part of the sustainability mindset.</p> <p>What makes this practice especially impactful is its networked structure. Kindergartens that repeatedly demonstrate excellence can receive the "Permanent Green Kindergarten" title and serve as peer mentors or "pillar kindergartens." These institutions share resources – like a 400 pages organized collection of good practices, ready to be adapted -, organize open teaching sessions, and support newcomers through the application process. This</p>

	<p>mentoring system ensures quality, scalability, and transfer of knowledge across the country.</p> <p>Today, around 23% of all Hungarian kindergartens are part of the network. The initiative's longevity is supported by ongoing professional development opportunities, an interactive website with guidelines and tools, and periodic reviews of the criteria system to ensure relevance. Local adaptations are encouraged; for example, schools in mountainous regions might focus on forest biodiversity, while urban ones may explore waste reduction and community gardening.</p>
Financial data	Originally supported through environmental education funds, national budgets, and European funding schemes. While there is no standard budget line for participation, the program's strength lies in its low-cost, high-impact design: it builds on existing infrastructure, uses locally available materials, and relies heavily on in-kind contributions and educator initiative. Minimal funding is needed for initial training and materials; most activities are integrated into daily routines.
Recommendations	<p>The program's success lies in its balanced combination of national-level policy support and strong local ownership.</p> <p>For those aiming to implement a similar model, it is essential to adopt a whole-institution approach where sustainability is embedded not only in educational content but also in the daily operations, infrastructure, and community relationships of the kindergarten. A flexible yet structured framework, such as the 20-point criteria system used in Hungary, can guide schools through gradual development while allowing for local adaptation. It is also strongly recommended to create a system of recognition and mentorship, where experienced institutions support newcomers, and to ensure that national or regional bodies provide coordination, visibility, and minimal but reliable resources to sustain long-term engagement.</p>
Further information	https://zoldovoda.hu/publications-in-english
Duration of the program.	Started in 2006 and continuously ongoing

47. [HU] Hungary's Forest School Program (Erdei Iskola)

Thematic area of the good practice	Outdoor environmental education; experiential learning in natural settings; forest pedagogy
Level of the good practice	National – implemented across Hungary through certified Forest Schools, forestry associations, and national parks
Good practice title	Hungary's Forest School Program (Erdei Iskola)
Good practice content	<p>Erdei Iskola—literally “forest school”—is a well-established experiential learning model in Hungary where children spend a day or several days immersed in nature, typically within forests managed by forestry organizations or national parks. Its origins date back to the late 1980s with the first program at the Mogyoró Hill Forestry School (later renamed László Madas Forestry School), founded in 1988 near Visegrád</p> <p>Today, this site welcomes around 8,000 visitors annually and remains a flagship example of forest education. Participants engage in full-day or multi-day programs that blend guided nature walks, wildlife observation (including bird ringing), aquatic biology, traditional herb and mushroom foraging, crafts, and team-building challenges—all linked to environmental stewardship, forest ecology, and physical well-being</p> <p>Over 120 certified Forest Schools operate nationwide, offering flexible formats from half-day classes to week-long camps, often in partnership with forestry companies and national parks</p> <p>One exemplary program is offered by Pilisi Park Forestry Ltd. at Mogyoró Hill, which provides forest school experiences tailored for both young children and adult learners, including holistic forest kindergartens and thematic events such as bird-tracking and archery</p> <p>Curricula are carefully designed, with full-day programs often including multiple sessions per day inside the forest, complemented by reflective indoor workshops. Educators—often trained foresters or certified forest pedagogues—focus on stimulating curiosity, building real-world connections, and fostering eco-ethics and cooperation. Infrastructure investments by forestry associations and public environmental funds include forest education houses, viewing platforms, specialist trails, and educational signage.</p>
Financial data	Forest school programs in Hungary are largely implemented through partnerships between forestry companies, national parks, and individual schools. While past infrastructure developments—such as forest teaching centers and environmental

	education houses—have benefited from state and EU funding, including emissions trading revenues, there is currently no centrally coordinated national program overseeing forest schools. As such, the provision varies regionally and depends heavily on local initiatives.
Recommendations	Institutions seeking to implement a forest school model should envisage a multi-stakeholder structure where certified forest pedagogues team up with schools and education authorities to co-design multi-day, curriculum-linked outdoor modules. A national certification framework—backed by forestry associations—helps ensure consistency and quality across diverse settings.
Further information	https://iskolabanazerdo.hu/programunkrol https://xn--knyezetvdelem-jkb3r.hu/kornyezeti-nevelesi-programok-erdei-iskolak
Duration of the program.	continuous

48.[ES] Escoles Verdes

Thematic area of the good practice	Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) , with a focus on environmental awareness, active citizenship, and school-wide sustainability culture.
Good practice title	"Escoles Verdes: Building a Culture of Sustainability in Escola Pia de Catalunya"
Good practice content	<p>The <i>Escoles Verdes</i> (Green Schools) project is part of a broader regional program supported by the Catalan Government. Escola Pia de Catalunya has been an active participant in this initiative, with several of its schools officially recognized as <i>Escoles Verdes</i>.</p> <p>The program aims to integrate environmental education into the whole school system—curriculum, culture, and operations. Each participating school creates an Environmental Committee made up of students, teachers, and staff, which leads sustainability actions and tracks progress.</p> <p>Key activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing and implementing a School Sustainability Plan. ● Running environmental campaigns on waste reduction, energy saving, and water conservation. ● Promoting biodiversity through school gardens or green spaces. ● Encouraging student leadership and participation in ecological projects. ● Integrating sustainability topics into classroom projects and interdisciplinary units. <p>The project fosters long-term thinking, responsibility, and community involvement, supporting the formation of environmentally conscious</p>

	citizens.
Financial data	<p>The project is largely supported by internal school resources, with occasional funding or training opportunities provided by the Generalitat de Catalunya (Catalan Government). Participation does not require high financial investment, as many actions are low-cost and rely on the commitment of the school community.</p> <p>Estimated annual cost per school (depending on activities):</p> <p>Between €500 and €2,000</p> <p>Main costs: materials for campaigns, signage, gardening supplies, and training.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Start with small actions: Begin with simple, visible initiatives (e.g., energy-saving, recycling) to build momentum. ● Create a student-led committee: Empower students to take the lead in identifying sustainability issues and proposing solutions. ● Integrate sustainability across the curriculum: Encourage interdisciplinary work to connect sustainability with science, ethics, economics, etc. ● Collaborate with local community partners: Engage parents, local businesses, and municipal services for broader impact. ● Commit long-term: Sustainability culture takes time—embed it into the school mission and yearly planning.
Further information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generalitat de Catalunya – <i>Programa Escoles Verdes</i>: https://xtec.gencat.cat/ca/projectes/escoles-verdes/ ● Escola Pia de Catalunya – Sustainability Initiatives:

	https://www.escolapia.cat
Duration of the prog.	This is an ongoing program . Schools typically enter through a multi-year commitment, with annual evaluations and adjustments. Escola Pia schools have been part of the <i>Escoles Verdes</i> network since the early 2000s, and the program continues to evolve each year.

49.[FI] Green Flag Programme

Thematic area of the good practice	Recognition of sustainable practices in educational institutions
Good practice title	The Green Flag Programme
Good practice content	The Green Flag program promotes sustainable development in schools and kindergartens through provision of an eco-label. Institutions that fulfill specific criteria are awarded the right to display the 'Green Flag' as a symbol of their commitment to sustainability. The program emphasizes key principles such as involving children and youth in active participation, reducing environmental waste, incorporating sustainability into daily routines, striving for ongoing improvement, and engaging with the wider community. In Finland, the Foundation for Environmental Education has created tailored educational materials for the country's daycare and school systems based on this program
Financial data	Unavailable
Recommendations	<p>Proposed Launch of a sustainable school programme:</p> <p>Building a sustainable society requires credible and significant measures in education and training. To achieve this, more than 20 environmental education and training organizations are proposing the launch of a national Sustainable School program. In the program, learners in early childhood education, comprehensive schools, and secondary schools will be equipped to build a sustainable future. Ecological sustainability is the foundation of the program.</p> <p>The Sustainable School programme enables Finland to develop into a sustainable society. The programme is based on national and international environmental and educational policy guidelines and national curricula. The aim of the Sustainable School is to instill sustainable development knowledge, skills and practices into the operating culture and lesson content of daycare centers, comprehensive schools and secondary schools. The programme is modelled on the Mobile School programme.</p>

Further information	Green Flag: https://feesuomi.fi/tietoa-meista/
Duration of the prog.	Green Flag Programme: no specific duration, ongoing The proposed Sustainable Schools programme: 2024-2026
What SDG goals does it support?	SDG 4, SDG 7, SDG 12
Which sustainability dimensions does it cover?	Environmental sustainability

50.[RO] Eco-Schools Romania

Thematic area of the good practice	Whole-school sustainability, infrastructure development, curriculum integration, inclusive education
Good practice title	Eco-Schools Romania – Coordinated by CCDG
Good practice content	<p>Eco-Schools Romania, coordinated by Centrul Carpato-Danubian de Geoecologie (CCDG), is part of the international FEE (Foundation for Environmental Education) network promoting sustainable development through education. The program encourages schools to follow a structured seven-step process to implement sustainability across school life.</p> <p>Each participating school sets up an Eco-Committee (students, teachers, parents, and community members) to plan and implement sustainability actions related to themes like waste reduction, energy, water, biodiversity, and climate change. Progress is recognized through the Green Flag certification, a respected international symbol for environmental excellence.</p> <p>Over 300 schools in Romania currently participate, including rural and disadvantaged areas. CCDG supports schools with workshops, teacher training, national competitions, and learning resources. The program emphasizes student leadership and experiential learning.</p>
Financial data	The program is low-cost and scalable. Participating schools cover basic costs (e.g., posters, bins, gardening tools). CCDG secures support through partnerships, fundraising, and occasional public grants
Recommendations	<p>Ideal entry point for schools beginning sustainability work.</p> <p>Support schools with local mentoring to achieve Green Flag status.</p> <p>Encourage broader municipal support to align school actions with local sustainability goals.</p> <p>Translate Eco-Schools themes into curriculum units to support GreenComp integration.</p>
Further	https://www.ccdg.ro/

information	
Duration of the prog.	Active in Romania since early 2000s; ongoing.

51. [PT] Eco-Schools Programme

Thematic area of the good practice	Environmental education, citizenship, climate action
Good practice title	<p>Eco-Schools Programme</p> <p>A national programme encouraging schools to adopt sustainability projects such as organic gardens, marine protection, sustainable playgrounds, and clean air initiatives. Involves students in practical environmental actions.</p>
Good practice content	<p>The Eco-Schools initiative is a powerful example of how education can inspire real change at the local level. By weaving sustainability into the school curriculum through hands-on, cross-disciplinary projects, the program empowers students to take the lead. Using active learning strategies like Project-Based Learning and Service-Learning, it encourages learners not just to study environmental issues but to take meaningful action on them. From identifying local challenges to designing and carrying out solutions, students are at the heart of every step. This student-centered approach fosters a wide range of essential competencies—from active and democratic citizenship to environmental literacy, critical thinking, teamwork, and communication. It also promotes autonomy and a strong sense of responsibility.</p> <p>The methodology combines classroom learning with real-world impact. It connects academic subjects through interdisciplinary themes, encourages collaboration through Environmental Committees, and builds lasting partnerships between schools and local municipalities.</p> <p>The results speak for themselves: hundreds of schools proudly fly the Green Flag as a symbol of their commitment, and year after year, students and teachers lead environmental projects that leave a tangible mark on their communities. With high levels of engagement across schools, local authorities, and families, Eco-Schools is more than an educational program—it's a movement for sustainable change.</p>
Financial data	Funded by ABAE with co-funding from local municipalities, private sponsors, and school budgets.
Recommendations	Permanently integrate the program into school culture; Ensure continuous

	teacher training; Strengthen collaboration with municipalities and NGOs; Share outcomes and good practices with other schools
Further information	https://ecoescolas.abae.pt ; Database-for-1000-schools.pdf
Duration of the prog.	Since 1996 – ongoing

ON ▾ SCHOOLS AND MUNICIPALITIES ▾ ECO-CAMPUS ▾ PROJECTS ▾ MEETINGS ▾ HIGHLIGHTS ▾ RESOURCES ▾ LOGIN

THEMES OF THE YEAR
CLIMATE ACTION
OUTDOOR SPACES
BIODIVERSITY: PRESERVE AND REGENERATE

- Organic Gardens in Eco-Schools
- Pollinator Garden
- Recreational Life
- My School's Biodiversity
- My School's Biodiversity - Lesson Plan
- Eco-trails
- The Air I Breathe - JogAR
- The Air I Breathe Manifest
- The Air I Breathe - QualAR
- The Air I Breathe - Lesson Plan
- Living walls
- O MAR COMEÇA AQUI
The Sea Starts Here! (with municipality)
- #MARVIVO Brigade
- Ecopatios [closed]
- Take your class to the Oceanarium
- Microforests in Eco-Schools
- Mini COP
- Municipal Climate Action Route
- Tetrapak Challenge - Caring for Animals

52.[RO] Pilot Network of Green Schools (Romanian Recovery and Resilience Plan)

Thematic area of the good practice	Whole-school sustainability, infrastructure development, curriculum integration, inclusive education
Good practice title	Pilot Network of Green Schools (Romanian Recovery and Resilience Plan)
Good practice content	<p>This national initiative, funded through Romania’s Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), aims to develop a network of “Green Schools” that serve as models for environmental sustainability and inclusive education. The program targets the renovation and modernization of school buildings with energy efficiency upgrades (insulation, heating systems, solar panels), as well as curricular and organizational reforms to embed sustainability competences.</p> <p>Green Schools are expected to integrate education for sustainable development (ESD) into teaching methods, extracurricular activities, and school culture, following the European Green Deal and GreenComp framework. The initiative encourages whole-school approaches by involving teachers, students, parents, and local communities in sustainability actions.</p> <p>The pilot includes measures such as digital green literacy programs, eco-laboratories, climate-resilient school yards, and professional development for educators. It aims to reduce energy consumption while promoting inclusive, forward-looking learning environments, especially in underserved or disadvantaged areas.</p>
Financial data	Funded under Romania’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan (2022–2026), part of the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). Total education-related investments exceed €3.6 billion, with a significant portion allocated to school infrastructure and digital/green transformation.
Recommendations	<p>Prioritize scaling the pilot to rural and vulnerable communities.</p> <p>Combine infrastructure investments with mandatory teacher training in sustainability.</p> <p>Develop certification and mentoring systems to support new “green schools.”</p> <p>Encourage cross-sector collaboration with local governments and NGOs.</p>

Further information	
Duration of the prog.	2022–2026

53.[RO] AGLT – Youth-Driven Sustainability Education in Rural Romania

Thematic area of the good practice	Non-formal sustainability education, rural youth empowerment, environmental citizenship, inclusion
Good practice title	AGLT – Youth-Driven Sustainability Education in Rural Romania
Good practice content	<p>AGLT (Asociația Grupurilor Locale de Tineret) is a Romanian NGO with over 40 active youth groups across rural areas. Its mission is to empower young people through non-formal education focused on personal development, community involvement, and environmental responsibility.</p> <p>AGLT organizes thematic camps, workshops, and community challenges that promote sustainability competences aligned with the GreenComp framework. Activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental education games • Clean-up actions • Awareness campaigns • Creative recycling and upcycling workshops • Youth-led green initiatives <p>A key feature is the peer-education approach, where trained youth leaders (ages 16–22) facilitate local learning activities for younger peers and collaborate with schools, churches, and community centers. The model fosters collective action, civic engagement, and critical thinking, particularly in regions with limited access to formal sustainability education.</p> <p>AGLT also runs national youth events and international exchanges that further develop environmental citizenship and cross-cultural collaboration.</p>
Financial data	The organization operates primarily through volunteer networks , small local sponsorships , and support from programs like Erasmus+ Youth, Romanian Youth Foundation , and local councils . Activities are designed to be low-cost and highly adaptable.
Recommendations	<p>Strong model for community-based ESD outreach in areas underserved by formal education.</p> <p>Encourage partnerships between schools and AGLT groups.</p> <p>Can be replicated in other regions with minimal infrastructure.</p>

	Ideal for integrating youth voice into municipal environmental strategies.
Further information	http://aglt.org/
Duration of the prog.	Ongoing since 2000; expanding annually.

54.[BG] Sustainability: Growing with care

Thematic area of the good practice	Inclusion Sustainable education
Good practice title	Sustainability: Growing with care
Good practice content	<p>By supporting the EU’s sustainability goals and empowering local communities, this project “Sustainability: Growing with care” encourages youth workers to reach for sustainable development in their everyday practice.</p> <p>The project aims to equip youth workers with the knowledge and tools necessary to integrate sustainability into their work, especially about designing meaningful and engaging activities.</p> <p>The project seeks to inspire youth workers to incorporate more non-formal educational methods in their strategy for career development while consciously choosing long-lasting, low-impact practices.</p> <p>Through cross-border collaboration, the project aims to build networks that allow youth workers from different countries to share innovative strategies and good practices in sustainability.</p> <p>The project involves the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive workshops focused on conscious environmental, economic, and social practices • Training youth workers on how to design engaging and impactful activities tailored to their target groups • Youth workers collaborate to design sustainability-focused initiatives that they can implement in their own communities • Experience first-hand non-formal educational methods that can be transferred to their local realities
Financial data	Erasmus KA2
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't just treat sustainability as an add-on. Design all activities, from workshops to excursions, with environmental, economic, and social sustainability in mind. This includes choosing low-impact materials, promoting local economies, and fostering inclusive practices.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Continue to prioritize interactive, experiential, and participant-centered learning. These methods are highly effective for teaching complex concepts like sustainability and fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills. ● Create ongoing platforms (online forums, regular meetings, workshops) for youth workers to share successful sustainability initiatives, challenges, and lessons learned. This fosters continuous learning and adaptation. ● Implement simple yet effective methods to track the impact of sustainability-focused activities. This could include participant surveys, observation of behavioral changes, or tracking the reach of community initiatives. This data can be used to refine programs and demonstrate success.
Further information	https://mundusbulgaria.com/en/training-courses/sustainability-growing-with-care/
Duration of the prog.	2021-ongoing

55.[BG] From Inclusive Education to Real Scale Transfer (FIERST)

Thematic area of the good practice	Inclusive education
Good practice title	From Inclusive Education to Real Scale Transfer (FIERST)
Good practice content	<p>The project aims to pilot effective ways for upscaling good practices for inclusive education from innovative teachers at the regional, national, and European levels. The partners in the three pilot countries—Bulgaria, Estonia, and Romania—are working with mainstream teachers and are changing their mindsets by training and supporting them to create and run professional learning communities (PLCs) in their schools, and to apply at school-level good practices for inclusive education.</p> <p>During the workshop attendees learned more about the PLCs, the practices upscaled in each pilot country, effective interventions when training and supporting mainstream teachers, what made the consortium partnership effective, and how the project’s findings could be used at the broader European worldwide levels.</p>
Financial data	Erasmus+ KA3: Support for Policy reform
Recommendations	Ongoing investment and a broader approach to digital learning are needed for lasting impact. Deeper changes, such as transforming teaching methods and increasing parental involvement, were harder to achieve and required further attention. Many teachers needed more advanced training.
Further information	https://teachforromania.org/en/fierst/
Duration of the prog.	2017-2020

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